

1 **Purging the clarification on human CRISPRs**

2

3

4

5 Rogier Louwen ^{1*}, Sanne Voogd¹

6

7

8

9 ¹CCassured, Breda, The Netherlands

10

11

12

13

14 ***Corresponding author**

15 Dr. Rogier Louwen, CCassured, Breda, The Netherlands

16 Email: r.louwen@ccassured.com

17 Phone: 00-31-(0) 6-43509279

18 <https://ccassured.com/>

19

20

21

22

23

24 In 2022, a discussion emerged on the potential presence of CRISPR-Cas systems in eukaryotes^{1,2}.
25 Ancestors of Cas9, a IscB protein family, encoded by transposons, genetic elements that can move
26 within the genome and into new genomes were also discovered in Eukaryotes². Moreover, IscB was
27 found to use single non-coding RNAs for a RNA-guided cleavage of double-stranded DNA and was
28 identified in all domains of life^{1,2}. In that same year putative CRISPR-like elements were reported to
29 exist in the human genome (hCRISPRs) and e.g., other chordate animals³. Some of them were even
30 found to be accompanied with putative *cas* genes or remnants thereof, further fueling the discussion
31 on the existence of complete CRISPR-Cas operons in the eukaryotic genome³. In line with the
32 transposon mediated mobility of CRISPR-Cas operons, it was revealed, that a Type I-E CRISPR-Cas
33 system from *Escherichia coli*, when introduced in the eukaryote *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*,
34 demonstrated functional interference. Concluding that prokaryotic CRISPR-Cas systems in eukaryotic
35 cells can be functional⁴, for example, when acquired by horizontal gene transfer.

36 Work by Wiedenheft and colleagues further nurtures the debate on the presence or absence
37 of CRISPR-Cas systems in eukaryotic cells⁵. The reported findings of hCRISPRs³ in the eukaryotic
38 genome came as a surprise to the authors leading them to ask a justified question why these elements
39 might have been missed in the past⁵. In the hCRISPR related publication potential reasons for missing
40 such elements are extensively discussed³. Moreover, examples were given such as that the CRISPR-Cas
41 searching software algorithms might miss the repeat – spacer - repeat elements with four repeats or
42 less, including missing the detection of more flexible repeats, as observed in archaea³. In both papers
43 it is also discussed that the software algorithms can misinterpreted CRISPR arrays^{3,5}. Indeed, a few
44 examples are presented and suggestively used to generate the impression that CRISPR arrays are not
45 to be confused with human repeats⁵.

46 In the work of Wiedenheft and colleagues an original putative hCRISPR array was studied in
47 more detail. Strikingly, their work lead to question their own findings and interpretations⁵, since the
48 authors had to admit that strong characteristics of a repeat – spacer - repeat architecture was present
49 in this putative hCRISPR with substantial similarities as found in prokaryotic CRISPR arrays⁵. On the
50 contrary, to weaken this observation Wiedenheft and colleagues stated that the analysed putative
51 hCRISPR array lacks accompanying *cas* genes. This is not a strong case, since in the CRISPR-Cas
52 literature it is extensively discussed that CRISPR arrays and *cas* genes are two separate systems that
53 have been shown to be functional on their own or together, as highlighted in³. Moreover, although
54 lacking in the discussion by Wiedenheft and colleagues⁵, the role of the human repeats was extensively
55 analysed in relation to the putative hCRISPRs³. Actually, it was revealed that a substantial number of
56 the putative hCRISPRs cannot be traced back to any known human repeat signature³. Interestingly,
57 Wiedenheft and colleagues did confirm the identification of these putative hCRISPRs by using the latest
58 versions of the CRISPR-Cas identification software tools, CRISPRCasFinder⁶, CasFinder⁷,
59 CRISPRCasTyper⁸ and CRISPRDetect⁹ and even reported additional ones⁵. CasFinder⁷ wasn't used in the
60 original paper, but the older version of the CRISPRFinder was applied instead^{3,10}. Variation between
61 the two studies was found and as claimed in both studies, it is more than likely that minor changes in
62 the search settings of the CRISPR-Cas identification software tools affect the output results^{3,5}.
63 Moreover, Wiedenheft and colleagues claim that in the original paper the evidence level of the
64 identified putative hCRISPR arrays was not reported. But, we noticed in the supplementary data 1, see
65 MOESM4 “overview of the human related CRISPR array findings”, that the final column of the
66 CRISPRCasFinder⁶ data section reports the evidence level of the identified putative hCRISPRs³.

67 The validity of the reported *cas* gene presence in the human genome was also inspected by
68 Wiedenheft and colleagues. The authors focused on the reported hCRISPRs that were discussed in
69 MOESM 6³, showing a subset of hCRISPRs being flanked by putative one or multiple *cas* gene signatures

70 (E-value < 10⁻⁵), which were identified in both the coding and non-coding genome by using the old
71 CRISPRFinder¹⁰ tool (**Supplementary Data 1**).

72 Although stated by Wiedenheft and colleagues that the finding presented in MOESM 6 (Supplementary
73 Data 3) was about complete CRISPR-Cas operons, we could not find this type of remarks in this table³.
74 Instead, it was reported that the putative *cas* genes identified in the non-coding genome are
75 potentially *cas* gene “**signatures or remnants**” and thus not established functional *cas* genes, let alone
76 complete functional CRISPR-Cas open reading frames. These potential *cas* gene “**signatures or**
77 **remnants**” were often accompanied with LINE-1 transposons and the reverse transcriptase RVT_1
78 (PF00078) known of being fused to the *cas1* of *Marinomonas mediterranea*³. This identification
79 occurred by analysing the 20.000bp regions flanking the putative hCRISPR on both sides of the array
80 and the 3D blast tool of the Expasy software or myhits motif tool³. Moreover, the updated version of
81 the CRISPRFinder⁶, also identified two *cas* genes of which one is presented in this work as an example
82 (**Figure 1**)³ and a putative CRISPR-Cas Type I-B operon as identified by CRISPRCasTyper³ is visualized
83 using the original output as an example (**Figure 2**). The Hg38 genome and the updated version of the
84 human genome T2T were analysed using HMMER and we found *cas* gene signatures with a E-value
85 that were much lower than the cut-off (E-value < 10⁻⁵) as set by Wiedenheft and colleagues
86 (**Supplementary Data 3 & 4**), contradicting their finding.

87 We do find agreement with some of the comments raised by Wiedenheft and colleagues. For
88 example, it is discussed whether the algorithms should be optimized to identify putative CRISPR-Cas
89 systems that might be hidden in other eukaryotic genomes^{1,2,3}, but also to remove software related
90 flawed results. From a therapeutic angle as discussed by Zhang and colleagues² our finding of putative
91 CRISPR arrays, *cas* genes and CRISPR-Cas systems in the eukaryotic genome is of interest. For example,
92 bacterial and archaeal Cas proteins might trigger immune responses^{11,12}, when directly used in the
93 human host. Moreover, CRISPR-Cas genome editing tools are linked to off-target effects, when applied
94 for therapeutic purposes¹³⁻¹⁵, for which the (putative) eukaryotic Cas proteins might provide a
95 solution^{1,2}. New options might also be opened by exploring the putative eukaryotic Cas proteins for
96 diagnostic applications as currently initiated by us. Overall, the work of Wiedenheft and colleagues is
97 certainly appreciated and the findings in the original paper were open for discussion and falsification
98 to move forward the mining of putative CRISPR-Cas systems in eukaryotes¹⁻³. In the end, when the
99 existence of eukaryotic CRISPR-Cas systems will become functionally established¹⁻³, it can certainly
100 bring new positive contributions to the health of mankind.

101

102

103

104

105

106

107 **References**

- 108 1. Karvelis, T. *et al.* Transposon-associated TnpB is a programmable RNA-guided DNA
109 endonuclease. *Nature* **599**, 692–696 (2021).
- 110 2. Altae-Tran, H. *et al.* The widespread IS200/IS605 transposon family encodes diverse
111 programmable RNA-guided endonucleases. *Science* **374**, 57–65 (2021).
- 112 3. van Riet, J. *et al.* CRISPRs in the human genome are differentially expressed between
113 malignant and normal adjacent to tumor tissue. *Commun. Biol.* **5**, 338 (2022).
- 114 4. Bindal, G., Amlinger, L., Lundgren, M. & Rath, D. Type I-E CRISPR-Cas System as a Defense
115 System in *Saccharomyces cerevisiae*. *mSphere* **7**, e0003822 (2022).
- 116 5. Buyukyoruk, M., Henriques, W. S. & Wiedenheft, B. Clarifying CRISPR: Why Repeats Identified
117 in the Human Genome Should Not Be Considered CRISPRs. *Cris. J.* (2023)
118 doi:10.1089/crispr.2022.0106.
- 119 6. Couvin, D. *et al.* CRISPRCasFinder, an update of CRISRFinder, includes a portable version,
120 enhanced performance and integrates search for Cas proteins. *Nucleic Acids Res.* (2018)
121 doi:10.1093/nar/gky425.
- 122 7. Aach, J., Mali, P. & Church, G. M. CasFinder: Flexible algorithm for identifying specific Cas9
123 targets in genomes. *bioRxiv* (2014) doi:10.1101/005074.
- 124 8. Russel, J., Pinilla-Redondo, R., Mayo-Muñoz, D., Shah, S. A. & Sørensen, S. J. CRISPRCasTyper:
125 Automated Identification, Annotation, and Classification of CRISPR-Cas Loci. *Cris. J.* **3**, 462–
126 469 (2020).
- 127 9. Biswas, A., Staals, R. H. J., Morales, S. E., Fineran, P. C. & Brown, C. M. CRISPRDetect: A flexible
128 algorithm to define CRISPR arrays. *BMC Genomics* **17**, 356 (2016).
- 129 10. Grissa, I., Vergnaud, G. & Pourcel, C. CRISPRFinder: a web tool to identify clustered regularly
130 interspace short palindromic repeats. *Nucleic Acids Res.* **35**, 52–57 (2007).
- 131 11. Roy, S. Immune responses to CRISPR-Cas protein. *Prog. Mol. Biol. Transl. Sci.* **178**, 213–229
132 (2021).
- 133 12. Crudele, J. M. & Chamberlain, J. S. Cas9 immunity creates challenges for CRISPR gene editing
134 therapies. *Nat. Commun.* **9**, 3497 (2018).
- 135 13. Saha, C. *et al.* Guide-free Cas9 from pathogenic *Campylobacter jejuni* bacteria causes severe
136 damage to DNA. *Sci. Adv.* **6**, eaaz4849 (2020).
- 137 14. Enache, O. M. *et al.* Cas9 activates the p53 pathway and selects for p53-inactivating
138 mutations. *Nat. Genet.* **52**, 662–668 (2020).
- 139 15. Haapaniemi, E., Botla, S., Persson, J., Schmierer, B. & Taipale, J. CRISPR–Cas9 genome editing
140 induces a p53-mediated DNA damage response. *Nat. Med.* **1** (2018) doi:10.1038/s41591-018-
141 0049-z.

142

143 **Acknowledgements**

144 Rogier Louwen and Sanne Voogd are Ultimate Beneficial Owners of CCassured and both receive
145 supporting funding from the EU H2020 project ONCOSCREEN entitled A European “shield” against
146 colorectal cancer based on novel, more precise and affordable risk-based screening methods and
147 viable policy pathways under the Grant agreement with ID: 101097036. We also like to acknowledge
148 Yassir Halimi for his contributing HMM analyses during his internship earlier.

149

150 **Figures**

151 **A**

CRISPRCasFinder [online]

152

153 **B**

CRISPRCasFinder [online]

154

155 **Figure 1 A putative cas3 gene is identified in chromosome Y. A)** Using the latest version of the
 156 CRISPRCasFinder and the Hg19 human genome or **B)** the Hg38 human genome reference sequences,
 157 a putative cas3 gene was identified flanking the putative hCRISPR encoded as chrY_33, see
 158 supplementary data 1³.

159

160

161

162

163

164

165

166

167

168 **Figure 2 putative CRISPR-Cas operons are identified in the human genome.** Using the CRISPR-Cas
 169 Typer software tool, twelve CRISPR-Cas operons were identified in the Hg38 human genome reference
 170 sequence earlier. Two putative CRISPR-Cas operons are presented of which one was linked to a Type
 171 I-B system signature, in which the reverse transcriptase (pfam00078) that often accompanies *cas1*,
 172 was prominently present. The other operon was unknown and was identified on chromosome X. This
 173 figure relates to Supplementary Figure 3C³ and the role of pfam00078 (reverse transcriptase) is
 174 extensively discussed in ref³. **Supplementary Data 2** reveals the HMM output related to this operon.

175

176 **Supplementary Data 1 Examples of putative hCRISPRs that were flanked in the non-coding genome**
 177 **with putative *cas* genes as detected with the older version of the CRISPRFinder software tool**
 178 **(PMCID: PMC1933234)**

179 **CRISPR ID: chrX_200**

CRISPR id : tmp_1_PossibleCrispr_47

- CRISPR start position : 15804342 ----- CRISPR end position : 15804465 ----- CRISPR length : 123
- DR consensus : TTATACTTTTATACATATATACTAAAAGTAAAAACA
- DR length : 39 Number of spacers : 1

15804342	TTATACTTTTATACATATATACTAAAAGTAAAAACA	TCCATGGGAAATTAATTCPCRNATATATAGPSTTAAAAATATATTC	15804426
15804427	TTATACTTTTATACATATATACTAAAAGTAAAAACA		15804465

Display spacers Crispr Properties Search the local cas bank search encoded proteins

180 Putative *cas* gene sequences producing significant alignments: Q7MTH7_PORGI CRISPR-associated protein Cas1 tax=Porphyromonas
 181 gingivalis, Length = 1031 score = 52.4 bits (124), Expect = 1e-06 Identities = 38/152 (25%), Positives = 74/152 (48%) Frame = +2
 182
 183

184 **CRISPR ID: chr3_386**

CRISPR id : tmp_1_PossibleCrispr_26

- CRISPR start position : 7044709 ----- CRISPR end position : 7044838 ----- CRISPR length : 129
- DR consensus : TATAATTTTATCATTTCAGAAATGTTACAGAAATGGAAT
- DR length : 39 Number of spacers : 1

7044709	TATAATTTTATCATTTCAGAAATGTTACAGAAATGGAAT	CATACAATGTAACCTTGGGATTACCCAGCACCAATTCATCTGTCCTCCATTTT	7044799
7044800	TATAATTTTATCATTTCAGAAATGTTACAGAAATGGAAT		7044838

Display spacers Crispr Properties Search the local cas bank search encoded proteins

186 Putative *cas* gene sequences producing significant alignments: Q7MTH7_PORGI CRISPR-associated protein Cas1 tax=Porphyromonas
 187 gingivalis Length = 1031 Score = 49.7 bits (117), Expect = 7e-06 Identities = 37/156 (23%), Positives = 73/156 (46%) Frame = +3
 188

189 **CRISPR ID: chrX_236**

CRISPR id : tmp_1_PossibleCrispr_23

- CRISPR start position : 12094104 ----- CRISPR end position : 12094196 ----- CRISPR length : 92
- DR consensus : TCTGATTGGTTGCAGAAAGCAAC
- DR length : 23 Number of spacers : 1

12094104	TCTGATTGGTTGCAGAAAGCAAC	AATCAGAGGCTGAAGTGAAGTTACAAAGTCACACTCCATATSCRAACA	12094173
12094174	TCTGATTGGTTGCAGAAAGCAAC		12094196

Display spacers Crispr Properties Search the local cas bank search encoded proteins

190 Putative *cas* gene sequences producing significant alignments: B8GB51_CHLAD Cmr1_family CRISPR-associated RAMP protein tax=Bacteria
 191 Length = 495 Score = 63.2 bits (152), Expect = 5e-10 Identities = 51/162 (31%), Positives = 68/162 (41%), Gaps = 10/162 (6%) Frame = +3
 192
 193

194 **CRISPR ID: chr22_133**

CRISPR id : tmp_1_PossibleCrispr_28

- CRISPR start position : 7418052 ----- CRISPR end position : 7418165 ----- CRISPR length : 113
- DR consensus : AGGTCTGAGAGGGCAGGGGTCTCCCTGACCAGCCCTGCC
- DR length : 41 Number of spacers : 1

7418052	AGGTCTGAGAGGGCAGGGGTCTCCCTGACCAGCCCTGCC	GGTAGCCAGGAACTGCTTTGTCTAGGAGG	7418124
7418125	AGGTCTGAGAGGGCAGGGGTCTCCCTGACCAGCCCTGCC		7418165

Display spacers Crispr Properties Search the local cas bank search encoded proteins

196 Multiple putative *cas* gene sequences producing significant alignments: B8GB51_CHLAD::Cmr1_family CRISPR-associated RAMP protein
 197 tax=Bac... 87 9e-18 B8GB48_CHLAD::Cmr4_family CRISPR-associated RAMP protein tax=Bac... 55 1e-07 O2AM5_SOLUE::Csm2_family
 198 CRISPR-associated protein tax=Solibact... 47 7e-06 >B8GB51_CHLAD::Cmr1_family CRISPR-associated RAMP protein tax=Bacteria Length
 199 = 495 Score = 87.4 bits (215), Expect = 9e-18 Identities = 47/126 (37%), Positives = 73/126 (57%), Gaps = 2/126 (1%) Frame = +2
 200
 201

202

203 **CRISPR ID: chr22_160 (coding genome)**

CRISPR id : tmp_1_PossibleCrispr_51

- CRISPR start position : 9579189 ----- CRISPR end position : 9579291 ----- CRISPR length : 102
- DR consensus : AATAGGATTAAAAATGGCCAATTA
- DR length : 25 Number of spacers : 1

9579189	AATAGGATTAAAAATGGCCAATTA	TCAGATTCTGACCAGATGATCCTTCCCCCTGCGGCCCCAGCCTATCAITTCAT	9579266
9579267	AATAGGATTAAAAATGACCCAATTA		9579291

204 Multiple putative *cas* gene sequences producing significant alignments: (bits) Value B8GB51_CHLAD::Cmr1_family CRISPR-associated RAMP
 205 protein tax=Bac...82 4e-16 B8GB48_CHLAD::Cmr4_family CRISPR-associated RAMP protein tax=Bac... 60 2e-09.
 206 >B8GB51_CHLAD::Cmr1_family CRISPR-associated RAMP protein tax=Bacteria Length = 495 Score = 82.0 bits (201), Expect = 4e-16 Identities
 207 = 68/195 (34%), Positives = 70/195 (35%) Frame = +3
 208
 209

210 **CRISPR ID: chr15_50 (coding genome)**

CRISPR id : tmp_1_PossibleCrispr_34

- CRISPR start position : 8753729 ----- CRISPR end position : 8753829 ----- CRISPR length : 100
- DR consensus : CTGCCTCAGCCTCCTGAGTAGCT
- DR length : 23 Number of spacers : 1

8753729	CTGCCTCAGCCTCCTGAGTAGCT	AGCATTAGAGGTGCCCGCCCACTACCCCTCCGCTTCAGGTTCAAGCSATCCT	8753806
8753807	CTGCCTCAGCCTCCTGAGTAGCT		8753829

212
 213 Multiple putative *cas* gene sequences producing significant alignments: (bits) Value B8GB48_CHLAD::Cmr4_family CRISPR-associated
 214 RAMP protein tax=Bac... 80 1e-15 A7NKP9_ROSCS::Csm5_family CRISPR-associated RAMP protein tax=Ros... 49 6e-06
 215 >B8GB48_CHLAD::Cmr4_family CRISPR-associated RAMP protein tax=Bacteria Length = 449 Score = 80.5 bits (197), Expect = 1e-15
 216 Identities = 56/124 (45%), Positives = 69/124 (55%), Gaps = 1/124 (0%) Frame = +2
 217

218
219

Supplementary Data 2 related HMM results for putative CRISPR-Cas operon chrX:83545604 - 8355571

Figure 2 related HMM results

Hmm	ORF	flen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Acc	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Case6_0_CAS-I-III-B	chrX:139086277-139096427_1	68	282.0.021	11.6	1717	1920	chrX:139086277-139096427	1.0	1.5735294117647058	0.13829787234042554	-	
Cmf5_1_HIC	chrX:155372216-155382287_1	76	178.0.0.2	9.3	365	592	chrX:155372216-155382287	1.0	0.5394736842105263	0.2303370786516854	-	
Cmf5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chrX:145079236-145089333_1	126	180.8.8	3.9	933	1310	chrX:145079236-145089333	1.0	0.5238055238055238	0.2722222222222222	-	
Cmf5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chrX:91824209-91843339_1	102	180.0.23	9.1	586	788	chrX:91824209-91843339	1.0	0.5104166666666666	0.4	-	
CorA_1_CAS-III-B	chrY:19035005-19045086_1	96	125.0.076	10.7	630	917	chrY:19035005-19045086	1.0	0.6666666666666666	0.496	-	
Cxv1_5_CAS-III	chrX:126369696-126379827_1	171	132.0.036	12.0	103	615	chrX:126369696-126379827	1.0	0.38596491228070173	0.5	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:102418434-102428541_1	537	298.9.6e-09	32.3	63	1673	chrX:102418434-102428541	1.0	0.3258845476163687	0.5302013422818792	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:146901839-146912019_1	125	298.0.0019	15.0	483	857	chrX:146901839-146912019	1.0	0.552	0.234893988590504	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:83545604-8355571_1	667	298.5.3e-12	43.0	1	2001	chrX:83545604-8355571	1.0	0.32083958020899506	0.6375838926174496	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:14460054-14470160_1	52	298.0.007	13.1	1221	1376	chrX:14460054-14470160	1.0	0.445	0.13087248322147652	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:102418434-102428541_1	537	213.1.8e-45	153.0	63	1673	chrX:102418434-102428541	1.0	0.72020297951582865	0.934272304694836	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:107958587-107958785_1	171	213.2.4e-12	44.7	1	513	chrX:107958587-107958785	1.0	0.3742690058479552	0.2816014084507044	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:12185400-12195472_1	164	213.1.9e-18	64.7	4088	4579	chrX:12185400-12195472	1.0	0.981707317031707	0.7183098591549254	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:122283947-122294023_1	86	213.1.1e-05	22.9	2	259	chrX:122283947-122294023	1.0	0.5465116279069767	0.21596244134556	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:146901839-146912019_1	125	213.1.5e-20	71.6	483	857	chrX:146901839-146912019	1.0	0.984	0.5164319248826291	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:82575296-82585427_1	157	213.2.4e-06	26.1	1697	2167	chrX:82575296-82585427	1.0	0.3821666050954414	0.25821596244131456	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:83545604-8355571_1	667	213.3.40E-37	178.2	2001	chrX:83545604-8355571	1.0	0.3853073463268366	1.0	-		
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:85654238-85664313_1	79	213.5.6e-05	20.6	349	585	chrX:85654238-85664313	1.0	0.797468544303798	0.26291079812206575	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:14460054-14470160_1	52	213.2.4e-05	21.9	1221	1376	chrX:14460054-14470160	1.0	0.6923076923076923	0.16901408450704225	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:24907918-24918015_1	104	213.2.4e-06	25.1	5171	5482	chrX:24907918-24918015	1.0	0.6826923076923077	0.300469485680751	-	
Cas10e_0_CAS-V-F	chrX:115231510-11523598_2	135	587.0.0027	14.4	4224	4628	chrX:115231510-11523598	1.0	0.4444444444444444	0.1022146507656098	-	
Cmf5gr11_10_CAS-III-B	chrX:14506770-14516910_2	134	146.0.0038	15.1	2186	2587	chrX:14506770-14516910	1.0	0.244426582089552388	0.253426573542466	-	
Csb1gr7_0_CAS-I-U	chrX:107943989-107954114_2	130	109.0.0063	14.1	1493	1882	chrX:107943989-107954114	1.0	0.2486153846153846	0.3727810650887574	-	
Cxv1_7_CAS-III	chrX:6645458-6655587_2	93	309.1.0.7	5.9	2441	2719	chrX:6645458-6655587	1.0	0.568982471182796	0.2330097873786409	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:126369696-126379827_1	171	298.0.0092	16.0	3698	4036	chrX:126369696-126379827	1.0	0.7017538569649122	0.248321216510067	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:14460054-14470160_2	202	298.0.0038	14.0	1377	1982	chrX:14460054-14470160	1.0	0.4554545454545454	0.268456735892662	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:107943989-107954114_2	130	213.4.1e-18	63.6	1493	1882	chrX:107943989-107954114	1.0	0.8538461538461538	0.46009386713615	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:12664002-12670503_2	623	213.0.0028	18.4	3147	3755	chrX:12664002-12670503	1.0	0.35960591133004927	0.26291079812206575	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:123292341-2330020_2	104	213.2.4e-06	25.1	5171	5482	chrX:123292341-2330020	1.0	0.88059149122807173	0.25511533996103	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:2524546-25253655_2	179	213.6.6e-08	20.2	3820	3156	chrX:2524546-25253655	1.0	0.4022234687820077	0.4540724253140878	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:146901839-146912019_2	205	213.9.7e-10	36.2	967	2241	chrX:146901839-146912019	1.0	0.18352941176470589	0.2769530513641925	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:12602201-12612314_2	300	213.1.2e-16	58.7	1831	2730	chrX:12602201-12612314	1.0	0.6066666666666666	0.7323943661971831	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:14460054-14470160_2	202	213.2.8e-17	60.8	1377	1982	chrX:14460054-14470160	1.0	0.2439603960396039	0.4553990610328687	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:23292341-2330020_2	104	213.2.4e-06	25.1	5171	5482	chrX:23292341-2330020	1.0	0.6823076923076923	0.300469485680751	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:2524546-25253655_2	179	213.6.6e-08	20.2	3820	3156	chrX:2524546-25253655	1.0	0.4022234687820077	0.4540724253140878	-	
Cas10e_0_CAS-V-F	chrX:151549949-151560056_2	92	139.0.017	13.8	2495	2770	chrX:151549949-151560056	1.0	0.2733812949640281	0.2733812949640281	-	
Cas5_0_IA	chrX:146861418-146871494_3	75	173.0.024	12.3	4564	4788	chrX:146861418-146871494	1.0	0.3048	0.2080924855491296	-	
Cmf5gr11_10_CAS-III-B	chrX:12602201-12612314_3	234	146.0.0022	12.6	3202	3903	chrX:12602201-12612314	1.0	0.34102564102564102	0.22602739726027396	-	
Cmf5gr11_10_CAS-III-B	chrX:124950915-124975912_3	144	146.0.002	12.1	3116	3817	chrX:124950915-124975912	1.0	0.4085111111111111	0.2452344537882466	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:20328295-20338381_3	616	298.2.00E-17	47.2	7022	8669	chrX:20328295-20338381	1.0	0.347400259740025974	0.64093959731543203	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:90738081-90771056_3	254	298.4.00E-09	33.6	7901	8662	chrX:90738081-90771056	1.0	0.6181102362204725	0.4697986577181268	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:13551138-13561410_3	440	298.0.0051	16.8	8722	10091	chrX:13551138-13561410	1.0	0.2	0.250335530407899	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:12664002-12670503_2	623	213.6.8e-21	79.2	3885	4599	chrX:12664002-12670503	1.0	0.5732333333333334	0.5211167605539879	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:20328295-20338381_3	616	213.5.0E-38	177.6	7022	8669	chrX:20328295-20338381	1.0	0.4412077922077922	1.0	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:83730087-83740186_3	50	213.6.6e-06	20.7	4782	4931	chrX:83730087-83740186	1.0	0.376	0.178403758685446	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:88792064-88802161_3	107	213.1.6e-10	38.8	1272	1592	chrX:88792064-88802161	1.0	0.9532710280373832	0.43661971803985913	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:89023935-89034032_3	212	213.5.4e-13	46.9	4183	4818	chrX:89023935-89034032	1.0	0.8962264150943396	0.7464788723294366	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:146901839-146912019_2	205	213.7.0E-16	39.1	7801	8662	chrX:146901839-146912019	1.0	0.758249168686044	0.7511737889291878	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:92438163-92448268_3	141	213.6.3e-05	20.5	5891	6313	chrX:92438163-92448268	1.0	0.3159730964539007	0.253521126705634	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:13551138-13561410_3	440	213.6.2e-23	79.3	8722	10091	chrX:13551138-13561410	1.0	0.3927722727272727	0.49295774647887325	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:23118372-23128468_3	104	213.2.4e-06	25.1	4615	4926	chrX:23118372-23128468	1.0	0.6826923076923077	0.300469485680751	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:12664002-12670503_2	623	213.2.4e-06	25.1	4615	4926	chrX:12664002-12670503	1.0	0.6826923076923077	0.300469485680751	-	
Cas10_1_HIB	chrX:21896555-21906624_4	80	116.0.038	12.1	7391	7630	chrX:21896555-21906624	1.0	0.4525	0.344827586208966	-	
Cmf5_1_HIC	chrX:11204547-112114623_4	92	178.3.2	5.4	6505	6780	chrX:11204547-112114623	1.0	0.673913043782609	0.34831460674157305	-	
Cmf5_1_HIC	chrX:19035005-19045086_4	223	178.9.8	3.8	2483	3151	chrX:19035005-19045086	1.0	0.44733623286995514	0.5842696629213483	-	
Cmf5gr11_10_CAS-III-B	chrX:14506770-14516910_4	134	146.0.002	12.6	3202	3903	chrX:14506770-14516910	1.0	0.275362318862597	0.235244537882466	-	
Cmf5gr11_2_CAS-III-B	chrX:24045448-24055555_4	104	138.0.019	13.0	7177	7488	chrX:24045448-24055555	1.0	0.4423076923076923	0.3333333333333333	-	
PIW1_0_CAS-III-AM	chrX:1182787-11829234_4	329	641.0.001	15.4	1889	2875	chrX:1182787-11829234	1.0	0.46504559270516715	0.045241809672399	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:11834083-11844252_4	635	298.0.0013	18.8	6974	8878	chrX:11834083-11844252	1.0	0.41417328346456693	0.2617496642595303	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:122283947-122294023_4	88	298.0.011	12.5	3299	3562	chrX:122283947-122294023	1.0	0.2954554545454545	0.087248321476517	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX:14506770-14516910_4	134	298.0.012	12.6	3864	4681	chrX:14506770-14516910	1.0	0.36047619047619047	0.247621807114493	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:11681938-116829451_4	65	213.7.6e-07	26.3	3154	3864	chrX:11681938-116829451	1.0	0.4786153846153846	0.2300469485680751	-	
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-V-V	chrX:11834083-11844252_4											

221 **Supplementary Data 3 related HMM results obtained after analysis from the Hg38 genome**

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas2_7_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr7_KI270807v1_alt_7	281	94	1.9e-07	23.9	13219	14061	7	0.5373665480427047	0.20212765957446807	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas11_0_IV	chr8_KI270818v1_alt_104	182	114	0.0027	10.5	132813	133358	104	0.2087912087912088	0.21929824561403508	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270818v1_alt_58	779	213	4.9e-54	176.0	55768	58104	58	0.3299101412066752	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270818v1_alt_58	779	298	4.7e-13	41.4	55768	58104	58	0.27471116816431324	0.6375838926174496	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CorA_0_CAS-III-B	chr8_KI270811v1_alt_161	515	528	1.4e-11	38.3	103208	104752	161	0.7902912621359224	0.06060606060606061	1
CorA_0_CAS-III-B	chr8_KI270811v1_alt_162	109	528	0.00014	15.2	104760	105086	162	0.7706422018348624	0.04924242424242424	1
Csf2_1_IVA3	chr8_KI270811v1_alt_283	119	263	0.016	9.0	205798	206154	283	0.5294117647058824	0.07604562737642585	1
Csx3_2_CAS-I-III	chr8_KI270811v1_alt_2	466	277	0.0032	11.1	1120	2517	2	0.19742489270386265	0.1588447653429603	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270811v1_alt_214	171	213	2.1e-27	90.7	152313	152825	214	0.8596491228070176	0.5352112676056338	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270811v1_alt_215	349	213	3.9e-19	63.7	152819	153865	215	0.3524355300859599	0.5164319248826291	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270811v1_alt_214	171	298	5.1e-07	23.4	152313	152825	214	0.5263157894736842	0.26174496644295303	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8f_3_CAS-I-F	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_180	79	376	0.0093	11.3	114728	114964	180	0.4936708860759494	0.09574468085106383	-1
Csn2_7_CAS-II-A	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_1148	120	372	0.00062	14.9	969513	969872	1148	0.6916666666666667	0.21774193548387097	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_548	194	213	7.8e-12	41.3	351099	351680	548	0.5051546391752577	0.3380281690140845	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_733	1276	213	2.8e-51	170.3	483444	487271	733	0.2249216300940439	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_747	319	213	2.1e-49	164.1	500750	501706	747	0.7115987460815048	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_763	244	213	1.4e-17	60.1	521382	522113	763	0.3770491803278688	0.38028169014084506	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_764	417	213	6.9e-26	87.3	522123	523373	764	0.38369304556354916	0.596244131455399	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_779	293	213	1.8e-43	144.7	534504	535382	779	0.6313993174061433	0.7746478873239436	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_807	417	213	7.00E-26	87.3	560897	562147	807	0.38369304556354916	0.596244131455399	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_808	244	213	1.4e-17	60.1	562157	562888	808	0.3770491803278688	0.38028169014084506	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_822	207	213	4.7e-14	48.6	582547	583167	822	0.33816425120772947	0.27699530516431925	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_823	606	213	4.4e-11	38.9	583139	584956	823	0.1617161716171617	0.3380281690140845	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_733	1276	298	5.5e-09	31.4	483444	487271	733	0.22335423197492163	0.8456375838926175	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_747	319	298	2.2e-11	39.2	500750	501706	747	0.670846394984326	0.6409395973154363	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_764	417	298	3.00E-05	19.2	522123	523373	764	0.21342925659472423	0.25838926174496646	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_779	293	298	2.3e-11	39.2	534504	535382	779	0.5460750853242321	0.5	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270821v1_alt_807	417	298	2.7e-05	19.3	560897	562147	807	0.2158273381294964	0.26174496644295303	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270813v1_alt_17	943	213	1.3e-41	134.1	183701	186529	17	0.18027571580063625	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270813v1_alt_17	943	298	1.3e-41	134.1	183701	186529	17	0.10180275715800637	0.32550335570469796	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270822v1_alt_76	295	213	1.8e-30	100.6	106695	107579	76	0.6067796610169491	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270822v1_alt_76	295	298	1.8e-30	100.6	106695	107579	76	0.488135593220339	0.4228187919463087	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270814v1_alt_25	280	213	1.40E-17	107.1	107417	108256	25	0.6392857142857142	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270814v1_alt_27	401	213	3.50E-27	138.4	130574	131776	27	0.5910224438902744	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270814v1_alt_25	280	298	3.00E-11	33.5	107417	108256	25	0.5142857142857142	0.4228187919463087	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270814v1_alt_27	401	298	3.3e-11	33.3	130574	131776	27	0.4713216957605985	0.5771812080536913	-1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas12a_M11_0_V-A	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_73	128	1241	4.3e-05	14.4	164690	165073	73	0.65625	0.06768734891216761	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_134	130	180	0.002	11.1	344901	345290	134	0.6307692307692307	0.3333333333333333	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_70	322	180	0.021	7.8	160630	161595	70	0.30124223602484473	0.4166666666666667	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_82	339	180	0.065	6.2	194181	195197	82	0.36578171091445427	0.4166666666666667	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_94	157	180	0.004	10.1	211708	212178	94	0.5668789808917197	0.5055555555555555	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_113	885	213	9.1e-54	175.4	253183	255837	113	0.2903954802259887	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_131	280	213	1.50E-33	161.7	341995	342834	131	0.7892857142857143	0.9061032863849765	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_22	110	213	3.00E-08	26.7	59577	59906	22	0.6636363636363637	0.45539906103286387	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_65	83	213	8.1e-12	38.3	154137	154385	65	0.9036144578313253	0.3051643192488263	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_66	101	213	3.9e-11	36.1	154385	154687	66	0.7821782178217822	0.3286384976525822	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_67	122	213	8.8e-07	21.9	154745	155110	67	0.27049180327868855	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_71	614	213	1.2e-32	106.4	161799	163640	71	0.30293159609120524	0.7793427230046949	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_72	345	213	2.4e-11	36.8	163615	164649	72	0.2927536231884058	0.352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_85	584	213	5.00E-53	173.0	196543	198294	85	0.4400684931506849	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_95	186	213	1.2e-37	122.8	212235	212792	95	0.9516129032258065	0.7276995305164319	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_113	885	298	1.7e-12	39.9	253183	255837	113	0.30847457627118646	0.6912751677852349	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_131	280	298	5.00E-13	41.7	341995	342834	131	0.75	0.6241610738255033	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_66	101	298	9.3e-05	14.5	154385	154687	66	0.49504950495049505	0.171114093959731544	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_85	584	298	1.00E-11	37.4	196543	198294	85	0.3681506849315068	0.6409395973154363	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_K1270810v1_alt_95	186	298	2.00E-12	39.7	212235	212792	95	0.7580645161290323	0.41946308724832215	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_K1270722v1_random_5	344	213	4.6e-52	168.9	78116	79147	5	0.7412790697674418	0.9906103286384976	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr14_K1270722v1_random_5	344	298	4.6e-52	168.9	78116	79147	5	0.622093023255814	0.6375838926174496	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5_2_CAS-I	chr8_K1270817v1_alt_24	261	213	3.6e-06	17.9	80375	81157	24	0.4482758620689655	0.24413145539906103	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas11_3_IV	chr8_K1270816v1_alt_244	116	160	0.0017	13.0	174345	174692	244	0.35344827586206895	0.21875	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr3gr5_0_CAS-III-B-III-C	chr9_GL383539v1_alt_2	68	373	1.4e-05	16.6	14012	14215	2	0.73529411176470589	0.13136729222520108	-1
Cmr3gr5_0_CAS-III-B-III-C	chr9_GL383539v1_alt_4	68	373	1.4e-05	16.6	34942	35145	4	0.73529411176470589	0.13136729222520108	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr9_GL383541v1_alt_3	226	180	0.018	5.4	142853	143530	3	0.504424778761062	0.4222222222222222	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_GL383540v1_alt_10	550	213	1.6e-06	18.4	31624	33273	10	0.1890909090909091	0.4647887323943662	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_GL383540v1_alt_5	550	213	1.6e-06	18.4	10614	12263	5	0.1890909090909091	0.4647887323943662	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_GL383541v1_alt_2	1276	213	1.20E-37	172.4	138619	142446	2	0.20141065830721003	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_GL383541v1_alt_6	242	213	8.2e-26	81.5	163856	164581	6	0.5702479338842975	0.5633802816901409	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_GL383542v1_alt_5	207	213	2.60E-17	106.0	42662	43282	5	0.8502415458937198	0.6713615023474179	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr9_GL383541v1_alt_2	1276	298	1.4e-12	37.6	138619	142446	2	0.2249216300940439	0.8456375838926175	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr9_GL383541v1_alt_6	242	298	2.2e-08	23.9	163856	164581	6	0.7355371900826446	0.540268456375839	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr9_GL383542v1_alt_5	207	298	1.4e-09	27.8	42662	43282	5	0.7053140096618358	0.42953020134228187	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr9_K1270823v1_alt_32	339	180	0.11	4.8	157456	158472	32	0.3746312684365782	0.42777777777777776	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270823v1_alt_12	647	213	5.7e-45	146.0	34299	36239	12	0.3462132921174652	0.9154929577464789	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270823v1_alt_31	1061	213	1.20E-37	174.3	153917	157099	31	0.2704995287464656	1.0	-1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270823v1_alt_67	156	213	4.5e-15	48.3	345410	345877	67	0.36538461538461536	0.24413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270823v1_alt_68	405	213	7.3e-14	44.3	346134	347348	68	0.24444444444444444	0.3427230046948357	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr9_K1270823v1_alt_12	647	298	5.2e-12	37.6	34299	36239	12	0.357032457496136	0.697986577181208	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr9_K1270823v1_alt_31	1061	298	4.7e-12	37.8	153917	157099	31	0.26861451460885954	0.8389261744966443	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8b10_0_CAS-I-B	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_39	258	618	0.026	6.3	39281	40054	39	0.47674418604651164	0.20064724919093851	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_39	258	180	0.19	4.7	39281	40054	39	0.6705426356589147	0.6555555555555556	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_118	218	213	3.4e-42	137.6	139432	140085	118	0.9587155963302753	0.8732394366197183	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_119	359	213	4.1e-16	52.4	141343	142419	119	0.3286908077994429	0.431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_31	159	213	1.30E-17	109.6	31456	31932	31	0.9622641509433962	0.6619718309859155	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_32	120	213	1.6e-12	40.6	31939	32298	32	0.6416666666666667	0.28169014084507044	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_37	202	213	6.00E-13	42.0	38186	38791	37	0.42574257425742573	0.3051643192488263	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_38	123	213	7.00E-20	64.7	38831	39199	38	0.983739837398374	0.5070422535211268	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_118	218	298	1.8e-12	39.9	139432	140085	118	0.7018348623853211	0.45302013422818793	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_31	159	298	1.8e-11	36.6	31456	31932	31	0.6540880503144654	0.33221476510067116	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_K1270824v1_alt_38	123	298	0.00027	13.0	38831	39199	38	0.4065040650406504	0.16778523489932887	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_121	315	213	9.4e-46	150.2	152901	153845	121	0.7587301587301587	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_154	176	213	1.2e-28	94.3	186058	186585	154	0.8636363636363636	0.6338028169014085	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_176	381	213	6.2e-52	170.4	206339	207481	176	0.6745406824146981	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_181	81	213	8.2e-07	22.9	210059	210301	181	0.8518518518518519	0.29577464788732394	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_210	261	213	5.00E-23	128.2	233689	234471	210	0.6360153256704981	0.6948356807511737	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_222	49	213	4.2e-08	27.2	253999	254145	222	0.8367346938775511	0.19248826291079812	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_223	141	213	1.5e-25	84.2	254230	254652	223	0.9574468085106383	0.5539906103286385	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_67	62	213	1.9e-08	28.3	94281	94466	67	0.8548387096774194	0.24882629107981222	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_68	108	213	7.7e-16	52.4	94463	94786	68	0.8425925925925926	0.38497652582159625	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_69	155	213	4.00E-07	23.9	94788	95252	69	0.43870967741935485	0.23943661971830985	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_72	78	213	0.00076	13.2	96755	96988	72	0.32051282051282054	0.12206572769953052	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_82	135	213	1.1e-29	97.7	107059	107463	82	0.8814814814814815	0.6103286384976526	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_98	139	213	3.00E-18	60.3	122119	122535	98	0.8633093525179856	0.4835680751173709	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_99	124	213	5.8e-19	62.6	122545	122916	99	0.7419354838709677	0.38028169014084506	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_121	315	298	1.00E-10	35.1	152901	153845	121	0.4984126984126984	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_154	176	298	4.1e-11	36.4	186058	186585	154	0.5738636363636364	0.3187919463087248	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_176	381	298	3.7e-13	43.1	206339	207481	176	0.5616797900262467	0.6375838926174496	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_210	261	298	1.9e-12	40.7	233689	234471	210	0.6130268199233716	0.4966442953020134	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_223	141	298	8.4e-07	22.2	254230	254652	223	0.6382978723404256	0.26174496644295303	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_68	108	298	1.2e-05	18.4	94463	94786	68	0.8055555555555556	0.27181208053691275	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_82	135	298	3.8e-05	16.8	107059	107463	82	0.6518518518518519	0.28859060402684567	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr10_GL383546v1_alt_98	139	298	0.00036	13.6	122119	122535	98	0.4244604316546763	0.1610738255033557	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8b5_0_CAS-I-B	chr10_K1270825v1_alt_69	112	825	0.018	6.3	80486	80821	69	0.5982142857142857	0.07515151515151515	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_GL000194v1_random_115	171	213	2.7e-21	69.5	170014	170526	115	0.7017543859649122	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr14_GL000194v1_random_115	171	298	2.7e-21	69.5	170014	170526	115	0.5029239766081871	0.2483221476510067	-1

	Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas6_8_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	93	275	0.0018	11.8	57996	58274	85	0.5913978494623656	0.19636363636363635	1
Csx10_1_IJID	Hmm	ORF	364	390	0.0078	9.7	45787	46878	83	0.14560439560439561	0.1358974358974359	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	Hmm	ORF	209	180	0.0076	9.1	93444	94070	58	0.48325358851674644	0.37777777777777777	1
CorA_1_CAS-III-B	Hmm	ORF	90	125	0.00061	12.8	2360	2629	2	0.6444444444444445	0.472	1
CorA_1_CAS-III-B	Hmm	ORF	209	125	0.09	5.8	93444	94070	58	0.5406698564593302	0.496	1
Csm2gr11_7_CAS-III-A	Hmm	ORF	209	110	0.0046	11.0	93444	94070	58	0.40669856459330145	0.6727272727272727	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	242	213	5,00E-46	150.0	9637	10362	10	0.9793388429752066	0.9295774647887324	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	187	213	6.7e-33	107.1	153536	154096	102	0.9090909090909091	0.7089201877934272	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	285	213	4.4e-06	19.5	154154	155008	103	0.22105263157894736	0.26291079812206575	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	121	213	1.3e-06	21.2	165184	165546	109	0.5619834710743802	0.23943661971830985	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	131	213	8.5e-23	74.1	165543	165935	110	0.816793893129771	0.4647887323943662	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	388	213	2.5e-24	79.1	32099	33262	25	0.42010309278350516	0.6713615023474179	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	115	213	2.9e-14	46.2	34596	34940	28	0.8695652173913043	0.3474178403755869	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	874	213	3.5e-52	170.1	94525	97146	59	0.2940503432494279	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	477	213	2,00E-12	40.2	132831	134261	85	0.3438155136268344	0.7934272300469484	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	242	298	6.6e-13	41.2	9637	10362	10	0.6570247933884298	0.47651006711409394	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	187	298	4.9e-10	31.7	153536	154096	102	0.6737967914438503	0.3691275167785235	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	131	298	2.8e-11	35.8	165543	165935	110	0.7786259541984732	0.32550335570469796	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	874	298	2.6e-11	36.0	94525	97146	59	0.3295194508009153	0.8489932885906041	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	477	298	4.3e-05	15.5	132831	134261	85	0.1320754716981132	0.2214765100671141	-1
Cas3d_0_CAS-I-D	Hmm	ORF	65	639	0.00015	10.1	113221	113415	11	0.5230769230769231	0.053208137715179966	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	244	213	0.00015	10.1	112280	113011	10	0.8155737704918032	0.7699530516431925	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	211	213	0.00015	10.1	117338	117970	14	0.5213270142180095	0.49295774647887325	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	244	298	0.00015	10.1	112280	113011	10	0.639344262295082	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	211	298	0.00015	10.1	117338	117970	14	0.7772511848341233	0.5100671140939598	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	Hmm	ORF	186	180	0.00013	15.0	33413	33970	23	0.3548387096774194	0.35555555555555557	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	85	213	0.00013	15.0	140308	140562	110	0.7176470588235294	0.3380281690140845	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	87	213	0.00013	15.0	140592	140852	111	0.39080459770114945	0.22535211267605634	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	96	213	0.00013	15.0	28501	28788	13	0.9583333333333334	0.40375586854460094	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	186	213	0.00013	15.0	33413	33970	23	0.1774193548387097	0.13145539906103287	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	190	213	0.00013	15.0	34010	34579	24	0.9368421052631579	0.7276995305164319	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	102	213	0.00013	15.0	114659	114964	88	0.6470588235294118	0.26291079812206575	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	96	298	0.00013	15.0	28501	28788	13	0.9166666666666666	0.2751677852348993	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	190	298	0.00013	15.0	34010	34579	24	0.5368421052631579	0.32550335570469796	1
Cas8b1_10_CAS-I-B	Hmm	ORF	62	567	0.00027	13.5	1713	1898	3	0.7419354838709677	0.08112874779541446	-1
Csb2gr5_1_CAS-I-U	Hmm	ORF	87	534	0.00027	13.5	35173	35433	53	0.40229885057471265	0.06554307116104868	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	142	213	0.00027	13.5	44100	44525	44	0.4859154929577465	0.24413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	225	213	0.00027	13.5	44586	45260	45	0.7333333333333333	0.6901408450704225	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	Hmm	ORF	84	213	0.00027	13.5	77835	78086	69	0.75	0.24882629107981222	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	Hmm	ORF	225	298	0.00027	13.5	44586	45260	45	0.6933333333333334	0.48322147651006714	-1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas1_1_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_333	114	261	0.016	9.0	342287	342628	333	0.9298245614035088	0.3486590038314176	1
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_378	98	255	0.038	8.0	390055	390348	378	0.5714285714285714	0.2196078431372549	-1
Csx1_7_CAS-III	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_387	137	309	3.6	1.6	398843	399253	387	0.7007299270072993	0.3106796116504854	1
Csx25_0_CAS-III-D	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_352	82	248	0.0011	13.0	360561	360806	352	0.524390243902439	0.17338709677419356	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_139	84	213	0.00078	13.7	143657	143908	139	0.39285714285714285	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_293	466	213	1.9e-23	77.8	299246	300643	293	0.2575107296137339	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_324	182	213	6.1e-05	17.3	332693	333238	324	0.3076923076923077	0.18779342723004694	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_334	256	213	9.2e-35	114.7	342726	343493	334	0.64453125	0.6948356807511737	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_368	196	213	1.7e-23	78.0	378441	379028	368	0.6122448979591837	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_369	79	213	1.7e-16	55.1	379142	379378	369	0.9493670886075949	0.323943661971831	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_293	466	298	7.9e-06	19.5	299246	300643	293	0.18454935622317598	0.2483221476510067	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_334	256	298	6.00E-11	36.3	342726	343493	334	0.5859375	0.4664429530201342	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL877876v1_alt_368	196	298	1.5e-06	21.8	378441	379028	368	0.5051020408163265	0.29194630872483224	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr14_KI270725v1_random_51	286	180	0.21	5.0	52725	53582	51	0.4020979020979021	0.4166666666666667	-1
CorA_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr14_KI270725v1_random_118	59	551	0.00037	12.9	138555	138731	118	0.5423728813559322	0.056261343012704176	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270725v1_random_50	891	213	4.5e-53	173.6	49831	52503	50	0.2884399551066218	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270726v1_random_43	58	213	1.3e-06	21.8	32793	32966	43	0.5172413793103449	0.14084507042253522	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270726v1_random_45	731	213	4.3e-45	147.5	33929	36121	45	0.32558139534883723	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr14_KI270726v1_random_43	58	298	0.0011	11.5	32793	32966	43	0.46551724137931033	0.09060402684563758	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr14_KI270726v1_random_45	731	298	1.6e-10	33.9	33929	36121	45	0.22571819425444598	0.4966442953020134	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr12_GL383549v1_alt_9	339	180	0.047	5.1	38210	39226	9	0.336283185840708	0.4222222222222222	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383549v1_alt_10	1216	213	6.3e-55	177.7	39290	42937	10	0.23601973684210525	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383549v1_alt_11	97	213	6.4e-10	30.6	45076	45366	11	0.6185567010309279	0.2347417840375587	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383549v1_alt_32	198	213	6.40E-08	76.4	111060	111653	32	0.5404040404040404	0.4507042253521127	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383549v1_alt_33	630	213	6.6e-25	79.6	111732	113621	33	0.19047619047619047	0.4413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383549v1_alt_10	1216	298	2.00E-13	41.5	39290	42937	10	0.23519736842105263	0.8456375838926175	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383549v1_alt_32	198	298	2.8e-06	18.0	111060	111653	32	0.4797979797979798	0.30201342281879195	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383549v1_alt_33	630	298	1.6e-06	18.9	111732	113621	33	0.1619047619047619	0.30201342281879195	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_KI270835v1_alt_128	181	213	2.6e-25	82.8	163904	164446	128	0.8674033149171271	0.5821596244131455	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_KI270835v1_alt_128	181	298	2.6e-25	82.8	163904	164446	128	0.4972375690607735	0.26174496644295303	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_15	539	213	9.60E-28	139.4	39746	41362	15	0.38589981447124305	0.8450704225352113	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_20	162	213	5.8e-14	45.3	45484	45969	20	0.3950617283950617	0.26291079812206575	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_21	154	213	6.00E-33	107.4	45980	46441	21	0.9675324675324676	0.6197183098591549	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_34	78	213	8.9e-08	25.1	62373	62606	34	0.8076923076923077	0.26291079812206575	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_48	50	213	2.1e-05	17.4	82843	82992	48	0.78	0.1784037558685446	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_61	71	213	4.8e-08	26.0	105080	105292	61	0.7746478873239436	0.2347417840375587	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_7	159	213	3.00E-29	95.3	24143	24619	7	0.9308176100628931	0.6150234741784038	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_71	191	213	3.4e-10	33.0	122571	123143	71	0.39790575916230364	0.27699530516431925	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_72	102	213	9.2e-16	51.2	123236	123541	72	0.7745098039215687	0.3380281690140845	-1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_81	168	213	1.7e-20	66.7	139685	140188	81	0.7321428571428571	0.49765258215962443	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_82	63	213	1.9e-06	20.8	140373	140561	82	0.5238095238095238	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383552v1_alt_28	344	213	9.9e-27	87.1	71455	72486	28	0.45348837209302323	0.5774647887323944	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383552v1_alt_29	186	213	4.9e-21	68.4	72480	73037	29	0.5	0.38497652582159625	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383552v1_alt_6	89	213	4.7e-09	29.3	15367	15633	6	0.6179775280898876	0.24882629107981222	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_15	539	298	7.1e-11	34.6	39746	41362	15	0.42115027829313545	0.6946308724832215	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_21	154	298	7.2e-12	37.9	45980	46441	21	0.9285714285714286	0.41946308724832215	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_7	159	298	3.1e-09	29.2	24143	24619	7	0.9433962264150944	0.4429530201342282	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_72	102	298	2.00E-07	23.3	123236	123541	72	0.7745098039215687	0.24496644295302014	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383550v2_alt_81	168	298	7.6e-06	18.1	139685	140188	81	0.5238095238095238	0.2550335570469799	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383552v1_alt_28	344	298	7.00E-07	21.5	71455	72486	28	0.25872093023255816	0.25838926174496646	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_6	259	180	0.0053	6.3	116752	117528	6	0.44015444015444016	0.4388888888888889	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_2	848	213	5.9e-54	172.6	103375	105918	2	0.3018867924528302	0.9953051643192489	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_3	809	213	9.4e-54	172.0	106578	109004	3	0.3176761433868974	0.9953051643192489	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_4	885	213	6.4e-54	172.5	109431	112085	4	0.28926553672316385	0.9953051643192489	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_5	848	213	8.2e-56	178.7	112622	115165	5	0.30306603773584906	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_2	848	298	8.4e-14	40.8	103375	105918	2	0.25235849056603776	0.6409395973154363	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_3	809	298	9.1e-14	40.7	106578	109004	3	0.26452410383189123	0.6409395973154363	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_4	885	298	9.7e-14	40.6	109431	112085	4	0.24180790960451978	0.6409395973154363	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383553v2_alt_5	848	298	1.2e-14	43.6	112622	115165	5	0.25235849056603776	0.6375838926174496	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr12_GL383551v1_alt_15	339	180	0.063	4.9	75914	76930	15	0.35103244837758113	0.4388888888888889	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr12_GL383551v1_alt_19	339	180	0.11	4.2	95306	96322	19	0.3215339233038348	0.4666666666666667	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383551v1_alt_14	1276	213	4.30E-39	178.5	72023	75850	14	0.20141065830721003	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_GL383551v1_alt_18	1276	213	4.4e-54	175.2	91415	95242	18	0.1974921630094044	0.9765258215962441	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383551v1_alt_14	1276	298	1.3e-13	42.3	72023	75850	14	0.2249216300940439	0.8456375838926175	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_GL383551v1_alt_18	1276	298	3.2e-14	44.3	91415	95242	18	0.2249216300940439	0.8456375838926175	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5_0_CAS-I	chr13_K1270840v1_alt_20	77	201	0.00044	11.2	138997	139227	20	0.6753246753246753	0.14925373134328357	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr13_K1270841v1_alt_2	181	213	1.4e-14	43.3	86555	87097	2	0.6077348066298343	0.39436619718309857	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5_1_IIC	chr14_K1270844v1_alt_94	186	178	0.043	7.1	134919	135476	94	0.3118279569892473	0.33707865168539325	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_K1270844v1_alt_80	288	213	4.9e-14	45.9	109174	110037	80	0.34375	0.3427230046948357	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_K1270844v1_alt_81	633	213	2.70E-11	89.3	110037	111935	81	0.27488151658767773	0.7230046948356808	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8b5_0_CAS-I-B	chr14_K1270847v1_alt_1317	121	825	3.6	2.2	1011204	1011566	1317	0.48760330578512395	0.07636363636363637	1
Cas8e_3_CAS-I-E	chr14_K1270847v1_alt_1208	136	518	0.023	10.1	939094	939501	1208	0.25735294117647056	0.06756756756756757	1
Cmr5_1_IIC	chr14_K1270847v1_alt_570	114	178	0.026	11.2	285460	285801	570	0.2719298245614035	0.16853932584269662	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr14_K1270847v1_alt_809	338	180	1.0	6.0	531688	532701	809	0.2988165680473373	0.4388888888888889	-1
Cs1_1_IVA1	chr14_K1270847v1_alt_1052	128	178	0.014	12.0	841483	841866	1052	0.2890625	0.20786516853932585	-1
Csx3_0_CAS-III	chr14_K1270847v1_alt_1858	242	83	0.065	10.4	1460403	1461128	1858	0.29338842975206614	0.2289156626506024	-1

Csx3_1_CAS-I-III	chr14_KI270847v1_alt_1858	242	84	2.2	5.3	1460403	1461128	1858	0.29338842975206614	0.2261904761904762	-1
Csx3_2_CAS-I-III	chr14_KI270847v1_alt_1858	242	277	0.022	10.7	1460403	1461128	1858	0.30991735537190085	0.09747292418772563	-1
Mem_01_0_CAS-III-B	chr14_KI270847v1_alt_962	68	534	0.021	10.5	745395	745598	962	0.7647058823529411	0.10112359550561797	1
Mem_04_0_CAS-III-D	chr14_KI270847v1_alt_1317	121	241	1.3	5.3	1011204	1011566	1317	0.4049586776859504	0.21161825726141079	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270847v1_alt_1622	226	213	5,00E-10	88.5	1183924	1184601	1622	0.6415929203539823	0.6009389671361502	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270847v1_alt_766	100	213	1.2e-06	25.1	475055	475354	766	0.59	0.28169014084507044	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270847v1_alt_786	161	213	0.0017	14.9	500001	500483	786	0.2857142857142857	0.2112676056338028	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr14_KI270847v1_alt_766	100	298	7.2e-05	18.6	475055	475354	766	0.59	0.19463087248322147	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas1_0_V	chr14_KI270845v1_alt_54	34	317	0.0017	11.0	48964	49065	54	0.7058823529411765	0.07570977917981073	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
ZOG_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_1592	62	205	0.0043	12.7	1314646	1314831	1592	0.6774193548387096	0.2	-1
Cas10_2_CAS-III	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_710	131	593	0.028	9.2	368547	368939	710	0.26717557251908397	0.05902192242833052	1
Cas5_1_IC	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_822	91	236	0.013	11.6	419062	419334	822	0.5714285714285714	0.2076271186440678	-1
Cas5_5_CAS-I-B	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_822	91	220	0.0026	14.1	419062	419334	822	0.6373626373626373	0.24545454545454545	-1
Cas6_1_CAS-III-D	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_433	109	316	5.6	2.7	206422	206748	433	0.6513761467889908	0.12974683544303797	1
Cmr5_1_IIC	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_945	184	178	0.12	8.8	545661	546212	945	0.657608695652174	0.5561797752808989	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_945	184	180	0.0053	13.2	545661	546212	945	0.5869565217391305	0.6166666666666667	-1
Cmr6gr7_0_CAS-III-B-III-C	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_979	145	544	0.0081	11.6	597215	597649	979	0.22758620689655173	0.0625	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_1039	422	213	3,70E-09	85.4	669167	670432	1039	0.4099526066350711	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_1249	202	213	1.8e-37	125.6	919384	919989	1249	0.8217821782178217	0.6948356807511737	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_1250	580	213	1.3e-08	31.3	920011	921750	1250	0.1310344827586207	0.27699530516431925	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_1039	422	298	0.015	10.8	669167	670432	1039	0.14928909952606634	0.2181208053691275	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr14_KI270846v1_alt_1249	202	298	2.3e-11	39.7	919384	919989	1249	0.7821782178217822	0.4899328859060403	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csm2gr11_6_CAS-III-A	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_70	125	139	0.00052	15.2	68713	69087	70	0.28	0.2589928057553957	-1
PrimPol_1_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_180	174	130	0.00093	14.4	140689	141210	180	0.5977011494252874	0.6076923076923076	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_429	141	213	2,30E-06	74.8	347986	348408	429	0.950354609929078	0.5492957746478874	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_430	186	213	7.2e-20	66.6	348402	348959	430	0.5053763440860215	0.38967136150234744	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_471	1010	213	4.2e-52	172.0	393680	396709	471	0.28415841584158413	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_506	112	213	3.2e-16	54.7	428697	429032	506	0.8839285714285714	0.431924882629108	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_521	153	213	2.1e-23	78.2	437292	437750	521	0.9673202614379085	0.6197183098591549	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_429	141	298	7.2e-05	16.9	347986	348408	429	0.23404255319148937	0.11073825503355705	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_430	186	298	0.00034	14.7	348402	348959	430	0.7634408602150538	0.4161073825503356	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_471	1010	298	9.4e-13	42.8	393680	396709	471	0.28415841584158413	0.8456375838926175	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270852v1_alt_506	112	298	0.00057	14.0	428697	429032	506	0.8482142857142857	0.2986577181208054	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_8_CAS-III-B	chr15_KI270848v1_alt_271	56	149	0.0012	12.9	236249	236416	271	0.5714285714285714	0.21476510067114093	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270848v1_alt_245	573	213	0.0012	12.9	197484	199202	245	0.1012216404886562	0.19718309859154928	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8f_7_CAS-I-F	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_97	104	376	0.00011	14.1	198696	199007	97	0.75	0.2074468085106383	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_100	221	213	0.00011	14.1	204133	204795	100	0.5203619909502263	0.7276995305164319	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_108	95	213	0.00011	14.1	224077	224361	108	0.8105263157894737	0.28169014084507044	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_32	122	213	0.00011	14.1	65100	65465	32	0.27049180327868855	0.13145539906103287	1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_33	92	213	0.00011	14.1	65688	65963	33	0.8804347826086957	0.3192488262910798	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_84	176	213	0.00011	14.1	187992	188519	84	0.8465909090909091	0.6103286384976526	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_95	117	213	0.00011	14.1	197383	197733	95	0.6495726495726496	0.39436619718309857	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_33	92	298	0.00011	14.1	65688	65963	33	0.3695652173913043	0.11409395973154363	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270849v1_alt_84	176	298	0.00011	14.1	187992	188519	84	0.8806818181818182	0.47315436241610737	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csm2gr11_6_CAS-III-A	chr15_KI270727v1_random_26	125	139	0.00038	15.2	37962	38336	26	0.28	0.2589928057553957	-1
PrimPol_1_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270727v1_random_128	162	130	0.0014	13.4	109938	110423	128	0.5925925925925926	0.5846153846153846	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270727v1_random_307	141	213	1.70E-06	74.8	317235	317657	307	0.950354609929078	0.5492957746478874	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270727v1_random_308	186	213	5.3e-20	66.6	317651	318208	308	0.5053763440860215	0.38967136150234744	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270727v1_random_340	1004	213	3.1e-52	172.0	362929	365940	340	0.2858565737051793	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270727v1_random_368	112	213	2.4e-16	54.7	397946	398281	368	0.8839285714285714	0.431924882629108	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270727v1_random_379	153	213	1.60E-07	78.2	406541	406999	379	0.9673202614379085	0.6197183098591549	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270727v1_random_307	141	298	5.2e-05	16.9	317235	317657	307	0.23404255319148937	0.11073825503355705	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270727v1_random_308	186	298	0.00025	14.7	317651	318208	308	0.7634408602150538	0.4161073825503356	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270727v1_random_340	1004	298	6.8e-13	42.8	362929	365940	340	0.2858565737051793	0.8456375838926175	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270727v1_random_368	112	298	0.00041	14.0	397946	398281	368	0.8482142857142857	0.2986577181208054	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5_1_IIIC	chr15_KI270850v1_alt_108	71	178	0.00041	13.1	313418	313630	108	0.8873239436619719	0.34831460674157305	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas10_1_IIIB	chr16_KI270855v1_alt_88	187	116	0.00084	12.3	209994	210554	88	0.5401069518716578	0.47413793103448276	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas11b_0_CAS-I-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4151	286	170	0.17	9.7	2410135	2410992	4151	0.4195804195804196	0.5588235294117647	-1
Cas13c_0_VIC	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_1884	96	1127	0.06	8.9	1132201	1132488	1884	0.4791666666666667	0.043478260869565216	1
Cas8b1_0_CAS-I-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_2155	92	469	0.0096	12.6	1293158	1293433	2155	0.5652173913043478	0.1044776119402985	-1
Cas8b2_4_CAS-I-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_120	123	65	0.028	12.7	71931	72299	120	0.2926829268292683	0.5538461538461539	-1
Cas8b5_0_CAS-I-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4151	286	825	0.1	8.5	2410135	2410992	4151	0.3146853146853147	0.11393939393939394	-1
Cas8f_0_CAS-I-F	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4467	59	422	0.029	11.1	2643577	2643753	4467	0.5932203389830508	0.08293838862559241	-1
CasR_2_CAS-III-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_2986	75	331	0.059	10.4	1735246	1735470	2986	0.5466666666666666	0.12386706948640483	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4151	286	180	5.3	4.8	2410135	2410992	4151	0.4125874125874126	0.4555555555555555	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4266	339	180	0.79	7.5	2505550	2506566	4266	0.3008849557522124	0.3777777777777777	-1
PD_DExK_2_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_1372	56	127	0.013	13.0	834533	834700	1372	0.32142857142857145	0.14173228346456693	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_1099	379	213	1.1e-09	36.3	674587	675723	1099	0.20052770448548812	0.27699530516431925	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_1371	379	213	1.1e-09	36.3	833314	834450	1371	0.20052770448548812	0.27699530516431925	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4149	982	213	9.8e-53	176.9	2406195	2409140	4149	0.26171079429735233	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4176	124	213	2.2e-21	74.5	2431870	2432241	4176	0.8467741935483871	0.4507042253521127	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4265	1239	213	7.9e-54	180.5	2501659	2505375	4265	0.20742534301856336	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4149	982	298	9.5e-13	45.7	2406195	2409140	4149	0.21792260692464357	0.6375838926174496	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4176	124	298	5.5e-10	36.6	2431870	2432241	4176	0.7983870967741935	0.31543624161073824	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4265	1239	298	8.1e-12	42.6	2501659	2505375	4265	0.23163841807909605	0.8456375838926175	-1
TniQ_0_V-K	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_4021	148	184	0.028	12.1	2319282	2319725	4021	0.4594594594594595	0.20652173913043478	1
Unk_02_0_CAS-III-A-III-B	chr16_KI270853v1_alt_2436	210	261	0.036	11.4	1439767	1440396	2436	0.16666666666666666	0.13026819923371646	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8a3_1_CAS-I-A	chr16_GL383557v1_alt_99	77	294	0.0029	10.7	71953	72183	99	0.2987012987012987	0.0782312925170068	-1

Csx1_7_CAS-III	chr16_GL383556v1_alt_38	158	309	0.0029	10.7	70896	71369	38	0.6139240506329114	0.3074433656957929	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8a1_1_IB	chr17_KI270857v1_alt_1370	60	571	0.0003	16.3	1789687	1789866	1370	0.6666666666666666	0.07005253940455342	-1
Cas8b1_1_CAS-I-B	chr17_KI270857v1_alt_1370	60	563	0.0003	16.3	1789687	1789866	1370	0.6166666666666667	0.06571936056838366	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
PD_DExK_0_CAS-I-B	chr17_GL383564v2_alt_6	99	231	2.9e-05	15.2	25384	25680	6	0.9292929292929293	0.42424242424242425	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_JH159147v1_alt_12	208	213	2.9e-05	15.2	52243	52866	12	0.4855769230769231	0.352112670656338	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8f_4_CAS-I-F	chr17_GL000258v2_alt_403	87	450	0.012	10.5	475923	476183	403	0.42528735632183906	0.08888888888888889	-1
Csx19_7_CAS-III-D	chr17_GL000258v2_alt_1322	61	141	0.012	10.5	1527632	1527814	1322	0.5573770491803278	0.24113475177304963	-1
Csx19_7_CAS-III-D	chr17_GL000258v2_alt_361	61	141	0.012	10.5	427580	427762	361	0.5573770491803278	0.24113475177304963	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr17_GL383565v1_alt_2	339	180	0.019	3.9	55879	56895	2	0.35398230088495575	0.4444444444444444	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr17_GL383565v1_alt_5	339	180	0.0087	4.9	159638	160654	5	0.35103244837758113	0.43888888888888889	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_GL383565v1_alt_3	1276	213	2.2e-55	176.6	56959	60786	3	0.1974921630094044	0.9765258215962441	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_GL383565v1_alt_7	741	213	3.7e-50	159.5	162323	164545	7	0.32118758434547906	0.9342723004694836	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr17_GL383565v1_alt_3	1276	298	3.4e-14	41.4	56959	60786	3	0.2249216300940439	0.8456375838926175	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr17_GL383565v1_alt_7	741	298	6.00E-13	37.3	162323	164545	7	0.25101214574898784	0.5704697986577181	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CasR_2_CAS-III-D	chr17_KI270858v1_alt_209	138	636	0.0017	10.6	222257	222670	209	0.2536231884057971	0.05345911949685535	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csn2_12_CAS-II-A	chr17_KI270859v1_alt_8	128	257	0.00086	13.0	5229	5612	8	0.390625	0.20233463035019456	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_KI270859v1_alt_31	93	213	0.00086	13.0	25675	25953	31	0.44086021505376344	0.17370892018779344	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5_0_CAS-I-E	chr17_KI270860v1_alt_281	144	182	0.0054	10.8	170566	170997	281	0.4861111111111111	0.3956043956043956	-1
Cas5_1_CAS-I-E	chr17_KI270860v1_alt_281	144	180	0.0054	10.8	170566	170997	281	0.4652777777777778	0.38333333333333336	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr18_GL383567v1_alt_17	339	180	0.2	3.8	55874	56890	17	0.3008849557522124	0.4	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383567v1_alt_16	1276	213	3.60E-40	179.2	51983	55810	16	0.20141065830721003	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383567v1_alt_25	152	213	1.9e-10	33.0	74340	74795	25	0.5263157894736842	0.323943661971831	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383567v1_alt_26	151	213	9.2e-12	37.3	75072	75524	26	0.37748344370860926	0.24413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr18_GL383567v1_alt_16	1276	298	1.6e-13	42.6	51983	55810	16	0.22570532915360503	0.8456375838926175	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_32	339	180	0.031	5.5	132698	133714	32	0.3480825958702065	0.5111111111111111	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_11	438	213	1.7e-07	22.4	75599	76912	11	0.15753424657534246	0.24413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_12	136	213	2.4e-23	74.2	76909	77316	12	0.7573529411764706	0.4507042253521127	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_13	257	213	1.1e-05	16.5	77374	78144	13	0.12840466926070038	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_26	257	213	7.70E-33	154.3	118597	119367	26	0.9221789883268483	0.9295774647887324	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_33	1276	213	2.8e-54	175.3	133778	137605	33	0.20141065830721003	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_9	82	213	2.6e-15	48.0	74042	74287	9	0.926829268292683	0.3286384976525822	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_12	136	298	3.4e-10	30.6	76909	77316	12	0.6617647058823529	0.28523489932885904	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_26	257	298	8.3e-14	42.5	118597	119367	26	0.6731517509727627	0.5234899328859061	1

RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr18_GL383570v1_alt_33	1276	298	7.6e-13	39.3	133778	137605	33	0.2249216300940439	0.8456375838926175	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_13	207	180	0.0037	9.1	53137	53757	13	0.47342995169082125	0.35	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_20	339	180	0.061	5.2	66025	67041	20	0.336283185840708	0.4222222222222222	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr18_GL383571v1_alt_7	68	180	0.00014	13.8	24643	24846	7	0.8529411764705882	0.3166666666666665	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_11	361	213	1.8e-27	88.4	48435	49517	11	0.40166204986149584	0.5258215962441315	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_16	293	213	9.6e-45	144.8	55501	56379	16	0.6689419795221843	0.7934272300469484	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_2	336	213	3.5e-06	18.8	3170	4177	2	0.20535714285714285	0.24413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_21	550	213	1.7e-06	19.9	67105	68754	21	0.06	0.13145539906103287	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_22	713	213	9.2e-39	125.3	68794	70932	22	0.29312762973352036	0.7981220657276995	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr18_GL383571v1_alt_6	217	213	3.6e-40	129.9	23677	24327	6	0.9585253456221198	0.8685446009389671	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_11	361	298	3.7e-07	21.3	48435	49517	11	0.24653739612188366	0.25838926174496646	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_16	293	298	1.5e-12	39.1	55501	56379	16	0.5426621160409556	0.4966442953020134	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr18_GL383568v1_alt_22	713	298	7.3e-12	36.8	68794	70932	22	0.25105189340813466	0.5469798657718121	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr18_GL383571v1_alt_6	217	298	3.5e-10	31.2	23677	24327	6	0.8018433179723502	0.44966442953020136	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csx16_2_CAS-I-III	chr18_GL383569v1_alt_68	114	90	0.00039	13.8	78946	79287	68	0.6052631578947368	0.6666666666666666	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas12a_1_CAS-V-A	chr16_KI270728v1_random_115	104	1086	0.011	10.5	142435	142746	115	0.5192307692307693	0.04880294659300184	-1
Cas12a_1_CAS-V-A	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1812	104	1086	0.011	10.5	1678839	1679150	1812	0.5192307692307693	0.04880294659300184	-1
Cas2_0_I-II-III-V	chr16_KI270728v1_random_124	64	83	0.0014	15.9	149351	149542	124	0.515625	0.4457831325301205	-1
Cas2_0_I-II-III-V	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1822	64	83	0.0014	15.9	1685761	1685952	1822	0.515625	0.4457831325301205	-1
Cas8a2_0_CAS-I-A	chr16_KI270728v1_random_524	98	329	0.0099	11.9	553645	553938	524	0.32653061224489793	0.0972644376899696	1
Cas8a2_0_CAS-I-A	chr16_KI270728v1_random_738	98	329	0.0099	11.9	780515	780808	738	0.32653061224489793	0.0972644376899696	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1121	257	180	0.76	6.5	1101313	1102083	1121	0.669260700389105	0.6555555555555556	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1125	169	180	0.34	7.7	1103323	1103829	1125	0.6627218934911243	0.4333333333333333	-1
Cmr7_0_CAS-III-B	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1417	91	187	0.0017	15.2	1279093	1279365	1417	0.7252747252747253	0.35294117647058826	1
Csm5gr7_2_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1036	85	258	0.015	11.6	1016348	1016602	1036	0.3176470588235294	0.1124031007751938	-1
Csn2_0_CAS-II-A	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1414	85	223	0.013	11.9	1275599	1275853	1414	0.5882352941176471	0.2242152466367713	-1
Csx22_0_CAS-III-A	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1996	75	191	0.024	11.1	1784618	1784842	1996	0.5866666666666667	0.23036649214659685	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1068	234	213	2.2e-37	125.7	1039592	1040293	1068	0.8418803418803419	0.7605633802816901	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1120	514	213	7.9e-41	137.0	1099693	1101234	1120	0.46108949416342415	0.9295774647887324	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1138	69	213	5.00E-09	33.0	1112501	1112707	1138	0.8840579710144928	0.25821596244131456	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_122	246	213	3.4e-37	125.1	145883	146620	122	0.7886178861788617	0.7464788732394366	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1249	314	213	1.5e-34	116.5	1171898	1172839	1249	0.7133757961783439	0.9248826291079812	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1423	81	213	9.6e-13	45.2	1281641	1281883	1423	0.654320987654321	0.22535211267605634	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1512	105	213	8.1e-08	29.1	1365752	1366066	1512	0.7238095238095238	0.30985915492957744	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1773	105	213	8.1e-08	29.1	1596324	1596638	1773	0.7238095238095238	0.30985915492957744	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1819	246	213	3.4e-37	125.1	1682291	1683028	1819	0.7886178861788617	0.7464788732394366	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_430	78	213	4.9e-06	23.3	415511	415744	430	0.6794871794871795	0.23943661971830985	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_434	192	213	2.5e-36	122.3	418099	418674	434	0.9895833333333334	0.784037558685446	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_453	60	213	5.2e-06	23.2	432263	432442	453	0.5666666666666667	0.1643192488262911	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_64	78	213	4.9e-06	23.3	103169	103402	64	0.6794871794871795	0.23943661971830985	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_68	192	213	2.5e-36	122.3	105757	106332	68	0.9895833333333334	0.784037558685446	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr16_KI270728v1_random_87	60	213	5.2e-06	23.2	119921	120100	87	0.5666666666666667	0.1643192488262911	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1068	234	298	2.9e-10	36.5	1039592	1040293	1068	0.6709401709401709	0.4697986577181208	-1

RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1120	514	298	2.9e-09	33.2	1099693	1101234	1120	0.29571984435797666	0.44966442953020136	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270728v1_random_122	246	298	7.8e-12	41.6	145883	146620	122	0.6341463414634146	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270728v1_random_1819	246	298	7.8e-12	41.6	1682291	1683028	1819	0.6341463414634146	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270728v1_random_434	192	298	7.00E-08	28.7	418099	418674	434	0.4947916666666667	0.2986577181208054	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr16_KI270728v1_random_68	192	298	7.00E-08	28.7	105757	106332	68	0.4947916666666667	0.2986577181208054	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas1_0_CAS-III-B	chr19_KI270865v1_alt_38	153	266	0.0012	12.6	26504	26962	38	0.35294117647058826	0.20300751879699247	1
Cas3HD_0_CAS-I-E	chr19_KI270868v1_alt_16	173	285	0.0012	12.6	9355	9873	16	0.2023121387283237	0.12280701754385964	-1
Cas5_0_CAS-I-E	chr19_KI270868v1_alt_6	70	182	0.0012	12.6	3326	3535	6	0.3	0.11538461538461539	1
Cas5_1_CAS-I-E	chr19_KI270868v1_alt_6	70	180	0.0012	12.6	3326	3535	6	0.2857142857142857	0.11111111111111111	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_23	385	180	0.085	6.3	147653	148807	23	0.3194805194805195	0.5555555555555556	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_26	219	180	0.0064	10.0	163781	164437	26	0.4292237442922374	0.5333333333333333	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_126	615	213	8.1e-53	172.8	237058	238902	126	0.41788617886178864	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_15	399	213	4.10E-08	79.0	88611	89807	15	0.40100250626566414	0.9154929577464789	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_23	385	213	7.70E-13	91.2	147653	148807	23	0.36103896103896105	0.568075117370892	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_24	82	213	4.3e-12	39.7	148783	149028	24	0.8780487804878049	0.29107981220657275	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_30	509	213	2.7e-53	174.4	171197	172723	30	0.48919449901768175	0.9765258215962441	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_37	303	213	7.20E-20	114.2	198679	199587	37	0.5478547854785478	0.6995305164319249	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_8	108	213	3.6e-13	43.2	57683	58006	8	0.6574074074074074	0.2863849765258216	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_126	615	298	2.2e-13	43.4	237058	238902	126	0.34959349593495936	0.6442953020134228	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_23	385	298	1.6e-05	17.5	147653	148807	23	0.32727272727272727	0.40604026845637586	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_30	509	298	1.4e-14	47.3	171197	172723	30	0.4223968565815324	0.6442953020134228	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL383573v1_alt_37	303	298	8.1e-09	28.4	198679	199587	37	0.5181518151815182	0.4865771812080537	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383575v2_alt_12	798	213	4.20E-25	134.0	13555	15948	12	0.21303258145363407	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383575v2_alt_126	106	213	4.20E-25	134.0	152000	152317	126	0.8867924528301887	0.49295774647887325	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383575v2_alt_26	147	213	4.20E-25	134.0	31194	31634	26	0.8707482993197279	0.7746478873239436	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL383575v2_alt_12	798	298	4.20E-25	134.0	13555	15948	12	0.11904761904761904	0.3221476510067114	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas3_1_I	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_99	206	178	0.00084	12.1	170311	170928	99	0.34951456310679613	0.4044943820224719	-1
Cas8a3_0_CAS-I-A	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_70	146	383	3.5e-05	15.6	120872	121309	70	0.7808219178082192	0.31070496083550914	-1
Cas8b5_0_CAS-I-B	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_93	102	825	0.0099	6.5	157200	157505	93	0.8235294117647058	0.10787878787878788	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_84	164	180	0.0031	10.1	150188	150679	84	0.8048780487804879	0.6166666666666667	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_38	133	213	8.4e-09	28.0	64597	64995	38	0.7293233082706767	0.647887323943662	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_4	114	213	4.4e-07	22.4	5176	5517	4	0.6228070175438597	0.29107981220657275	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_43	722	213	3.1e-41	134.0	72116	74281	43	0.23545706371191136	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_61	78	213	2.9e-08	26.3	101999	102232	61	0.8589743589743589	0.2863849765258216	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_85	141	213	5.6e-18	58.0	151121	151543	85	0.8865248226950354	0.5164319248826291	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_91	173	213	1.5e-07	23.9	155790	156308	91	0.44508670520231214	0.27699530516431925	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_92	132	213	6.1e-19	61.2	156531	156926	92	0.7196969696969697	0.39906103286384975	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_43	722	298	4.4e-07	21.7	72116	74281	43	0.13157894736842105	0.3221476510067114	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL383576v1_alt_85	141	298	5.8e-06	18.0	151121	151543	85	0.5319148936170213	0.23154362416107382	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5_1_IIIC	chr19_GL383574v1_alt_157	103	178	2.4e-05	18.1	135625	135933	157	0.6407766990291263	0.38202247191011235	-1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CasR_1_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_K1270867v1_alt_224	76	218	0.001	12.3	220404	220631	224	0.5131578947368421	0.0963302752293578	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr19_K1270867v1_alt_190	583	180	0.01	9.7	200003	201751	190	0.2950257289879931	0.6555555555555556	-1
Csx1_13_CAS-III	chr19_K1270867v1_alt_224	76	426	0.003	10.5	220404	220631	224	0.25	0.04460093896713615	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_K1270867v1_alt_10	79	213	3.5e-09	30.6	25855	26091	10	0.9493670886075949	0.3192488262910798	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_K1270867v1_alt_190	583	213	1.5e-21	71.0	200003	201751	190	0.22641509433962265	0.5586854460093896	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_K1270867v1_alt_22	548	213	1.4e-31	103.8	45701	47344	22	0.36496350364963503	0.6948356807511737	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_K1270867v1_alt_22	548	298	8.3e-10	32.0	45701	47344	22	0.26824817518248173	0.45302013422818793	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr19_GL949746v1_alt_905	515	284	0.0012	14.4	885586	887130	905	0.040776699029126215	0.07394366197183098	1
Csm5_1_IIA	chr19_GL949746v1_alt_530	68	373	0.0012	14.4	450051	450254	530	0.7352941176470589	0.13404825737265416	-1
Csm5gr7_1_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr19_GL949746v1_alt_530	68	369	0.0012	14.4	450051	450254	530	0.75	0.13821138211382114	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL949746v1_alt_705	61	213	0.0012	14.4	624470	624652	705	0.7377049180327869	0.22065727699530516	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL949746v1_alt_956	180	213	0.0012	14.4	925764	926303	956	0.6888888888888889	0.460093896713615	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL949746v1_alt_956	180	298	0.0012	14.4	925764	926303	956	0.4944444444444444	0.25838926714496646	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr20_GL383577v2_alt_74	339	180	0.59	4.1	110058	111074	74	0.336283185840708	0.4388888888888889	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr20_GL383577v2_alt_75	1276	213	3.2e-54	178.0	111138	114965	75	0.20141065830721003	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr20_GL383577v2_alt_75	1276	298	6.1e-13	42.5	111138	114965	75	0.2249216300940439	0.8456375838926175	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5_0_I	chr20_K1270870v1_alt_80	48	43	0.0088	10.0	41468	41611	80	0.8333333333333334	0.5581395348837209	1
Cas7_1_CAS-I-E	chr20_K1270870v1_alt_50	120	359	0.001	12.7	24333	24692	50	0.5416666666666666	0.181058495821727	1
Cas9_1_CAS-II-C	chr20_K1270870v1_alt_151	72	568	0.0017	11.4	87986	88201	151	0.625	0.07042253521126761	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_GL383578v2_alt_15	83	213	2.2e-09	31.4	25151	25399	15	0.7590361445783133	0.29107981220657275	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_27	69	255	0.0038	9.8	50902	51108	27	0.7536231884057971	0.22745098039215686	-1
Cmr5gr11_9_CAS-III-B	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_59	106	137	0.00035	13.1	130649	130966	59	0.5188679245283019	0.40875912408759124	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270873v1_alt_26	64	213	2.7e-11	36.5	81786	81977	26	0.921875	0.2347417840375587	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270873v1_alt_38	105	213	1.1e-09	31.3	113700	114014	38	0.780952380952381	0.352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_14	96	213	1.5e-20	66.8	19880	20167	14	0.9270833333333334	0.38497652582159625	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_21	78	213	6.6e-11	35.3	33650	33883	21	0.8717948717948718	0.29107981220657275	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_41	131	213	3.9e-07	22.9	87591	87983	41	0.45038167938931295	0.20187793427230047	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_47	264	213	4.20E-20	117.6	100500	101291	47	0.8825757575757576	0.9107981220657277	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_6	127	213	3.00E-23	75.6	8751	9131	6	0.9133858267716536	0.4694835680751174	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_61	108	213	1.6e-20	66.7	131617	131940	61	0.8333333333333334	0.39436619718309857	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_68	218	213	8.1e-25	80.7	141754	142407	68	0.944954128440367	0.863849765258216	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_80	172	213	1.9e-14	46.8	156885	157400	80	0.7674418604651163	0.7276995305164319	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_K1270873v1_alt_26	64	298	5.6e-06	18.4	81786	81977	26	0.5	0.10738255033557047	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_14	96	298	3.5e-09	29.0	19880	20167	14	0.9166666666666666	0.2751677852348993	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_47	264	298	1.7e-07	23.5	100500	101291	47	0.6022727272727273	0.47651006711409394	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_6	127	298	3.6e-09	28.9	8751	9131	6	0.6850393700787402	0.27181208053691275	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_61	108	298	5.7e-09	28.3	131617	131940	61	0.8240740740740741	0.2785234899328859	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_K1270874v1_alt_68	218	298	3.1e-05	16.0	141754	142407	68	0.518348623853211	0.3691275167785235	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr21_GL383579v2_alt_65	339	180	0.19	4.8	156185	157201	65	0.35103244837758113	0.4388888888888889	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_GL383579v2_alt_64	1276	213	7.7e-55	179.0	152294	156121	64	0.20141065830721003	1.0	-1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_GL383579v2_alt_74	223	213	2.9e-23	75.9	176013	176681	74	0.5381165919282511	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr21_GL383580v2_alt_60	848	213	8.5e-55	178.9	66692	69235	60	0.30306603773584906	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_GL383579v2_alt_64	1276	298	1.00E-12	40.8	152294	156121	64	0.2249216300904039	0.8456375838926175	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_GL383579v2_alt_74	223	298	5.8e-06	18.6	176013	176681	74	0.38565022421524664	0.2483221476510067	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr21_GL383580v2_alt_60	848	298	7.3e-14	44.5	66692	69235	60	0.25235849056603776	0.6375838926174496	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5_0_CAS-I	chr21_KI270872v1_alt_33	180	201	0.56	3.0	30771	31310	33	0.39444444444444443	0.12935323383084577	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas10_1_CAS-III	chr22_KI270875v1_alt_65	544	654	3.8	-1.2	123424	125055	65	0.20588235294117646	0.08868501529051988	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas3HD_1_CAS-I	chr22_KI270878v1_alt_76	160	191	0.0028	11.6	52699	53178	76	0.225	0.18848167539267016	-1
Cse2gr11_2_CAS-I-E	chr22_KI270878v1_alt_142	57	227	0.0028	11.6	103699	103869	142	0.6491228070175439	0.15859030837004406	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr1gr7_1_CAS-III-B-III-C	chr22_KI270877v1_alt_23	74	587	0.0001	13.7	27997	28218	23	0.6756756756756757	0.08347529812606473	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csx25_0_CAS-III-D	chr22_GL383582v2_alt_95	106	248	0.0012	11.1	146116	146433	95	0.5188679245283019	0.20161290322580644	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CasR_2_CAS-III-B	chrX_KI270880v1_alt_334	51	331	0.0031	11.5	168587	168739	334	0.6078431372549019	0.09365558912386707	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr17_GL000205v2_random_133	337	180	3.2	0.7	45483	46493	133	0.42433234421364985	0.48333333333333334	1
Csx1_15_CAS-III	chr17_GL000205v2_random_55	126	474	0.00014	13.9	16785	17162	55	0.46825396825396826	0.12869198312236288	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_GL000205v2_random_134	656	213	3.00E-20	118.1	46668	48635	134	0.2926829268292683	0.8075117370892019	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr17_GL000205v2_random_134	656	298	7.9e-09	27.9	46668	48635	134	0.35060975609756095	0.697986577181208	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_104	56	213	7.1e-07	21.8	140276	140443	104	0.75	0.18309859154929578	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_105	100	213	7.1e-07	21.8	140478	140777	105	0.6	0.24413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_11	101	213	7.1e-07	21.8	18454	18756	11	0.9603960396039604	0.41784037558685444	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_22	72	213	7.1e-07	21.8	27465	27680	22	0.9305555555555556	0.28169014084507044	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_32	42	213	7.1e-07	21.8	34100	34225	32	0.8571428571428571	0.16901408450704225	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_33	201	213	7.1e-07	21.8	34331	34933	33	0.7960199004975125	0.596244131455399	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_4	257	213	7.1e-07	21.8	1112	1882	4	0.9260700389105059	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_48	96	213	7.1e-07	21.8	48113	48400	48	0.7291666666666666	0.29577464788732394	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_69	329	213	7.1e-07	21.8	94988	95974	69	0.729483282674772	0.9436619718309859	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_72	71	213	7.1e-07	21.8	103309	103521	72	0.7605633802816901	0.23943661971830985	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_77	88	213	7.1e-07	21.8	107129	107392	77	0.7954545454545454	0.29577464788732394	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_89	327	213	7.1e-07	21.8	118713	119693	89	0.7155963302752294	0.9671361502347418	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_91	327	213	7.1e-07	21.8	121445	122425	91	0.7155963302752294	0.9671361502347418	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_33	201	298	7.1e-07	21.8	34331	34933	33	0.43781094527363185	0.2550335570469799	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_4	257	298	7.1e-07	21.8	1112	1882	4	0.6070038910505836	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_69	329	298	7.1e-07	21.8	94988	95974	69	0.6048632218844985	0.587248322147651	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_72	71	298	7.1e-07	21.8	103309	103521	72	0.8169014084507042	0.20134228187919462	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_77	88	298	7.1e-07	21.8	107129	107392	77	0.5909090909090909	0.17785234899328858	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_89	327	298	7.1e-07	21.8	118713	119693	89	0.6483180428134556	0.6308724832214765	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrX_KI270881v1_alt_91	327	298	7.1e-07	21.8	121445	122425	91	0.6483180428134556	0.6308724832214765	1

	Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270882v1_alt_3	557	213	1,60E-22	126.0	10235	11905	3	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270882v1_alt_3	557	298	1,60E-22	126.0	10235	11905	3	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270883v1_alt_2	557	213	2.6e-38	124.2	3514	5184	2	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270883v1_alt_2	557	298	2.6e-38	124.2	3514	5184	2	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270884v1_alt_2	420	213	8.9e-39	125.6	3963	5222	2	0.4642857142857143	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270884v1_alt_2	420	298	8.9e-39	125.6	3963	5222	2	0.37142857142857144	0.4664429530201342	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270885v1_alt_3	557	213	9.2e-39	126.2	4089	5759	3	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270885v1_alt_3	557	298	9.2e-39	126.2	4089	5759	3	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270887v1_alt_13	557	213	2,00E-38	126.0	15910	17580	13	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270887v1_alt_5	154	213	2,00E-38	126.0	3910	4371	5	0.19480519480519481	0.11737089201877934	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270887v1_alt_13	557	298	2,00E-38	126.0	15910	17580	13	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270888v1_alt_6	557	213	1,60E-22	126.2	3653	5323	6	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270888v1_alt_6	557	298	1,60E-22	126.2	3653	5323	6	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270890v1_alt_3	557	213	1.3e-38	126.0	3769	5439	3	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270890v1_alt_3	557	298	1.3e-38	126.0	3769	5439	3	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270890v1_alt_3	557	213	1.3e-38	126.0	3769	5439	3	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270890v1_alt_3	557	298	1.3e-38	126.0	3769	5439	3	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_KI270729v1_random_717	580	213	6.5e-05	18.7	193337	195076	717	0.1103448275862069	0.2676056338028169	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270891v1_alt_3	557	213	2.1e-38	125.0	3780	5450	3	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270891v1_alt_3	557	298	2.1e-38	125.0	3780	5450	3	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
	Cas1_3_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_KI270894v1_alt_219	138	262	0.0033	10.9	195556	195969	219	0.34782608695652173	0.183206106870229	1
	Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr2_KI270894v1_alt_182	237	180	0.14	6.2	164509	165219	182	0.6455696202531646	0.6111111111111112	-1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_KI270894v1_alt_181	269	213	1.8e-23	77.5	163392	164198	181	0.587360594795539	0.5868544600938967	-1
	RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_KI270894v1_alt_181	269	298	1.6e-05	18.2	163392	164198	181	0.3308550185873606	0.25838926174496646	-1
	Csf1_0_IV	chr2_KI270893v1_alt_81	379	227	0.0013	10.9	90255	91391	81	0.11873350923482849	0.06607929515418502	-1
	Cas8c_2_CAS-I-C	chr4_KI270896v1_alt_94	511	713	0.00034	12.5	184984	186516	94	0.8199608610567515	0.20897615708274894	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_KI270896v1_alt_127	97	213	4.7e-19	62.2	305118	305408	127	0.9175257731958762	0.38497652582159625	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_KI270896v1_alt_128	572	213	8.4e-07	22.1	305445	307160	128	0.11713286713286714	0.2347417840375587	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_KI270896v1_alt_139	181	213	5.3e-37	120.8	329250	329792	139	0.9171270718232044	0.6948356807511737	1
	RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_KI270896v1_alt_73	160	213	3.1e-33	108.5	131164	131643	73	0.9375	0.6244131455399061	-1

RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_KI270896v1_alt_127	97	298	1.3e-08	27.4	305118	305408	127	0.9072164948453608	0.2751677852348993	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_KI270896v1_alt_139	181	298	6.2e-13	41.6	329250	329792	139	0.8674033149171271	0.4899328859060403	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_KI270896v1_alt_73	160	298	1.6e-11	36.9	131164	131643	73	0.9	0.4228187919463087	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_1043	647	213	8.4e-54	178.4	1135774	1137714	1043	0.3972179289026275	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_271	289	213	8.4e-54	178.4	306421	307287	271	0.41522491349480967	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_272	254	213	8.4e-54	178.4	307384	308145	272	0.4015748031496063	0.4272300469483568	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_41	189	213	8.4e-54	178.4	65122	65688	41	0.5291005291005291	0.3474178403755869	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_446	289	213	8.4e-54	178.4	504933	505799	446	0.41522491349480967	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_447	254	213	8.4e-54	178.4	505896	506657	447	0.4015748031496063	0.4272300469483568	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_47	162	213	8.4e-54	178.4	74885	75370	47	0.6975308641975309	0.4084507042253521	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_768	162	213	8.4e-54	178.4	793808	794293	768	0.6975308641975309	0.4084507042253521	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_774	189	213	8.4e-54	178.4	803490	804056	774	0.5291005291005291	0.3474178403755869	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_1043	647	298	8.4e-54	178.4	1135774	1137714	1043	0.33075734157650694	0.6375838926174496	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_272	254	298	8.4e-54	178.4	307384	308145	272	0.3661417322834646	0.2953020134228188	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_KI270897v1_alt_447	254	298	8.4e-54	178.4	505896	506657	447	0.3661417322834646	0.2953020134228188	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_7284	98	284	5.3e-05	21.8	4242317	4242610	7284	0.29591836734693877	0.1056338028169014	-1
Cas10_6_CAS-III	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_7031	67	717	0.034	11.6	4041453	4041653	7031	0.6417910447761194	0.058577405857740586	1
Cas1_0_I-II-III-V	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_952	103	315	0.66	7.6	663091	663399	952	0.34951456310679613	0.11428571428571428	1
Cas1_0_IE	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4183	169	269	2.2	6.3	2538649	2539155	4183	0.40828402366863903	0.17472118959107807	-1
Cas2_7_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6881	89	94	0.026	13.9	3925504	3925770	6881	0.4044943820224719	0.3829787234042553	1
Cas2_8_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_7480	72	101	0.011	14.5	4364768	4364983	7480	0.6666666666666666	0.48514851485148514	-1
Cas3_0_CAS-I	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1156	194	353	0.086	10.8	816769	817350	1156	0.42783505154639173	0.23229461756373937	-1
Cas3_0_I	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1156	194	358	0.05	11.5	816769	817350	1156	0.25257731958762886	0.13687150837988826	-1
Cas5_0_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_307	122	182	0.44	9.2	232110	232475	307	0.4098360655737705	0.27472527472527475	-1
Cas5_1_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_307	122	180	0.61	8.7	232110	232475	307	0.36885245901639346	0.24444444444444444	-1
Cas8a1_0_IB	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_3260	73	308	0.016	13.5	2091588	2091806	3260	0.5068493150684932	0.11363636363636363	-1
Cas8b2_1_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_3260	73	334	0.046	11.8	2091588	2091806	3260	0.5068493150684932	0.10479041916167664	-1
Cas8b2_4_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1201	85	65	1.7	7.9	859804	860058	1201	0.3764705882352941	0.2923076923076923	-1
Cas8b2_4_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_5682	65	65	0.014	14.6	3289944	3290138	5682	0.676923076923077	0.6615384615384615	1
Cas8b2_8_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_5682	65	70	0.00022	20.3	3289944	3290138	5682	0.676923076923077	0.7	1
Cas8f_4_CAS-I-F	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2222	73	450	0.028	11.7	1487199	1487417	2222	0.7671232876712328	0.12222222222222222	1
Cas9_0_CAS-II-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6272	116	804	0.014	12.5	3561507	3561854	6272	0.5258620689655172	0.06840796019900497	1
Cas9_0_IIB	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6272	116	802	0.0071	13.5	3561507	3561854	6272	0.5258620689655172	0.06982543640897755	1
Cmr3gr5_1_CAS-III-B-III-C	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1878	65	324	0.067	11.8	1287658	1287852	1878	0.7076923076923077	0.14506172839506173	-1
Cmr5gr11_8_CAS-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_5871	289	149	0.18	10.4	3374356	3375222	5871	0.09688581314878893	0.18791946308724833	1
Cse2gr11_4_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1368	113	181	0.084	11.7	988769	989107	1368	0.5929203539823009	0.36464088397790057	-1
Csf1_0_IV	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_5994	153	227	0.066	11.6	3428143	3428601	5994	0.477124183006536	0.29515418502202645	-1
Csf3_0_IV	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_5578	93	222	0.019	13.6	3244792	3245070	5578	0.3763440860215054	0.14864864864864866	-1
Csm3gr7_10_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4691	106	228	0.038	12.3	2813959	2814276	4691	0.46226415094339623	0.17105263157894737	-1
Csm3gr7_5_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_7394	72	620	0.095	9.9	4301888	4302103	7394	0.44444444444444444	0.05	1
Csx19_10_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4128	317	121	0.66	9.0	2506351	2507301	4128	0.5110410094637224	0.4132231404958678	-1
Csx19_18_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_3377	90	200	0.043	11.8	2144737	2145006	3377	0.55555555555555556	0.245	-1
Csx19_19_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_3377	90	200	0.043	11.8	2144737	2145006	3377	0.55555555555555556	0.245	-1

Csx1_15_CAS-III	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_826	112	474	0.037	11.8	558243	558578	826	0.4642857142857143	0.10759493670886076	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1040	280	213	2.7e-41	140.4	727178	728017	1040	0.8785714285714286	0.971830985915493	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1054	262	213	1.7e-05	23.4	736185	736970	1054	0.2633587786259542	0.43661971830985913	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1090	308	213	1.4e-11	43.3	764136	765059	1090	0.32792207792207795	0.352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1094	155	213	8.70E-07	76.7	768734	769198	1094	0.9419354838709677	0.6056338028169014	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1133	162	213	1.10E-14	105.7	797477	797962	1133	0.9506172839506173	0.6431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1193	74	213	6.4e-08	31.4	850369	850590	1193	0.7027027027027027	0.215962441314554	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_137	447	213	2.1e-19	68.9	113719	115059	137	0.2796420581655481	0.5258215962441315	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_138	171	213	1.00E-10	89.5	115053	115565	138	0.9005847953216374	0.568075117370892	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1848	186	213	9.6e-21	73.3	1266932	1267489	1848	0.5053763440860215	0.38967136150234744	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1849	141	213	1.3e-23	82.6	1267483	1267905	1849	0.9361702127659575	0.539906103286385	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_217	161	213	6.00E-20	123.0	176420	176902	217	0.9751552795031055	0.9107981220657277	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2335	819	213	9.5e-51	171.3	1560676	1563132	2335	0.3076923076923077	0.9765258215962441	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2623	218	213	5.40E-29	149.2	1730716	1731369	2623	0.9678899082568807	0.8826291079812206	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2865	116	213	0.00098	17.7	1893034	1893381	2865	0.5344827586206896	0.18309859154929578	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2866	118	213	0.015	13.8	1893432	1893785	2866	0.4661016949152542	0.2347417840375587	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2903	280	213	8.6e-31	106.1	1913858	1914697	2903	0.6392857142857142	0.6854460093896714	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2907	155	213	2.9e-10	39.0	1916700	1917164	2907	0.4774193548387097	0.29577464788732394	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2978	107	213	0.006	15.1	1957367	1957687	2978	0.6822429906542056	0.2676056338028169	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_3072	201	213	4.7e-22	77.6	2004531	2005133	3072	0.7164179104477612	0.5352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_354	114	213	0.00014	20.4	261514	261855	354	0.43859649122807015	0.25821596244131456	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4024	127	213	2.2e-10	39.4	2448015	2448395	4024	0.5275590551181102	0.3286384976525822	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4575	269	213	1.3e-39	134.9	2737013	2737819	4575	0.8773234200743495	0.9248826291079812	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_458	130	213	4.3e-22	77.7	320555	320944	458	0.9	0.4694835680751174	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4691	106	213	1.6e-09	36.6	2813959	2814276	4691	0.7830188679245284	0.4131455399061033	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4692	122	213	2.2e-05	23.1	2814301	2814666	4692	0.5163934426229508	0.4084507042253521	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4864	161	213	9.00E-15	53.8	2912577	2913059	4864	0.8881987577639752	0.863849765258216	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_496	218	213	5.00E-11	41.5	342481	343134	496	0.24311926605504589	0.22535211267605634	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_497	159	213	1.9e-30	104.9	343186	343662	497	0.9371069182389937	0.6197183098591549	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6567	184	213	8.70E-15	102.8	3697292	3697843	6567	0.907608695652174	0.704225352112676	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6615	200	213	2.4e-06	26.2	3721213	3721812	6615	0.33	0.24882629107981222	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6856	713	213	1.40E-17	115.2	3905910	3908048	6856	0.2791023842917251	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6866	145	213	1.4e-14	53.1	3913720	3914154	6866	0.4827586206896552	0.38028169014084506	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_693	158	213	4.50E-07	77.6	451705	452178	693	0.7468354430379747	0.49295774647887325	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6957	158	213	9.3e-25	86.4	3977387	3977860	6957	0.8607594936708861	0.812206572769953	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_7246	169	213	3.5e-23	81.2	4216713	4217219	7246	0.9526627218934911	0.676056338028169	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_7373	94	213	0.0016	17.0	4287582	4287863	7373	0.6170212765957447	0.24413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_7647	89	213	6.4e-05	21.6	4464306	4464572	7647	0.4157303370786517	0.17370892018779344	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_812	251	213	2.7e-22	78.3	546604	547356	812	0.7091633466135459	0.6807511737089202	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_820	135	213	1.4e-10	40.0	553966	554370	820	0.7407407407407407	0.3474178403755869	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_880	96	213	5.2e-07	28.4	607718	608005	880	0.6458333333333334	0.26291079812206575	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_953	565	213	6.6e-32	109.7	663729	665423	953	0.3168141592920354	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_971	130	213	1.9e-09	36.3	678971	679360	971	0.7923076923076923	0.431924882629108	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_985	136	213	0.012	14.1	688644	689051	985	0.22794117647058823	0.14553990610328638	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1094	155	298	0.00075	17.3	768734	769198	1094	0.8838709677419355	0.39932885906040266	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1133	162	298	3.00E-08	31.8	797477	797962	1133	0.8888888888888888	0.4228187919463087	-1

RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1193	74	298	0.061	11.1	850369	850590	1193	0.6891891891891891	0.1912751677852349	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_138	171	298	7.6e-06	23.9	115053	115565	138	0.52046783625731	0.25838926174496646	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_1849	141	298	0.00024	19.0	1267483	1267905	1849	0.6382978723404256	0.26174496644295303	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_217	161	298	0.00041	18.2	176420	176902	217	0.453416149068323	0.23825503355704697	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2335	819	298	6.3e-13	47.1	1560676	1563132	2335	0.2612942612942613	0.6375838926174496	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2623	218	298	8.2e-11	40.2	1730716	1731369	2623	0.5275229357798165	0.3691275167785235	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_2903	280	298	1.00E-08	33.3	1913858	1914697	2903	0.5142857142857142	0.4228187919463087	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_3072	201	298	0.00016	19.6	2004531	2005133	3072	0.4626865671641791	0.27181208053691275	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4024	127	298	3.9e-08	31.4	2448015	2448395	4024	0.5748031496062992	0.2516778523489933	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4575	269	298	1.4e-09	36.1	2737013	2737819	4575	0.6171003717472119	0.4899328859060403	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_458	130	298	0.00052	17.9	320555	320944	458	0.6846153846153846	0.25838926174496646	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4864	161	298	0.012	13.4	2912577	2913059	4864	0.5527950310559007	0.2953020134228188	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_497	159	298	5.2e-08	31.0	343186	343662	497	0.5534591194968553	0.2751677852348993	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6567	184	298	5.00E-07	27.8	3697292	3697843	6567	0.8532608695652174	0.4697986577181208	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_6856	713	298	7.6e-08	30.5	3905910	3908048	6856	0.2187938288920056	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_693	158	298	0.0015	16.4	451705	452178	693	0.7151898734177216	0.35570469798657717	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_953	565	298	5.3e-08	31.0	663729	665423	953	0.2938053097345133	0.5	-1
RecD_0_IVD	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_3376	116	763	0.00098	16.2	2144314	2144661	3376	0.27586206896551724	0.04062909567496723	-1
SSgr11_0_CAS-III-F	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_4347	72	197	0.039	12.6	2625630	2625845	4347	0.4861111111111111	0.18274111675126903	-1
TnsC_0_V-K	chr6_GL000251v2_alt_7604	164	283	0.012	13.6	4439530	4440021	7604	0.5304878048780488	0.2826855123674912	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr7_KI270899v1_alt_24	713	213	8.1e-39	126.3	39814	41952	24	0.29312762973352036	0.7981220657276995	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr7_KI270899v1_alt_24	713	298	1.7e-11	36.4	39814	41952	24	0.24684431977559607	0.5369127516778524	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas7_0_IC	chr17_KI270730v1_random_251	45	284	0.003	12.0	48131	48265	251	0.5555555555555556	0.0880281690140845	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270901v1_alt_12	492	213	3.10E-39	179.4	28125	29600	12	0.5223577235772358	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270901v1_alt_29	141	213	3.10E-39	179.4	66934	67356	29	0.9645390070921985	0.596244131455399	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270901v1_alt_12	492	298	3.10E-39	179.4	28125	29600	12	0.4349593495934959	0.6375838926174496	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270901v1_alt_29	141	298	3.10E-39	179.4	66934	67356	29	0.5815602836879432	0.2550335570469799	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_287	94	180	0.0027	12.1	208188	208469	287	0.6808510638297872	0.3444444444444444	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_295	339	180	0.073	7.4	218163	219179	295	0.29793510324483774	0.4444444444444444	1
Cse2gr11_6_CAS-I-E	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_376	62	183	0.023	8.8	307465	307650	376	0.5483870967741935	0.09289617486338798	-1
Cse2gr11_6_CAS-I-E	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_377	151	183	0.41	4.7	307668	308120	377	0.5496688741721855	0.10382513661202186	-1
Csf2_1_IVA3	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_145	150	263	0.013	9.2	110970	111419	145	0.5666666666666667	0.07604562737642585	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_286	152	213	5.5e-24	79.5	207116	207571	286	0.7894736842105263	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_297	741	213	8.9e-48	157.2	220844	223066	297	0.32118758434547906	0.9342723004694836	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_63	171	213	2.1e-27	90.7	57142	57654	63	0.8596491228070176	0.5352112676056338	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_64	321	213	9.7e-22	72.2	57648	58610	64	0.2897196261682243	0.38497652582159625	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_286	152	298	3.8e-05	17.2	207116	207571	286	0.5657894736842105	0.2483221476510067	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_297	741	298	2.3e-11	37.6	220844	223066	297	0.25101214574898784	0.5704697986577181	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270900v1_alt_63	171	298	4.9e-07	23.4	57142	57654	63	0.5263157894736842	0.26174496644295303	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas6_8_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr11_KI270903v1_alt_79	93	275	0.0022	11.8	52286	52564	79	0.5913978494623656	0.19636363636363635	1

Csb3_0_JU	chr11_K1270903v1_alt_89	63	282	0.0022	11.8	55151	55339	89	0.5079365079365079	0.11347517730496454	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas1_1_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_345	114	261	0.026	9.0	306649	306990	345	0.9298245614035088	0.3486590038314176	1
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_335	90	255	0.096	7.4	300118	300387	335	0.6666666666666666	0.2235294117647059	1
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_387	98	255	0.063	8.0	354368	354661	387	0.5714285714285714	0.2196078431372549	-1
Csm2gr11_7_CAS-III-A	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_565	130	110	0.0034	13.7	510210	510599	565	0.4846153846153846	0.5727272727272728	1
Csx25_0_CAS-III-D	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_362	82	248	0.0018	13.0	324937	325182	362	0.524390243902439	0.17338709677419356	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_331	182	213	0.0001	17.3	297055	297600	331	0.3076923076923077	0.18779342723004694	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_346	256	213	1.5e-34	114.7	307088	307855	346	0.64453125	0.6948356807511737	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_378	196	213	3.7e-23	77.5	342749	343336	378	0.6122448979591837	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_379	186	213	1.2e-20	69.3	343450	344007	379	0.5	0.38497652582159625	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_465	145	213	8.4e-18	60.0	416568	417002	465	0.6482758620689655	0.39436619718309857	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_529	84	213	3.00E-11	38.6	482278	482529	529	0.9642857142857143	0.352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_541	295	213	1.1e-40	134.8	488907	489791	541	0.8	0.9342723004694836	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_549	578	213	5.30E-39	181.6	495941	497674	549	0.444636678200692	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_570	81	213	1.7e-15	52.5	512892	513134	570	0.9135802469135802	0.3192488262910798	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_571	256	213	8.1e-24	79.7	513128	513895	571	0.6171875	0.5868544600938967	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_595	131	213	7.4e-21	70.0	531067	531459	595	0.7251908396946565	0.38497652582159625	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_596	99	213	8.00E-17	56.8	531512	531808	596	0.9292929292929293	0.40375586854460094	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_67	89	213	0.002	13.0	63357	63623	67	0.6629213483146067	0.24882629107981222	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_346	256	298	9.9e-11	36.3	307088	307855	346	0.5859375	0.4664429530201342	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_378	196	298	2.2e-06	22.0	342749	343336	378	0.4387755102040816	0.2483221476510067	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_465	145	298	5.1e-06	20.8	416568	417002	465	0.593103448275862	0.2483221476510067	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_541	295	298	2.00E-09	32.0	488907	489791	541	0.4745762711864407	0.40939597315436244	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_549	578	298	1.4e-14	49.0	495941	497674	549	0.370242214532872	0.6375838926174496	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_571	256	298	7.9e-06	20.2	513128	513895	571	0.34765625	0.25838926174496646	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr12_K1270904v1_alt_595	131	298	1.9e-05	19.0	531067	531459	595	0.6641221374045801	0.2516778523489933	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270906v1_alt_107	580	213	6.5e-08	26.0	66814	68553	107	0.1310344827586207	0.27699530516431925	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas4_0_I-II	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_1051	56	180	0.03	11.9	1446098	1446265	1051	0.5714285714285714	0.1777777777777778	-1
Cas4_1_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_302	129	270	0.039	11.3	516377	516763	302	0.34108527131782945	0.16296296296296298	-1
Cas5_6_CAS-I-B	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_2565	409	272	0.023	11.8	3287582	3288808	2565	0.08312958435207823	0.12867647058823528	-1
Cas7_1_CAS-I-C	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_1395	70	278	0.039	11.1	1891135	1891344	1395	0.6428571428571429	0.1618705035971223	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_2040	1074	180	1.2	6.8	2626932	2630153	2040	0.15735567970204842	0.6444444444444445	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_3134	339	180	1.6	6.3	3916345	3917361	3134	0.35103244837758113	0.4	-1
Csx3_0_CAS-I-III	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_2011	99	83	4.0	5.6	2584676	2584972	2011	0.5555555555555556	0.43373493975903615	1
Csx3_0_CAS-I-III	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_3594	99	83	4.0	5.6	4524348	4524644	3594	0.5555555555555556	0.43373493975903615	-1
PD_DExK_0_CAS-I-B	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_3064	154	231	0.031	11.5	3842755	3843216	3064	0.37662337662337664	0.22943722943722944	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_1219	213	213	7.1e-30	102.1	1662303	1662941	1219	0.7699530516431925	0.6807511737089202	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_1958	260	213	4.4e-23	79.9	2526625	2527404	1958	0.46153846153846156	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_2040	1074	213	1.4e-51	173.0	2626932	2630153	2040	0.239292364990689	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_3030	61	213	0.00096	16.7	3804568	3804750	3030	0.9016393442622951	0.22535211267605634	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_3121	135	213	2.7e-19	67.5	3904951	3905355	3121	0.9037037037037037	0.5117370892018779	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_3132	201	213	3.5e-39	132.5	3914080	3914682	3132	0.9900497512437811	0.8262910798122066	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_K1270905v1_alt_3446	213	213	7.1e-12	43.3	4332197	4332835	3446	0.4272300469483568	0.3051643192488263	-1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3447	135	213	2.5e-19	67.6	4332838	4333242	3447	0.9037037037037037	0.5117370892018779	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3475	217	213	1.9e-30	104.0	4364001	4364651	3475	0.9631336405529954	0.8732394366197183	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3524	135	213	3.4e-23	80.2	4427104	4427508	3524	0.9481481481481482	0.539906103286385	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3560	1074	213	3.4e-50	168.5	4470888	4474109	3560	0.239292364990689	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3647	260	213	4.3e-23	79.9	4581917	4582696	3647	0.46153846153846156	0.4413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_1219	213	298	2.2e-09	34.5	1662303	1662941	1219	0.4694835680751174	0.3187919463087248	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_1958	260	298	1.1e-05	22.4	2526625	2527404	1958	0.3346153846153846	0.2516778523489933	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_2040	1074	298	1.6e-11	41.5	2626932	2630153	2040	0.26256983240223464	0.8422818791946308	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3121	135	298	0.0016	15.2	3904951	3905355	3121	0.4	0.18456375838926176	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3132	201	298	7.3e-09	32.8	3914080	3914682	3132	0.8159203980099502	0.47315436241610737	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3447	135	298	0.0011	15.8	4332838	4333242	3447	0.43703703703703706	0.20134228187919462	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3524	135	298	0.0016	15.2	4427104	4427508	3524	0.3925925925925926	0.18120805369127516	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3560	1074	298	3.8e-11	40.3	4470888	4474109	3560	0.2644320297951583	0.8456375838926175	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr15_KI270905v1_alt_3647	260	298	1.1e-05	22.4	4581917	4582696	3647	0.3346153846153846	0.2516778523489933	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_KI270909v1_alt_47	191	213	3.3e-18	58.9	174407	174979	47	0.6387434554973822	0.6901408450704225	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_KI270909v1_alt_94	191	213	3.3e-18	58.9	275974	276546	94	0.6387434554973822	0.6901408450704225	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr17_KI270909v1_alt_47	191	298	3.3e-18	58.9	174407	174979	47	0.4397905759162304	0.28859060402684567	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr17_KI270909v1_alt_94	191	298	3.3e-18	58.9	275974	276546	94	0.4397905759162304	0.28859060402684567	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_9_CAS-III-B	chr17_JH159148v1_alt_56	88	137	0.00016	13.5	64051	64314	56	0.6363636363636364	0.41605839416058393	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_JH159148v1_alt_54	208	213	0.00016	13.5	62502	63125	54	0.4855769230769231	0.352112670656338	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr17_JH159148v1_alt_71	289	213	0.00016	13.5	73783	74649	71	0.8581314878892734	0.9906103286384976	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr17_JH159148v1_alt_71	289	298	0.00016	13.5	73783	74649	71	0.532871972318339	0.4597315436241611	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8b1_12_CAS-I-B	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_2067	95	503	0.025	10.1	1386382	1386666	2067	0.43157894736842106	0.0775347912524851	1
Cas8f_4_CAS-I-F	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_466	82	450	0.025	10.1	271758	272003	466	0.45121951219512196	0.08888888888888889	-1
Cmr4_0_III-B	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_379	120	283	0.025	10.1	203861	204220	379	0.65	0.2862190812720848	-1
Cmr4_0_III-B	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_386	120	283	0.025	10.1	207855	208214	386	0.65	0.2862190812720848	-1
Cmr4_0_III-B	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_393	120	283	0.025	10.1	211848	212207	393	0.65	0.2862190812720848	-1
Cmr4_0_III-B	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_400	120	283	0.025	10.1	215842	216201	400	0.65	0.2862190812720848	-1
Cmr4_0_III-B	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_407	120	283	0.025	10.1	219836	220195	407	0.65	0.2862190812720848	-1
Csx25_0_CAS-III-D	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_1065	154	248	0.025	10.1	631926	632387	1065	0.42857142857142855	0.24193548387096775	-1
Csx3_1_CAS-I-III	chr17_KI270908v1_alt_1627	54	84	0.025	10.1	1052682	1052843	1627	0.7407407407407407	0.4642857142857143	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr19_GL949747v2_alt_1103	508	284	0.0015	14.4	627411	628934	1103	0.04133858267716536	0.07394366197183098	1
PrimPol_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL949747v2_alt_180	84	361	0.0015	14.4	88422	88673	180	0.7857142857142857	0.18282548476454294	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL949747v2_alt_1183	180	213	0.0015	14.4	667568	668107	1183	0.6888888888888889	0.460093896713615	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL949747v2_alt_862	557	213	0.0015	14.4	508881	510551	862	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL949747v2_alt_879	91	213	0.0015	14.4	522089	522361	879	0.34065934065934067	0.12206572769953052	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL949747v2_alt_1183	180	298	0.0015	14.4	667568	668107	1183	0.49444444444444446	0.25838926174496646	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL949747v2_alt_862	557	298	0.0015	14.4	508881	510551	862	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	-1
SSgr11_1_CAS-III-F	chr19_GL949747v2_alt_39	76	97	0.0015	14.4	22956	23183	39	0.47368421052631576	0.3711340206185567	1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CasR_2_CAS-III-B	chrX_KI270913v1_alt_321	51	331	0.0031	11.5	157727	157879	321	0.6078431372549019	0.09365558912386707	1
Csx3_1_CAS-I-III	chrX_KI270913v1_alt_433	75	84	0.0031	11.5	219351	219575	433	0.5333333333333333	0.5	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270915v1_alt_2	557	213	5.2e-39	126.2	3780	5450	2	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270915v1_alt_2	557	298	5.2e-39	126.2	3780	5450	2	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270916v1_alt_4	557	213	1.4e-38	126.0	4022	5692	4	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270916v1_alt_4	557	298	1.4e-38	126.0	4022	5692	4	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270917v1_alt_154	557	213	9.00E-38	124.2	142554	144224	154	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270917v1_alt_154	557	298	9.00E-38	124.2	142554	144224	154	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270919v1_alt_2	557	213	1.4e-38	124.2	3781	5451	2	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270919v1_alt_2	557	298	1.4e-38	124.2	3781	5451	2	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270920v1_alt_73	557	213	1.2e-37	122.0	149631	151301	73	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270920v1_alt_73	557	298	1.2e-37	122.0	149631	151301	73	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270921v1_alt_92	557	213	8.1e-39	126.0	233846	235516	92	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270921v1_alt_92	557	298	8.1e-39	126.0	233846	235516	92	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270922v1_alt_140	557	213	4.9e-38	124.2	139557	141227	140	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270922v1_alt_140	557	298	4.9e-38	124.2	139557	141227	140	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270923v1_alt_82	557	213	2.9e-38	124.2	140973	142643	82	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270923v1_alt_82	557	298	2.9e-38	124.2	140973	142643	82	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	-1
Cas12j_0_CAS-V-J	chr4_KI270925v1_alt_56	130	638	0.0012	11.5	89343	89732	56	0.46923076923076923	0.09090909090909091	-1
Csx26_0_CAS-III-D	chr4_KI270925v1_alt_160	93	119	0.00019	15.8	265817	266095	160	0.7204301075268817	0.5714285714285714	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_KI270925v1_alt_288	160	213	6.8e-33	108.5	446340	446819	288	0.9375	0.6244131455399061	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_KI270925v1_alt_288	160	298	3.5e-11	36.9	446340	446819	288	0.9	0.4228187919463087	-1
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5410	98	284	3.9e-05	21.8	4073688	4073981	5410	0.29591836734693877	0.1056338028169014	-1
Cas1_0_I-II-III-V	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_378	103	315	2.1	5.6	442143	442451	378	0.34951456310679613	0.11428571428571428	1
Cas1_0_IE	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_3010	169	269	1.6	6.3	2315643	2316149	3010	0.40828402366863903	0.17472118959107807	-1
Cas3_0_CAS-I	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_528	194	353	0.064	10.8	595822	596403	528	0.42783505154639173	0.23229461756373937	-1
Cas3_0_I	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_528	194	358	0.037	11.5	595822	596403	528	0.25257731958762886	0.13687150837988826	-1
Cas5_0_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_15	122	182	0.33	9.2	7018	7383	15	0.4098360655737705	0.27472527472527475	-1
Cas5_1_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_15	122	180	0.46	8.7	7018	7383	15	0.36885245901639346	0.24444444444444444	-1
Cas8b2_4_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_552	85	65	1.3	7.9	638847	639101	552	0.3764705882352941	0.2923076923076923	-1
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_556	78	255	6.2	4.7	641904	642137	556	0.7692307692307693	0.23921568627450981	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_483	280	180	1.0	7.6	540201	541040	483	0.30357142857142855	0.45555555555555555	1

Cmf5gr11_8_CAS-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_4281	289	149	0.13	10.4	3144705	3145571	4281	0.09688581314878893	0.18791946308724833	1
Cse2gr11_4_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_679	113	181	0.062	11.7	767840	768178	679	0.5929203539823009	0.36464088397790057	-1
Csf1_0_IV	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_4385	153	227	0.049	11.6	3198496	3198954	4385	0.477124183006536	0.29515418502202645	-1
Csf3_0_IV	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_4027	93	222	0.014	13.6	3015310	3015588	4027	0.3763440860215054	0.14864864864864866	-1
Csm3gr7_10_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_3436	106	228	0.028	12.4	2581110	2581427	3436	0.4339622641509434	0.16666666666666666	-1
Csx19_10_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_2963	317	121	0.49	9.0	2283271	2284221	2963	0.5110410094637224	0.4132231404958678	-1
Csx19_18_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_2315	90	200	0.032	11.8	1920847	1921116	2315	0.5555555555555556	0.245	-1
Csx19_19_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_2315	90	200	0.032	11.8	1920847	1921116	2315	0.5555555555555556	0.245	-1
Csx19_3_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_4492	173	160	0.029	12.5	3253369	3253887	4492	0.1791907514450867	0.21875	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1075	186	213	5.1e-20	70.5	1046133	1046690	1075	0.4946236559139785	0.38028169014084506	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1076	82	213	7.00E-10	37.3	1046861	1047106	1076	0.9024390243902439	0.3004694835680751	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1432	2338	213	5.5e-33	112.8	1332265	1339278	1432	0.06629597946963216	0.6431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_145	82	213	2.5e-10	38.8	95781	96026	145	0.9146341463414634	0.3051643192488263	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_177	159	213	1.40E-14	104.9	118273	118749	177	0.9371069182389937	0.6197183098591549	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1876	116	213	0.00073	17.7	1669201	1669548	1876	0.5344827586206896	0.18309859154929578	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1910	280	213	6.40E-15	106.1	1690027	1690866	1910	0.6392857142857142	0.6854460093896714	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1913	155	213	2.1e-10	39.0	1692870	1693334	1913	0.4774193548387097	0.29577464788732394	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1972	107	213	0.0045	15.1	1733467	1733787	1972	0.6822429906542056	0.2676056338028169	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_2052	201	213	3.50E-06	77.6	1780632	1781234	2052	0.7164179104477612	0.5352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_272	174	213	3.00E-09	35.3	325732	326253	272	0.5804597701149425	0.352112676056338	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_278	135	213	1.1e-10	40.0	333090	333494	278	0.7407407407407407	0.3474178403755869	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_2879	127	213	1.6e-10	39.4	2242751	2225131	2879	0.5275590551181102	0.3286384976525822	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_321	96	213	3.9e-07	28.4	386770	387057	321	0.6458333333333334	0.26291079812206575	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_3347	269	213	9.8e-40	134.9	2513887	2514693	3347	0.8773234200743495	0.9248826291079812	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_3436	106	213	1.2e-09	36.6	2581110	2581427	3436	0.7830188679245284	0.4131455399061033	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_3437	122	213	1.6e-05	23.1	2581452	2581817	3437	0.5163934426229508	0.4084507042253521	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_379	565	213	1.2e-31	108.5	442781	444475	379	0.3168141592920354	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_393	130	213	1.4e-09	36.3	458027	458416	393	0.7923076923076923	0.431924882629108	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_404	136	213	0.009	14.1	467705	468112	404	0.22794117647058823	0.14553990610328638	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_442	280	213	2.00E-41	140.4	506219	507058	442	0.8785714285714286	0.971830985915493	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_456	262	213	7.8e-06	24.1	515226	516011	456	0.2633587786259542	0.43661971830985913	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_4831	184	213	6.5e-30	102.8	3500302	3500853	4831	0.907608695652174	0.704225352112676	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_486	308	213	1.00E-11	43.3	543179	544102	486	0.32792207792207795	0.352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_4872	200	213	1.8e-06	26.2	3524219	3524818	4872	0.33	0.24882629107981222	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_490	155	213	9.9e-22	76.1	547776	548240	490	0.9419354838709677	0.6056338028169014	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5036	84	213	0.00016	19.8	3690443	3690694	5036	0.8095238095238095	0.27230046948356806	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5057	137	213	3.3e-23	80.9	3709710	3710120	5057	0.9927007299270073	0.5586854460093896	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5066	143	213	5.70E-07	76.8	3715901	3716329	5066	0.7132867132867133	0.5305164319248826	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_512	162	213	8.2e-31	105.7	576530	577015	512	0.9506172839506173	0.6431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5194	1276	213	7.80E-38	177.7	3861784	3865611	5194	0.20141065830721003	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5375	104	213	2.7e-10	38.7	4048095	4048406	5375	0.9134615384615384	0.4131455399061033	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_54	114	213	0.00011	20.4	36422	36763	54	0.43859649122807015	0.25821596244131456	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5482	94	213	0.0012	17.0	4118910	4119191	5482	0.6170212765957447	0.24413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5686	89	213	4.7e-05	21.6	4295725	4295991	5686	0.4157303370786517	0.17370892018779344	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1432	2338	298	1.00E-08	32.9	1332265	1339278	1432	0.06372968349016253	0.4597315436241611	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_177	159	298	3.9e-08	31.0	118273	118749	177	0.5534591194968553	0.2751677852348993	1

RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_1910	280	298	7.7e-09	33.3	1690027	1690866	1910	0.5142857142857142	0.4228187919463087	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_2052	201	298	0.00012	19.6	1780632	1781234	2052	0.4626865671641791	0.27181208053691275	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_2879	127	298	2.9e-08	31.4	2224751	2225131	2879	0.5748031496062992	0.2516778523489933	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_3347	269	298	1.1e-09	36.1	2513887	2514693	3347	0.6171003717472119	0.4899328859060403	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_379	565	298	8.2e-08	29.9	442781	444475	379	0.2920353982300885	0.4966442953020134	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_4831	184	298	3.7e-07	27.8	3500302	3500853	4831	0.8532608695652174	0.4697986577181208	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_490	155	298	0.00045	17.7	547776	548240	490	0.8838709677419355	0.39932885906040266	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5057	137	298	6.3e-06	23.7	3709710	3710120	5057	0.6423357664233577	0.2751677852348993	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_512	162	298	2.2e-08	31.8	576530	577015	512	0.8888888888888888	0.4228187919463087	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5194	1276	298	3.9e-11	40.8	3861784	3865611	5194	0.2249216300940439	0.8456375838926175	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_5375	104	298	0.017	12.5	4048095	4048406	5375	0.8461538461538461	0.2785234899328859	-1
RecD_0_IVD	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_2314	116	763	0.00073	16.2	1920424	1920771	2314	0.27586206896551724	0.04062909567496723	-1
SSgr11_0_CAS-III-F	chr6_GL000252v2_alt_3151	69	197	0.027	12.6	2402521	2402727	3151	0.5072463768115942	0.18274111675126903	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr8_KI270926v1_alt_6	94	180	0.00063	12.1	11667	11948	6	0.6808510638297872	0.3444444444444444	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr8_KI270926v1_alt_9	305	180	0.013	7.8	21730	22644	9	0.33114754098360655	0.3611111111111111	1
Cse2gr11_6_CAS-I-E	chr8_KI270926v1_alt_38	65	183	0.0045	9.1	110802	110996	38	0.5230769230769231	0.09289617486338798	-1
Cse2gr11_6_CAS-I-E	chr8_KI270926v1_alt_39	170	183	0.083	4.9	111005	111514	39	0.5882352941176471	0.09836065573770492	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr8_KI270926v1_alt_10	1275	213	5.5e-54	175.5	22708	26532	10	0.2227450980392157	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr8_KI270926v1_alt_10	1275	298	3.1e-13	41.7	22708	26532	10	0.22588235294117648	0.8456375838926175	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr1_KI270706v1_random_116	117	180	0.00018	14.8	154000	154350	116	0.7264957264957265	0.4611111111111111	1
Csa5gr11_9_CAS-I-A	chr1_KI270706v1_random_10	75	115	0.00018	14.8	12627	12851	10	0.8666666666666667	0.5565217391304348	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_KI270706v1_random_7	257	213	0.00018	14.8	9334	10104	7	0.6964980544747081	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_KI270707v1_random_32	431	213	0.00018	14.8	29174	30466	32	0.5986078886310905	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_KI270706v1_random_7	257	298	0.00018	14.8	9334	10104	7	0.5603112840466926	0.4228187919463087	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_KI270707v1_random_32	431	298	0.00018	14.8	29174	30466	32	0.4988399071925754	0.6375838926174496	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8b1_6_CAS-I-B	chr22_KI270928v1_alt_11	62	569	0.003	10.1	8166	8351	11	0.5483870967741935	0.05975395430579965	-1
Csb1gr7_0_CAS-I-U	chr22_KI270928v1_alt_198	95	169	0.002	11.9	127524	127808	198	0.4105263157894737	0.23668639053254437	1
Csx25_0_CAS-III-D	chr22_KI270928v1_alt_230	91	248	0.002	11.6	158217	158489	230	0.6153846153846154	0.20161290322580644	-1
Csx3_2_CAS-I-III	chr22_KI270928v1_alt_44	159	277	0.0018	11.3	30822	31298	44	0.1509433962264151	0.08664259927797834	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr22_KI270928v1_alt_47	93	213	4.8e-08	26.8	33629	33907	47	0.6129032258064516	0.29107981220657275	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr22_KI270928v1_alt_47	93	298	9.7e-06	18.6	33629	33907	47	0.6559139784946236	0.21140939597315436	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270929v1_alt_118	557	213	1,00E-38	126.2	137826	139496	118	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270929v1_alt_118	557	298	1,00E-38	126.2	137826	139496	118	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270930v1_alt_2	557	213	8.2e-39	126.2	3780	5450	2	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270930v1_alt_2	557	298	8.2e-39	126.2	3780	5450	2	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270931v1_alt_4	557	213	3,80E-22	124.2	4137	5807	4	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270931v1_alt_4	557	298	3,80E-22	124.2	4137	5807	4	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270932v1_alt_2	557	213	9.2e-39	126.0	4115	5785	2	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270932v1_alt_2	557	298	9.2e-39	126.0	4115	5785	2	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270933v1_alt_4	557	213	3.7e-38	125.0	3780	5450	4	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270933v1_alt_4	557	298	3.7e-38	125.0	3780	5450	4	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4999	94	284	0.00034	18.6	4249469	4249750	4999	0.2553191489361702	0.0880281690140845	-1
Cas1_0_I-II-III-V	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_462	101	315	1.8	5.6	442109	442411	462	0.3564356435643564	0.11428571428571428	1
Cas1_0_JE	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2963	169	269	1.5	6.3	2366779	2367285	2963	0.40828402366863903	0.17472118959107807	-1
Cas3_0_CAS-I	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_606	194	353	0.057	10.8	595781	596362	606	0.42783505154639173	0.23229461756373937	-1
Cas3_0_I	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_606	194	358	0.034	11.5	595781	596362	606	0.25257731958762886	0.13687150837988826	-1
Cas4_0_I-II-V	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4562	125	177	0.027	12.8	3783341	3783715	4562	0.456	0.3220338983050847	-1
Cas4_0_IA	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2941	191	273	0.083	10.8	2350628	2351200	2941	0.08900523560209424	0.06227106227106227	-1
Cas5_0_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_13	111	182	0.0099	14.0	7018	7350	13	0.45045045045045046	0.27472527472527475	-1
Cas5_1_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_13	111	180	0.014	13.6	7018	7350	13	0.40540540540540543	0.24444444444444444	-1
Cas8b2_0_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2781	62	389	0.079	10.6	2218409	2218594	2781	0.5483870967741935	0.09254498714652956	1
Cas8f_4_CAS-I-F	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1475	73	450	0.019	11.7	1268545	1268763	1475	0.7671232876712328	0.12222222222222222	1
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1189	143	255	4.8	4.9	1058052	1058480	1189	0.4405594405594406	0.2627450980392157	1
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_644	78	255	5.6	4.7	641546	641779	644	0.7692307692307693	0.23921568627450981	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1390	339	180	5.9	5.0	1207886	1208902	1390	0.3480825958702065	0.43333333333333335	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3250	122	180	0.01	13.9	2566116	2566481	3250	0.5327868852459017	0.35	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3251	316	180	1.5	6.9	2566438	2567385	3251	0.439873417721519	0.5555555555555556	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_558	282	180	0.46	8.6	540158	541003	558	0.30141843971631205	0.45555555555555555	1
Cse2gr11_4_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_775	113	181	0.056	11.7	767442	767780	775	0.5929203539823009	0.36464088397790057	-1
Csm3gr7_10_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3334	106	228	0.026	12.3	2642189	2642506	3334	0.46226415094339623	0.17105263157894737	-1
Csm3gr7_5_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_5072	74	620	0.068	9.8	4309036	4309257	5072	0.43243243243243246	0.05	1
Csx19_10_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2925	317	121	0.45	9.0	2337173	2338123	2925	0.5110410094637224	0.4132231404958678	-1
Csx19_18_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2381	90	200	0.029	11.8	1975246	1975515	2381	0.5555555555555556	0.245	-1
Csx19_19_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2381	90	200	0.029	11.8	1975246	1975515	2381	0.5555555555555556	0.245	-1
Csx1_15_CAS-III	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_379	112	474	0.024	11.8	337314	337649	379	0.4642857142857143	0.10759493670886076	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1171	186	213	4.6e-20	70.5	1045724	1046281	1171	0.4946236559139785	0.38028169014084506	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1172	141	213	3.8e-23	80.5	1046275	1046697	1172	0.9361702127659575	0.539906103286385	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_133	130	213	2.9e-22	77.7	95598	95987	133	0.9	0.4694835680751174	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1391	1276	213	2.6e-53	179.1	1208966	1212793	1391	0.20141065830721003	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1495	77	213	9.5e-10	36.8	1286348	1286578	1495	0.8181818181818182	0.2676056338028169	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1556	789	213	2.2e-50	169.5	1341655	1344021	1556	0.3193916349809886	0.9765258215962441	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_162	218	213	3.3e-11	41.5	117523	118176	162	0.24311926605504589	0.22535211267605634	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_163	159	213	1.30E-14	104.9	118228	118704	163	0.9371069182389937	0.619718309591549	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1774	218	213	3.60E-28	149.2	1561185	1561838	1774	0.9678899082568807	0.8826291079812206	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1956	111	213	0.00061	17.8	1723603	1723935	1956	0.5585585585585585	0.18309859154929578	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1957	130	213	4.2e-06	24.9	1723950	1724339	1957	0.46923076923076923	0.2535211267605634	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1977	132	213	3.2e-17	61.2	1736687	1737082	1977	0.9393939393939394	0.5211267605633803	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1988	280	213	5.80E-16	106.1	1744414	1745253	1988	0.6392857142857142	0.6854460093896714	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1991	155	213	1.9e-10	39.0	1747257	1747721	1991	0.4774193548387097	0.29577464788732394	1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2044	94	213	0.008	14.1	1786525	1786806	2044	0.30851063829787234	0.107981220657277	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2125	84	213	8.8e-13	46.7	1834768	1835019	2125	0.8571428571428571	0.30985915492957744	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2126	200	213	3.50E-06	77.4	1835031	1835630	2126	0.715	0.5305164319248826	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_274	153	213	2.80E-06	77.7	230873	231331	274	0.7712418300653595	0.49295774647887325	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2863	127	213	1.5e-10	39.4	2278673	2279053	2863	0.5275590551181102	0.3286384976525822	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3220	293	213	0.015	13.3	2543457	2544335	3220	0.07849829351535836	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3249	271	213	1.9e-40	137.1	2565139	2565951	3249	0.8782287822878229	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3334	106	213	1.2e-09	36.5	2642189	2642506	3334	0.7830188679245284	0.4131455399061033	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3335	122	213	1.5e-05	23.1	2642531	2642896	3335	0.5163934426229508	0.4084507042253521	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3479	169	213	7.2e-15	53.5	2740279	2740785	3479	0.8461538461538461	0.863849765258216	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_367	251	213	1.80E-06	78.3	325687	326439	367	0.7091633466135459	0.6807511737089202	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_368	129	213	7.3e-06	24.1	328238	328624	368	0.6976744186046512	0.27699530516431925	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_373	152	213	7.6e-20	69.7	333045	333500	373	0.7697368421052632	0.4272300469483568	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4362	214	213	7.90E-23	128.5	3563892	3564533	4362	0.9719626168224299	0.8685446009389671	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4382	108	213	7.2e-12	43.7	3577400	3577723	4382	0.6759259259259259	0.30985915492957744	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4394	258	213	3.00E-16	58.0	3587615	3588388	4394	0.5038759689922481	0.5352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4550	137	213	2.9e-23	80.9	3773674	3774084	4550	0.9927007299270073	0.5586854460093896	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4556	143	213	5.2e-22	76.8	3779865	3780293	4556	0.7132867132867133	0.5305164319248826	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_463	565	213	1.00E-31	108.5	442741	444435	463	0.3168141592920354	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4669	158	213	1.2e-23	82.2	3881895	3882368	4669	0.9683544303797469	0.6431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4670	111	213	0.0074	14.2	3882444	3882776	4670	0.24324324324324326	0.1267605633802817	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4672	462	213	3.1e-35	120.0	3884417	3885802	4672	0.4199134199134199	0.7464788732394366	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4690	107	213	3.5e-06	25.1	3929152	3929472	4690	0.45794392523364486	0.215962441314554	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4765	127	213	9.80E-09	82.5	4000417	4000797	4765	0.9133858267716536	0.4694835680751174	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4802	1276	213	7.00E-53	177.7	4036182	4040009	4802	0.20141065830721003	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4871	151	213	3.5e-21	74.1	4094506	4094958	4871	0.8410596026490066	0.5117370892018779	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_488	174	213	1.1e-10	39.8	467668	468189	488	0.43103448275862066	0.323943661971831	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4980	169	213	2.4e-23	81.2	4222798	4223304	4980	0.9526627218934911	0.676056338028169	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_5056	93	213	0.0011	17.0	4294737	4295015	5056	0.6236559139784946	0.24413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_51	114	213	9.5e-05	20.4	36395	36736	51	0.43859649122807015	0.25821596244131456	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_525	280	213	1.8e-41	140.4	506181	507020	525	0.8785714285714286	0.971830985915493	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_535	262	213	7.00E-06	24.1	515188	515973	535	0.2633587786259542	0.43661971830985913	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_560	122	213	3.4e-05	21.9	542414	542779	560	0.27049180327868855	0.13145539906103287	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_561	327	213	5.9e-20	70.1	543085	544065	561	0.363914373088685	0.43661971830985913	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_565	155	213	9.00E-22	76.1	547739	548203	565	0.9419354838709677	0.6056338028169014	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_593	162	213	7.4e-31	105.7	576489	576974	593	0.9506172839506173	0.6431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_594	116	213	1.7e-11	42.5	577037	577384	594	0.45689655172413796	0.22535211267605634	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_610	102	213	8.8e-13	46.7	601770	602075	610	0.803921568627451	0.352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_665	221	213	4.9e-12	44.2	671664	672326	665	0.3891402714932127	0.3051643192488263	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1172	141	298	0.00044	17.5	1046275	1046697	1172	0.6382978723404256	0.26174496644295303	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_133	130	298	0.00035	17.9	95598	95987	133	0.6846153846153846	0.25838926174496646	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1391	1276	298	2.3e-11	41.5	1208966	1212793	1391	0.2249216300940439	0.8456375838926175	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1556	789	298	7.3e-13	46.4	1341655	1344021	1556	0.27122940430925224	0.6375838926174496	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_163	159	298	3.5e-08	31.0	118228	118704	163	0.5534591194968553	0.2751677852348993	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1774	218	298	5.5e-11	40.2	1561185	1561838	1774	0.5275229357798165	0.3691275167785235	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1957	130	298	0.033	11.4	1723950	1724339	1957	0.4	0.17785234899328858	1

RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_1988	280	298	6.9e-09	33.3	1744414	1745253	1988	0.5142857142857142	0.4228187919463087	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2126	200	298	0.0001	19.6	1835031	1835630	2126	0.465	0.27181208053691275	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_274	153	298	0.00092	16.5	230873	231331	274	0.738562091503268	0.35570469798657717	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2863	127	298	2.6e-08	31.4	2278673	2279053	2863	0.5748031496062992	0.2516778523489933	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3249	271	298	7.8e-10	36.4	2565139	2565951	3249	0.7527675276752768	0.6040268456375839	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3479	169	298	0.0094	13.2	2740279	2740785	3479	0.5266272189349113	0.2953020134228188	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_373	152	298	0.00056	17.2	333045	333500	373	0.6644736842105263	0.2953020134228188	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4362	214	298	4.1e-07	27.5	3563892	3564533	4362	0.7429906542056075	0.47651006711409394	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4382	108	298	0.0013	16.0	3577400	3577723	4382	0.6574074074074074	0.2181208053691275	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4550	137	298	5.6e-06	23.7	3773674	3774084	4550	0.6423357664233577	0.2751677852348993	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_463	565	298	7.4e-08	29.9	442741	444435	463	0.2920353982300885	0.4966442953020134	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4669	158	298	0.00013	19.3	3881895	3882368	4669	0.9113924050632911	0.4261744966442953	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4672	462	298	1.9e-08	31.9	3884417	3885802	4672	0.3398268398268398	0.4697986577181208	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4690	107	298	0.0023	15.2	3929152	3929472	4690	0.514018691588785	0.174496644295302	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4765	127	298	4.00E-07	27.5	4000417	4000797	4765	0.7007874015748031	0.2785234899328859	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4802	1276	298	3.5e-11	40.8	4036182	4040009	4802	0.2249216300904039	0.8456375838926175	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4871	151	298	0.00037	17.8	4094506	4094958	4871	0.6423841059602649	0.3053691275167785	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_4980	169	298	3.8e-05	21.0	4222798	4223304	4980	0.9171597633136095	0.46308724832214765	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_561	327	298	0.015	12.5	543085	544065	561	0.2599388379204893	0.24496644295302014	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_565	155	298	0.00051	17.3	547739	548203	565	0.8838709677419355	0.39932885906040266	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_593	162	298	2.00E-08	31.8	576489	576974	593	0.8888888888888888	0.4228187919463087	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_610	102	298	1.1e-06	26.1	601770	602075	610	0.7843137254901961	0.2483221476510067	1
RecD_0_IVD	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_2380	116	763	0.00066	16.2	1974823	1975170	2380	0.27586206896551724	0.04062909567496723	-1
SSgr11_0_CAS-III-F	chr6_GL000253v2_alt_3110	92	197	0.038	12.0	2453714	2453989	3110	0.3804347826086957	0.18274111675126903	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csx1_15_CAS-III	chr1_K1270708v1_random_35	417	474	2.8e-05	16.3	77753	79003	35	0.36211031175059955	0.09071729957805907	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270708v1_random_70	90	213	2.4e-08	27.0	89713	89982	70	0.8777777777777778	0.3286384976525822	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270709v1_random_54	187	213	1.3e-34	112.9	47583	48143	54	0.9625668449197861	0.7370892018779343	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270710v1_random_4	183	213	9.6e-07	21.8	19709	20257	4	0.3224043715846995	0.20187793427230047	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_K1270709v1_random_54	187	298	3.3e-12	39.1	47583	48143	54	0.8128342245989305	0.44966442953020136	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_4826	98	284	3.6e-05	21.8	4129197	4129490	4826	0.29591836734693877	0.1056338028169014	-1
Cas1_0_I-II-III-V	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_385	101	315	0.43	7.7	442275	442577	385	0.3564356435643564	0.11428571428571428	1
Cas1_0_IE	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2446	169	269	1.5	6.3	2400387	2400893	2446	0.40828402366863903	0.17472118959107807	-1
Cas2_8_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_4963	71	101	0.0077	14.5	4251616	4251828	4963	0.676056338028169	0.48514851485148514	-1
Cas3_0_CAS-I	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_452	194	353	0.058	10.8	596002	596583	452	0.42783505154639173	0.23229461756373937	-1
Cas3_0_I	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_452	194	358	0.034	11.5	596002	596583	452	0.25257731958762886	0.13687150837988826	-1
Cas4_0_IA	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2419	191	273	0.084	10.8	2384252	2384824	2419	0.08900523560209424	0.06227106227106227	-1
Cas8b2_0_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2198	62	389	0.036	11.8	2252320	2252505	2198	0.6451612903225806	0.10796915167095116	1
Cas8f_3_CAS-I-F	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_5530	79	376	0.0034	15.0	4775856	4776092	5530	0.569620253164557	0.12234042553191489	1
Cas8f_4_CAS-I-F	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1237	73	450	0.019	11.7	1351870	1352088	1237	0.7671232876712328	0.12222222222222222	1
Cas8f_7_CAS-I-F	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_5530	79	376	0.02	12.3	4775856	4776092	5530	0.5443037974683544	0.11702127659574468	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2780	122	180	0.0076	14.4	2599797	2600162	2780	0.5327868852459017	0.35	-1
Cse2gr11_4_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_572	109	181	0.052	11.8	767692	768018	572	0.6146788990825688	0.36464088397790057	-1

Csf1_0_IV	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_3823	153	227	0.045	11.6	3292752	3293210	3823	0.477124183006536	0.29515418502202645	-1
Csm3gr7_10_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2862	106	228	0.026	12.3	2675744	2676061	2862	0.46226415094339623	0.17105263157894737	-1
Csm4_0_IIIA	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1820	60	302	0.022	12.4	1940139	1940318	1820	0.5166666666666667	0.10264900662251655	-1
Csm4gr5_0_CAS-III-A	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1820	60	301	0.017	12.8	1940139	1940318	1820	0.5166666666666667	0.10299003322259136	-1
Csx19_10_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2402	317	121	0.45	9.0	2370797	2371747	2402	0.5110410094637224	0.4132231404958678	-1
Csx19_3_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_3960	172	160	0.023	12.7	3380365	3380880	3960	0.18023255813953487	0.21875	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1322	819	213	4.8e-51	171.7	1424995	1427451	1322	0.3076923076923077	0.9765258215962441	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1539	116	213	0.00066	17.7	1757388	1757735	1539	0.5344827586206896	0.18309859154929578	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1540	145	213	1.5e-05	23.1	1757750	1758184	1540	0.41379310344827586	0.24882629107981222	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1572	280	213	5.90E-15	106.1	1778213	1779052	1572	0.7178571428571429	0.7887323943661971	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1576	156	213	2.00E-10	39.0	1781048	1781515	1576	0.47435897435897434	0.29577464788732394	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_166	218	213	3.8e-11	41.3	117562	118215	166	0.3440366972477064	0.3286384976525822	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_167	159	213	1.30E-14	104.9	118267	118743	167	0.9371069182389937	0.6197183098591549	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1684	201	213	3.20E-06	77.6	1868849	1869451	1684	0.7164179104477612	0.5352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2317	127	213	1.5e-10	39.4	2312583	2312963	2317	0.5275590551181102	0.3286384976525822	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2754	293	213	0.015	13.3	2577142	2578020	2754	0.07849829351535836	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2779	269	213	8.9e-40	134.9	2598821	2599627	2779	0.8773234200743495	0.9248826291079812	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2862	106	213	1.1e-09	36.6	2675744	2676061	2862	0.7830188679245284	0.4131455399061033	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2863	83	213	2.7e-06	25.5	2676086	2676334	2863	0.7831325301204819	0.41784037558685444	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_323	251	213	1.3e-21	75.5	325872	326624	323	0.7091633466135459	0.6807511737089202	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_386	565	213	4.4e-32	109.7	442907	444601	386	0.3168141592920354	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_399	101	213	1.8e-09	35.9	458231	458533	399	0.8811881188118812	0.3568075117370892	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_440	162	213	7.5e-31	105.7	576710	577195	440	0.9506172839506173	0.6431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_441	116	213	1.7e-11	42.5	577258	577605	441	0.45689655172413796	0.22535211267605634	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_4541	137	213	3.00E-23	80.9	3810305	3810715	4541	0.9927007299270073	0.5586854460093896	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_4548	143	213	5.2e-22	76.8	3816496	3816924	4548	0.7132867132867133	0.5305164319248826	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_4796	169	213	2.5e-23	81.2	4102537	4103043	4796	0.9526627218934911	0.676056338028169	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_49	114	213	9.6e-05	20.4	36415	36756	49	0.43859649122807015	0.25821596244131456	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_5066	87	213	1.3e-05	23.2	4351262	4351522	5066	0.42528735632183906	0.17370892018779344	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_972	186	213	4.6e-20	70.5	1045799	1046356	972	0.4946236559139785	0.38028169014084506	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_973	141	213	3.8e-23	80.5	1046350	1046772	973	0.9361702127659575	0.539906103286385	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1322	819	298	1.7e-13	48.5	1424995	1427451	1322	0.2612942612942613	0.6375838926174496	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1572	280	298	7.00E-09	33.3	1778213	1779052	1572	0.5142857142857142	0.4228187919463087	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_167	159	298	3.5e-08	31.0	118267	118743	167	0.5534591194968553	0.2751677852348993	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1684	201	298	0.00011	19.6	1868849	1869451	1684	0.4626865671641791	0.27181208053691275	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2317	127	298	2.6e-08	31.4	2312583	2312963	2317	0.5748031496062992	0.2516778523489933	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2779	269	298	9.6e-10	36.1	2598821	2599627	2779	0.6171003717472119	0.4899328859060403	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_386	565	298	3.8e-08	30.9	442907	444601	386	0.2938053097345133	0.5	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_440	162	298	2.00E-08	31.8	576710	577195	440	0.8888888888888888	0.4228187919463087	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_4541	137	298	5.7e-06	23.7	3810305	3810715	4541	0.6423357664233577	0.2751677852348993	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_4796	169	298	3.8e-05	21.0	4102537	4103043	4796	0.9171597633136095	0.46308724832214765	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_973	141	298	0.00044	17.5	1046350	1046772	973	0.6382978723404256	0.26174496644295303	1
RecD_0_IVD	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_1952	116	763	0.00067	16.2	2008648	2008995	1952	0.27586206896551724	0.04062909567496723	-1
SSgr11_0_CAS-III-F	chr6_GL000254v2_alt_2586	93	197	0.039	12.0	2487327	2487605	2586	0.3763440860215054	0.18274111675126903	-1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas1_0_CAS-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2118	58	266	0.018	12.7	2108984	2109157	2118	0.46551724137931033	0.10150375939849623	-1
Cas5_0_I	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_162	58	43	0.0025	15.6	128058	128231	162	0.41379310344827586	0.5348837209302325	-1
Cas8a1_0_IB	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1807	73	308	0.009	13.5	1866952	1867170	1807	0.5068493150684932	0.11363636363636363	-1
Cas8b2_1_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1807	73	334	0.027	11.8	1866952	1867170	1807	0.5068493150684932	0.10479041916167664	-1
Cas8b2_4_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_3179	65	65	0.0049	15.2	3068521	3068715	3179	0.676923076923077	0.6615384615384615	1
Cas8b2_8_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_3179	65	70	0.00013	20.3	3068521	3068715	3179	0.676923076923077	0.7	1
Cmr1_0_IIC	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_4536	48	348	0.068	10.5	4452741	4452884	4536	0.6041666666666666	0.08333333333333333	-1
Cmr1gr7_7_CAS-III-B-III-C	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_4536	48	346	0.038	11.5	4452741	4452884	4536	0.6041666666666666	0.0838150289017341	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2604	316	180	0.69	7.8	2512831	2513778	2604	0.439873417721519	0.5555555555555556	-1
Cse2gr11_4_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_657	113	181	0.048	11.7	767783	768121	657	0.5929203539823009	0.36464088397790057	-1
Csf1_0_IV	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_3369	153	227	0.038	11.6	3206691	3207149	3369	0.477124183006536	0.29515418502202645	-1
Csm3gr7_5_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_4147	74	620	0.058	9.8	4083970	4084191	4147	0.43243243243243246	0.05	1
Csx19_10_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2308	317	121	0.38	9.0	2282294	2283244	2308	0.5110410094637224	0.4132231404958678	-1
Csx19_20_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_4251	57	147	0.046	11.4	4181231	4181401	4251	0.7368421052631579	0.2857142857142857	1
Csx19_3_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_3429	167	160	0.018	12.9	3261563	3262063	3429	0.19161676664706588	0.21875	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1222	573	213	1.00E-09	36.5	1336057	1337775	1222	0.1431064572425829	0.3051643192488263	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1223	257	213	9.00E-21	121.6	1337742	1338512	1223	0.6070038910505836	0.647887323943662	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1418	218	213	3.60E-28	149.0	1506043	1506696	1418	0.981651376146789	0.8967136150234741	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1601	280	213	5.00E-31	106.1	1689260	1690099	1601	0.7178571428571429	0.7887323943661971	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2249	127	213	1.2e-10	39.4	2223595	2223975	2249	0.5275590551181102	0.3286384976525822	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2578	257	213	0.011	13.4	2489851	2490621	2578	0.08949416342412451	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2603	271	213	3.1e-41	139.4	2511532	2512344	2603	0.8782287822878229	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_3660	218	213	6.4e-39	131.9	3482245	3482898	3660	0.9724770642201835	0.8873239436619719	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_3847	139	213	2.3e-20	71.3	3698737	3699153	3847	0.7050359712230215	0.5117370892018779	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_391	152	213	6.5e-20	69.7	333068	333523	391	0.7697368421052632	0.4272300469483568	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_4135	94	213	0.00092	17.0	4069669	4069950	4135	0.6170212765957447	0.24413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_4172	69	213	5.6e-07	27.5	4112684	4112890	4172	0.7971014492753623	0.23943661971830985	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_437	96	213	3.00E-07	28.4	386753	387040	437	0.6458333333333334	0.26291079812206575	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_494	565	213	8.90E-17	108.5	442764	444458	494	0.3168141592920354	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_505	130	213	1.1e-09	36.3	458014	458403	505	0.7923076923076923	0.431924882629108	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_516	136	213	0.0069	14.1	467691	468098	516	0.22794117647058823	0.14553990610328638	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_555	269	213	1.5e-36	124.1	506205	507011	555	0.8847583643122676	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_565	231	213	4.9e-06	24.4	515212	515904	565	0.2987012987012987	0.43661971830985913	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1223	257	298	3.1e-11	40.8	1337742	1338512	1223	0.5914396887159533	0.47315436241610737	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1418	218	298	3.9e-11	40.5	1506043	1506696	1418	0.6422018348623854	0.42953020134228187	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_1601	280	298	5.9e-09	33.3	1689260	1690099	1601	0.5142857142857142	0.4228187919463087	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2249	127	298	2.2e-08	31.4	2223595	2223975	2249	0.5748031496062992	0.2516778523489933	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2603	271	298	5.6e-10	36.7	2511532	2512344	2603	0.7527675276752768	0.6040268456375839	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_3660	218	298	3.4e-07	27.5	3482245	3482898	3660	0.7293577981651376	0.47651006711409394	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_391	152	298	0.00048	17.2	333068	333523	391	0.6644736842105263	0.2953020134228188	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_4172	69	298	0.033	11.2	4112684	4112890	4172	0.3188405797101449	0.0738255033557047	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_494	565	298	6.3e-08	29.9	442764	444458	494	0.2920353982300885	0.4966442953020134	-1
SSgr11_0_CAS-III-F	chr6_GL000255v2_alt_2464	92	197	0.032	12.0	2401214	2401489	2464	0.3804347826086957	0.18274111675126903	-1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_5192	94	284	0.00036	18.6	4229371	4229652	5192	0.2553191489361702	0.0880281690140845	-1
Cas1_0_I-II-III-V	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_581	103	315	2.0	5.6	485912	486220	581	0.34951456310679613	0.11428571428571428	1
Cas3_0_CAS-I	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_726	194	353	0.063	10.8	639617	640198	726	0.42783505154639173	0.23229461756373937	-1
Cas3_0_I	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_726	194	358	0.035	11.6	639617	640198	726	0.25257731958762886	0.13687150837988826	-1
Cas5_0_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_65	122	182	0.32	9.2	50771	51136	65	0.4098360655737705	0.27472527472527475	-1
Cas5_1_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_65	122	180	0.44	8.7	50771	51136	65	0.36885245901639346	0.24444444444444444	-1
Cas8b2_4_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_759	85	65	1.2	7.9	682324	682578	759	0.3764705882352941	0.2923076923076923	-1
Cas8b5_0_CAS-I-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4853	163	825	0.22	7.8	3907876	3908364	4853	0.5214723926380368	0.10909090909090909	1
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_761	78	255	8.0	4.3	685384	685617	761	0.7948717948717948	0.24313725490196078	-1
CasR_3_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_5859	93	384	0.027	11.8	4872138	4872416	5859	0.5053763440860215	0.11458333333333333	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4853	163	180	6.3	5.0	3907876	3908364	4853	0.6871165644171779	0.37777777777777777	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_683	280	180	1.0	7.6	583991	584830	683	0.30357142857142855	0.45555555555555555	1
Cmr5gr11_5_CAS-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_962	64	156	0.031	12.8	857354	857545	962	0.578125	0.23076923076923078	-1
Cse2gr11_4_CAS-I-E	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_884	109	181	0.055	11.8	811328	811654	884	0.6146788990825688	0.36464088397790057	-1
Csf1_0_IV	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_3994	153	227	0.047	11.6	3251905	3252363	3994	0.477124183006536	0.29515418502202645	-1
Csf3_0_IV	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_3787	93	222	0.013	13.6	3066828	3067106	3787	0.3763440860215054	0.14864864864864866	-1
Csm3gr7_10_CAS-III-A-III-D	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_3040	91	228	0.0076	14.2	2635864	2636136	3040	0.5934065934065934	0.25	-1
Csx19_10_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2646	317	121	0.48	9.0	2327391	2328341	2646	0.5110410094637224	0.4132231404958678	-1
Csx19_18_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2409	90	200	0.031	11.8	1965776	1966045	2409	0.5555555555555556	0.245	-1
Csx19_19_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2409	90	200	0.031	11.8	1965776	1966045	2409	0.5555555555555556	0.245	-1
Csx19_3_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4103	173	160	0.028	12.5	3306783	3307301	4103	0.1791907514450867	0.21875	-1
Csx19_3_CAS-III-D	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4171	172	160	0.025	12.7	3339518	3340033	4171	0.18023255813953487	0.21875	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_103	114	213	0.0001	20.4	80186	80527	103	0.43859649122807015	0.25821596244131456	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_1565	819	213	2.6e-50	169.4	1379824	1382280	1565	0.3076923076923077	0.9765258215962441	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2000	116	213	0.0011	17.0	1711796	1712143	2000	0.5172413793103449	0.18309859154929578	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2001	133	213	3.7e-05	21.9	1712194	1712592	2001	0.42857142857142855	0.2347417840375587	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2160	201	213	3.3e-22	77.6	1825565	1826167	2160	0.7164179104477612	0.5352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_222	159	213	1.40E-14	104.9	161918	162394	222	0.9371069182389937	0.6197183098591549	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2911	257	213	0.014	13.4	2536348	2537118	2911	0.08949416342412451	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_3040	91	213	2.3e-08	32.4	2635864	2636136	3040	0.9230769230769231	0.41784037558685444	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_382	158	213	3.3e-22	77.6	274684	275157	382	0.7468354430379747	0.49295774647887325	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4469	214	213	8.5e-38	128.5	3575161	3575802	4469	0.9719626168224299	0.8685446009389671	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4511	200	213	1.7e-06	26.2	3599069	3599668	4511	0.33	0.24882629107981222	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4707	143	213	5.5e-22	76.8	3790895	3791323	4707	0.7132867132867133	0.5305164319248826	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4833	148	213	7.2e-21	73.2	3892596	3893039	4833	0.9527027027027027	0.5868544600938967	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4836	463	213	7.9e-36	122.1	3895115	3896503	4836	0.42116630669546434	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_484	135	213	1.00E-10	40.0	376849	377253	484	0.7407407407407407	0.3474178403755869	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_5162	104	213	2.6e-10	38.7	4203797	4204108	5162	0.9134615384615384	0.4131455399061033	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_524	96	213	3.7e-07	28.4	430532	430819	524	0.6458333333333334	0.26291079812206575	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_5493	89	213	4.6e-05	21.6	4501212	4501478	5493	0.4157303370786517	0.17370892018779344	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_582	565	213	1.1e-31	108.5	486550	488244	582	0.3168141592920354	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_594	130	213	1.4e-09	36.3	501800	502189	594	0.7923076923076923	0.431924882629108	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_641	280	213	1.9e-41	140.4	550008	550847	641	0.8785714285714286	0.971830985915493	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_656	262	213	7.5e-06	24.1	559015	559800	656	0.2633587786259542	0.43661971830985913	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_687	327	213	6.3e-20	70.1	586912	587892	687	0.363914373088685	0.43661971830985913	1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_691	155	213	9.6e-22	76.1	591566	592030	691	0.9419354838709677	0.6056338028169014	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_1565	819	298	8.1e-13	46.3	1379824	1382280	1565	0.2612942612942613	0.6375838926174496	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2160	201	298	0.00011	19.6	1825565	1826167	2160	0.4626865671641791	0.27181208053691275	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_222	159	298	3.7e-08	31.0	161918	162394	222	0.5534591194968553	0.27516777852348993	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_382	158	298	0.0011	16.4	274684	275157	382	0.7151898734177216	0.35570469798657717	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4469	214	298	4.4e-07	27.5	3575161	3575802	4469	0.7429906542056075	0.47651006711409394	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4833	148	298	0.00075	16.9	3892596	3893039	4833	0.8986486486486487	0.38926174496644295	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_4836	463	298	6.3e-09	33.5	3895115	3896503	4836	0.3390928725701944	0.4697986577181208	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_5162	104	298	0.016	12.5	4203797	4204108	5162	0.8461538461538461	0.2785234899328859	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_582	565	298	7.9e-08	29.9	486550	488244	582	0.2920353982300885	0.4966442953020134	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_687	327	298	0.016	12.5	586912	587892	687	0.2599388379204893	0.24496644295302014	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_691	155	298	0.00054	17.3	591566	592030	691	0.8838709677419355	0.39932885906040266	1
RecD_0_IVD	chr6_GL000256v2_alt_2408	116	763	0.00071	16.2	1965353	1965700	2408	0.27586206896551724	0.04062909567496723	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr19_GL949752v1_alt_1357	515	284	0.0017	14.4	884938	886482	1357	0.040776699029126215	0.07394366197183098	1
Cmr5_1_IIIC	chr19_GL949752v1_alt_633	127	178	0.0017	14.4	373443	373823	633	0.33070866141732286	0.2303370786516854	-1
Cmr5_1_IIIC	chr19_GL949752v1_alt_96	100	178	0.0017	14.4	54765	55064	96	0.46	0.25842696629213485	1
PrimPol_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL949752v1_alt_154	84	361	0.0017	14.4	88422	88673	154	0.7857142857142857	0.18282548476454294	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_GL949752v1_alt_1167	555	213	0.0017	14.4	767982	769646	1167	0.35135135135135137	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_GL949752v1_alt_1167	555	298	0.0017	14.4	767982	769646	1167	0.2810810810810811	0.4664429530201342	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr19_GL949753v2_alt_695	515	284	0.00093	14.4	694349	695893	695	0.040776699029126215	0.07394366197183098	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
AbiEii_0_CAS-III	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_1626	494	284	0.002	14.5	964733	966214	1626	0.04251012145748988	0.07394366197183098	1
Cas9_1_IIB	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_1490	109	827	0.002	14.5	896441	896767	1490	0.3394495412844037	0.04353083434099154	-1
Csn2_10_CAS-II-A	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_971	239	321	0.002	14.5	564398	565114	971	0.301255230125523	0.23052959501557632	-1
PrimPol_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_167	84	361	0.002	14.5	88422	88673	167	0.7857142857142857	0.18282548476454294	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_1404	557	213	0.002	14.5	846176	847846	1404	0.3500897666068223	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_1417	90	213	0.002	14.5	858835	859104	1417	0.7555555555555555	0.2863849765258216	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_971	239	213	0.002	14.5	564398	565114	971	0.5564853556485355	0.539906103286385	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_1404	557	298	0.002	14.5	846176	847846	1404	0.2800718132854578	0.4664429530201342	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_971	239	298	0.002	14.5	564398	565114	971	0.4686192468619247	0.35906040268456374	-1
SSgr11_1_CAS-III-F	chr19_KI270938v1_alt_37	76	97	0.002	14.5	22956	23183	37	0.47368421052631576	0.3711340206185567	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csm2gr11_1_CAS-III-A	chrUn_KI270411v1_5	65	192	0.0012	12.6	1729	1923	5	0.7230769230769231	0.24479166666666666	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr7_0_IIIB	chrUn_KI270442v1_797	98	191	0.036	9.5	336339	336632	797	0.6122448979591837	0.2356020942408377	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_566	531	213	1.7e-50	167.3	116857	118449	566	0.4896421845574388	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_597	213	213	2.8e-12	42.4	131809	132447	597	0.4413145539906103	0.3192488262910798	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_633	99	213	0.00021	16.7	151994	152290	633	0.2222222222222222	0.10328638497652583	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_634	238	213	1.5e-33	111.9	152348	153061	634	0.8109243697478992	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_689	211	213	3.00E-21	71.7	189819	190451	689	0.5450236966824644	0.48826291079812206	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_695	326	213	1.6e-45	151.0	195709	196686	695	0.6748466257668712	0.9014084507042254	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_759	118	213	2.3e-07	26.4	257889	258242	759	0.5508474576271186	0.27230046948356806	1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_775	141	213	4.60E-07	74.4	305931	306353	775	0.9290780141843972	0.5352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270442v1_816	288	213	4.1e-45	149.7	345727	346590	816	0.6736111111111112	0.784037558685446	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270442v1_566	531	298	1.00E-11	40.0	116857	118449	566	0.3935969868173258	0.6208053691275168	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270442v1_634	238	298	1.6e-10	36.1	152348	153061	634	0.6638655462184874	0.47315436241610737	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270442v1_689	211	298	1.8e-05	19.5	189819	190451	689	0.5213270142180095	0.348993288590604	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270442v1_695	326	298	1.5e-08	29.6	195709	196686	695	0.48466257668711654	0.4899328859060403	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270442v1_759	118	298	0.0046	11.5	257889	258242	759	0.3983050847457627	0.15771812080536912	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270442v1_775	141	298	0.00047	14.8	305931	306353	775	0.5815602836879432	0.2348993288590604	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270442v1_816	288	298	2.2e-13	45.4	345727	346590	816	0.5486111111111112	0.49328859060402686	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chrUn_KI270435v1_12	165	180	0.0079	10.9	14859	15353	12	0.7757575757575758	0.5833333333333334	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270435v1_11	153	213	2.70E-12	93.9	14103	14561	11	0.954248366013072	0.6244131455399061	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270435v1_23	387	213	6.6e-45	148.2	31431	32591	23	0.5607235142118863	0.8873239436619719	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270435v1_5	197	213	7.3e-23	76.2	4685	5275	5	0.6091370558375635	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270435v1_6	144	213	3.6e-13	44.5	5495	5926	6	0.3263888888888889	0.22065727699530516	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270512v1_7	325	213	6.9e-46	151.4	11213	12187	7	0.6984615384615385	0.9342723004694836	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270435v1_11	153	298	2.8e-06	21.3	14103	14561	11	0.6470588235294118	0.31543624161073824	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270435v1_23	387	298	2.8e-11	37.7	31431	32591	23	0.46770025839793283	0.5302013422818792	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270435v1_5	197	298	2.3e-06	21.6	4685	5275	5	0.43147208121827413	0.24496644295302014	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270512v1_7	325	298	2.6e-13	44.4	11213	12187	7	0.48923076923076925	0.4966442953020134	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas10_1_CAS-III	chrUn_KI270538v1_17	79	654	0.33	4.1	19928	20164	17	0.4936708860759494	0.05504587155963303	1
Cmr7_0_III-B	chrUn_KI270517v1_2	137	191	0.0046	11.5	2843	3253	2	0.45255474452554745	0.17277486910994763	1
Cmr7_0_III-B	chrUn_KI270519v1_113	109	191	0.0015	13.0	87131	87457	113	0.5596330275229358	0.27225130890052357	-1
Cmr7_0_III-B	chrUn_KI270579v1_25	72	191	0.00039	15.0	13780	13995	25	0.6666666666666666	0.2774869109947644	1
DEDDh_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270538v1_23	83	160	0.0056	11.6	24356	24604	23	0.7349397590361446	0.3	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270519v1_169	186	213	3.3e-19	64.1	122384	122941	169	0.44623655913978494	0.3755868544600939	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270519v1_65	270	213	5.6e-12	40.5	46516	47325	65	0.37407407407407406	0.352112676056338	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270519v1_98	433	213	3.4e-51	168.6	76219	77517	98	0.5935334872979214	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270538v1_84	186	213	3.1e-21	70.7	69164	69721	84	0.5053763440860215	0.38967136150234744	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270538v1_85	85	213	1.2e-07	26.3	69891	70145	85	0.9058823529411765	0.3145539906103286	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270580v1_1	97	213	7.00E-19	63.0	289	579	1	0.9175257731958762	0.38497652582159625	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270581v1_2	182	213	3.6e-18	60.7	5507	6052	2	0.6703296703296703	0.5258215962441315	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270581v1_3	346	213	4.5e-05	17.9	6003	7040	3	0.1994219653179191	0.24413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270519v1_98	433	298	6.5e-14	46.2	76219	77517	98	0.628175519630485	0.7919463087248322	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270580v1_1	97	298	1.5e-09	31.8	289	579	1	0.8969072164948454	0.27181208053691275	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270581v1_2	182	298	0.0016	12.1	5507	6052	2	0.3021978021978022	0.18456375838926176	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000195v1_10	64	213	1.5e-07	20.9	145823	146014	10	0.765625	0.2112676056338028	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000195v1_7	317	213	1.5e-07	20.9	60494	61444	7	0.7287066246056783	0.9389671361502347	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_GL000195v1_7	317	298	1.5e-07	20.9	60494	61444	7	0.6719242902208202	0.6375838926174496	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000219v1_20	114	213	2.2e-20	66.0	5476	5817	20	0.9210526315789473	0.431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000219v1_26	127	213	2.2e-20	66.0	19496	19876	26	0.8661417322834646	0.460093896713615	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000219v1_34	366	213	2.2e-20	66.0	36970	38067	34	0.3825136612021858	0.5727699530516432	1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000219v1_43	184	213	2.2e-20	66.0	59561	60112	43	0.875	0.6713615023474179	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000219v1_48	185	213	2.2e-20	66.0	67245	67799	48	0.9297297297297298	0.7089201877934272	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000219v1_54	566	213	2.2e-20	66.0	112584	114281	54	0.4540636042402827	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_GL000219v1_20	114	298	2.2e-20	66.0	5476	5817	20	0.8157894736842105	0.29194630872483224	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_GL000219v1_26	127	298	2.2e-20	66.0	19496	19876	26	0.8110236220472441	0.3288590604026846	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_GL000219v1_34	366	298	2.2e-20	66.0	36970	38067	34	0.29508196721311475	0.34563758389261745	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_GL000219v1_48	185	298	2.2e-20	66.0	67245	67799	48	0.5513513513513514	0.3288590604026846	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_GL000219v1_54	566	298	2.2e-20	66.0	112584	114281	54	0.37809187279151946	0.6375838926174496	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000224v1_40	282	213	3.2e-36	118.9	112493	113338	40	0.7340425531914894	0.7887323943661971	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_GL000224v1_40	282	298	3.2e-36	118.9	112493	113338	40	0.5567375886524822	0.4697986577181208	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270741v1_1	282	213	2.9e-36	118.9	54364	55209	1	0.7340425531914894	0.7887323943661971	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270741v1_230	127	213	2.9e-36	118.9	138405	138785	230	0.8661417322834646	0.460093896713615	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270741v1_232	366	213	2.9e-36	118.9	155879	156976	232	0.3825136612021858	0.5727699530516432	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270741v1_1	282	298	2.9e-36	118.9	54364	55209	1	0.5567375886524822	0.4697986577181208	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270741v1_230	127	298	2.9e-36	118.9	138405	138785	230	0.8110236220472441	0.3288590604026846	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270741v1_232	366	298	2.9e-36	118.9	155879	156976	232	0.29508196721311475	0.34563758389261745	1
SSgr11_0_CAS-III-F	chrUn_KI270741v1_228	115	197	2.9e-36	118.9	126296	126640	228	0.40869565217391307	0.23857868020304568	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
PrimPol_1_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_GL000213v1_56	342	130	1.6e-05	17.5	82367	83392	56	0.32456140350877194	0.6153846153846154	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CasR_1_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270743v1_7	59	218	0.00048	11.7	25753	25929	7	0.6101694915254238	0.1651376146788991	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270743v1_14	133	213	0.00048	11.7	57754	58152	14	0.9398496240601504	0.4647887323943662	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270743v1_19	268	213	0.00048	11.7	77397	78200	19	0.3656716417910448	0.3427230046948357	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270743v1_20	201	213	0.00048	11.7	78234	78836	20	0.7064676616915423	0.5821596244131455	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270743v1_5	251	213	0.00048	11.7	12930	13682	5	0.7051792828685259	0.676056338028169	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270743v1_83	370	213	0.00048	11.7	197356	198465	83	0.5216216216216216	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270743v1_20	201	298	0.00048	11.7	78234	78836	20	0.5572139303482587	0.35906040268456374	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270743v1_5	251	298	0.00048	11.7	12930	13682	5	0.5537848605577689	0.40604026845637586	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270743v1_83	370	298	0.00048	11.7	197356	198465	83	0.4243243243243243	0.4697986577181208	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_8_CAS-III-B	chrUn_KI270750v1_190	71	149	0.0041	11.5	124083	124295	190	0.5352112676056338	0.2550335570469799	-1
CorA_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chrUn_KI270749v1_40	59	551	0.0026	11.2	26239	26415	40	0.5423728813559322	0.056261343012704176	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270749v1_123	89	213	7.3e-08	27.0	95116	95382	123	0.6404494382022472	0.2676056338028169	1
tm_4_0_CAS-VI-B	chrUn_KI270750v1_130	113	225	7.7	1.2	89985	90323	130	0.6460176991150443	0.2577777777777778	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_KI270751v1_9	294	213	2.1e-34	111.3	128030	128911	9	0.608843537414966	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_KI270751v1_9	294	298	2.1e-34	111.3	128030	128911	9	0.4897959183673469	0.4228187919463087	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8a1_1_IA	chrUn_KI270756v1_272	70	316	0.00097	12.8	47551	47760	272	0.8	0.18354430379746836	-1
Cas8b3_0_CAS-I-B	chrUn_KI270756v1_272	70	316	0.00097	12.8	47551	47760	272	0.8	0.18354430379746836	-1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8f_1_CAS-I-F	chrUn_K1270742v1_49	93	458	1.1e-05	16.9	119478	119756	49	0.5161290322580645	0.10480349344978165	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_K1270742v1_43	509	213	2.1e-34	111.1	99030	100556	43	0.3516699410609037	0.6854460093896714	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_K1270742v1_51	107	213	4.9e-13	41.3	119923	120243	51	0.8878504672897196	0.323943661971831	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_K1270742v1_64	218	213	2.00E-14	45.9	164444	165097	64	0.5412844036697247	0.431924882629108	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chrUn_K1270742v1_65	65	213	2.00E-09	29.5	165131	165325	65	0.9846153846153847	0.2676056338028169	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_K1270742v1_43	509	298	1.3e-07	22.9	99030	100556	43	0.3654223968565815	0.5637583892617449	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chrUn_K1270742v1_65	65	298	0.00013	13.0	165131	165325	65	0.6153846153846154	0.1342281879194631	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas1_0_IE	chrUn_GL000216v2_136	73	269	0.14	6.3	23415	23633	136	0.5342465753424658	0.08178438661710037	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr22_K1270732v1_random_9	186	255	1.2	1.4	21683	22240	9	0.6021505376344086	0.23529411764705882	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr22_K1270732v1_random_4	447	213	5.4e-34	110.5	5545	6885	4	0.4228187919463087	0.7323943661971831	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr22_K1270732v1_random_4	447	298	1.2e-11	36.9	5545	6885	4	0.3400447427293065	0.44966442953020136	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5_2_CAS-I-B	chr22_K1270739v1_random_16	71	194	0.0039	12.3	6959	7171	16	0.2535211267605634	0.09278350515463918	-1
Cas8b2_5_CAS-I-B	chr22_K1270739v1_random_105	72	496	4.7e-05	17.2	42848	43063	105	0.875	0.12298387096774194	1
Cas8b2_5_CAS-I-B	chr22_K1270739v1_random_69	73	496	0.0027	11.4	27259	27477	69	0.8493150684931506	0.12096774193548387	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr22_K1270738v1_random_361	96	180	0.0035	12.3	90147	90434	361	0.8958333333333334	0.3277777777777778	1
Cmr7_0_IIIB	chr22_K1270739v1_random_37	57	191	0.004	12.0	15715	15885	37	0.5789473684210527	0.17277486910994763	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr22_K1270738v1_random_10	59	213	8.4e-05	17.3	16792	16968	10	0.576271186440678	0.16901408450704225	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr22_K1270739v1_random_99	369	213	2.9e-53	175.7	39747	40853	99	0.6937669376693767	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr22_K1270739v1_random_99	369	298	6.1e-14	46.7	39747	40853	99	0.5853658536585366	0.6476510067114094	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_GL000221v1_random_12	124	213	2.00E-07	21.6	68611	68982	12	0.2661290322580645	0.13145539906103287	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_GL000221v1_random_13	664	213	4.2e-28	89.2	69160	71151	13	0.24096385542168675	0.596244131455399	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_GL000221v1_random_24	276	213	6.4e-30	95.2	134354	135181	24	0.6702898550724637	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_GL000221v1_random_13	664	298	5.8e-06	16.2	69160	71151	13	0.22289156626506024	0.4228187919463087	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_GL000221v1_random_24	276	298	6.4e-08	22.6	134354	135181	24	0.33695652173913043	0.27181208053691275	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000008v2_random_32	294	213	7.5e-36	116.5	28220	29101	32	0.6054421768707483	0.6807511737089202	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000008v2_random_45	133	213	7.5e-36	116.5	72893	73291	45	0.9398496240601504	0.4647887323943662	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000008v2_random_56	267	213	7.5e-36	116.5	92498	93298	56	0.37453183520599254	0.352112676056338	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000008v2_random_57	202	213	7.5e-36	116.5	93335	93940	57	0.7029702970297029	0.5821596244131455	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL000008v2_random_32	294	298	7.5e-36	116.5	28220	29101	32	0.4897959183673469	0.4228187919463087	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL000008v2_random_57	202	298	7.5e-36	116.5	93335	93940	57	0.5495049504950495	0.35570469798657717	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5_2_CAS-I-B	chr5_GL000208v1_random_251	47	194	0.00087	13.3	85337	85477	251	0.9361702127659575	0.24742268041237114	1
Cas5_2_CAS-I-B	chr5_GL000208v1_random_257	47	194	0.00074	13.6	87551	87691	257	0.9361702127659575	0.24742268041237114	1

Cas8a2_0_CAS-I-A	chr5_GL000208v1_random_224	130	329	0.00025	14.2	76063	76452	224	0.7846153846153846	0.2887537993920973	1
Cas8a2_0_CAS-I-A	chr5_GL000208v1_random_237	130	329	0.0002	14.5	80490	80879	237	0.7923076923076923	0.2917933130699088	1
Cas8a2_0_CAS-I-A	chr5_GL000208v1_random_262	130	329	0.00037	13.6	89345	89734	262	0.7692307692307693	0.2826747720364742	1
Cas8a2_0_CAS-I-A	chr5_GL000208v1_random_269	130	329	0.00033	13.8	91559	91948	269	0.7692307692307693	0.2826747720364742	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr5_GL000208v1_random_112	218	180	0.065	7.1	34255	34908	112	0.4954128440366973	0.35	-1
CorA_1_CAS-III-B	chr5_GL000208v1_random_189	96	125	0.0033	11.4	62180	62467	189	0.6666666666666666	0.496	-1
PD_DExK_2_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL000208v1_random_112	218	127	0.018	8.7	34255	34908	112	0.37155963302752293	0.3543307086614173	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL000208v1_random_106	330	213	1.90E-20	119.7	31227	32216	106	0.5848484848484848	0.7511737089201878	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL000208v1_random_107	152	213	7.7e-12	39.3	32183	32638	107	0.34868421052631576	0.22535211267605634	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL000208v1_random_185	341	213	4.90E-17	108.6	58684	59706	185	0.5249266862170088	0.6854460093896714	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL000208v1_random_186	149	213	7.1e-14	46.0	59758	60204	186	0.3691275167785235	0.2347417840375587	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL000208v1_random_204	110	213	4.5e-17	56.4	69048	69377	204	0.8363636363636363	0.38967136150234744	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL000208v1_random_88	119	213	3.6e-14	46.9	25695	26051	88	0.6470588235294118	0.352112676056338	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL000208v1_random_106	330	298	3.7e-11	36.5	31227	32216	106	0.4757575757575757	0.4697986577181208	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL000208v1_random_185	341	298	1.4e-08	28.0	58684	59706	185	0.41935483870967744	0.41946308724832215	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL000208v1_random_204	110	298	8.00E-06	18.9	69048	69377	204	0.8	0.2751677852348993	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL000208v1_random_88	119	298	0.00011	15.1	25695	26051	88	0.2605042016806723	0.1040268456375839	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas11b_2_CAS-I-B	chr9_K1270719v1_random_37	122	100	0.00028	15.5	56371	56736	37	0.6065573770491803	0.78	1
Cas5_0_I	chr9_K1270717v1_random_22	74	43	0.0074	10.6	17748	17969	22	0.32432432432432434	0.5348837209302325	1
Csx27_0_CAS-VI-B	chr9_K1270719v1_random_54	120	238	0.0019	12.8	75786	76145	54	0.8166666666666667	0.4117647058823529	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270719v1_random_13	129	213	1.1e-13	45.8	17249	17635	13	0.7054263565891473	0.3051643192488263	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270719v1_random_167	172	213	9.6e-27	88.5	132126	132641	167	0.7906976744186046	0.5539906103286385	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270720v1_random_11	100	213	2.5e-11	38.1	5749	6048	11	0.96	0.323943661971831	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270720v1_random_12	91	213	5.4e-10	33.8	6048	6320	12	0.7032967032967034	0.23943661971830985	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270720v1_random_23	184	213	1.40E-12	94.5	13382	13933	23	0.9130434782608695	0.7089201877934272	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr9_K1270720v1_random_24	111	213	1.00E-12	42.6	13934	14266	24	0.4594594594594595	0.215962441314554	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr9_K1270719v1_random_167	172	298	1.00E-09	32.2	132126	132641	167	0.5872093023255814	0.3221476510067114	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr9_K1270720v1_random_23	184	298	2.9e-05	17.6	13382	13933	23	0.8478260869565217	0.4664429530201342	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270766v1_alt_108	394	213	5.3e-06	19.0	236262	237443	108	0.1598984771573604	0.26291079812206575	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270766v1_alt_64	326	213	1.00E-43	142.3	131522	132499	64	0.6809815950920245	0.9107981220657277	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_K1270766v1_alt_64	326	298	4.00E-09	28.6	131522	132499	64	0.656441717791411	0.6375838926174496	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas2_11_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270760v1_alt_18	173	71	0.00032	13.2	89173	89691	18	0.23699421965317918	0.5774647887323944	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr1_K1270760v1_alt_19	339	180	0.0094	8.1	91927	92943	19	0.2890855457227139	0.3611111111111111	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270760v1_alt_21	707	213	7.80E-23	122.5	94715	96835	21	0.272984441301273	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270760v1_alt_26	324	213	2.4e-51	166.6	108297	109268	26	0.7067901234567902	0.9483568075117371	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_K1270760v1_alt_21	707	298	9.00E-12	36.7	94715	96835	21	0.24752475247524752	0.5302013422818792	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_K1270760v1_alt_26	324	298	8.9e-15	46.6	108297	109268	26	0.6574074074074074	0.6342281879194631	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csx21_0_CAS-III-A	chr1_GL383519v1_alt_82	78	210	0.0022	12.2	48028	48261	82	0.5769230769230769	0.21428571428571427	-1
TniQ_1_I-F	chr1_GL383519v1_alt_128	76	400	0.0022	12.2	79563	79790	128	0.2631578947368421	0.05	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand

Csf3_0_IV	chr1_GL383520v2_alt_50	64	222	0.0024	12.1	46247	46438	50	0.84375	0.24324324324324326	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_GL383520v2_alt_114	123	213	0.0024	12.1	105349	105717	114	0.8292682926829268	0.3568075117370892	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270764v1_alt_3	143	213	1.1e-21	66.0	28897	29325	3	0.916083916083916	0.5446009389671361	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_K1270764v1_alt_3	143	298	1.1e-21	66.0	28897	29325	3	0.8321678321678322	0.348993288590604	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csx23_0_CAS-III-D	chr1_K1270763v1_alt_646	82	130	0.0075	11.5	688360	688605	646	0.5609756097560976	0.3384615384615385	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270763v1_alt_635	190	213	0.0075	11.5	672478	673047	635	0.9631578947368421	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270763v1_alt_732	176	213	0.0075	11.5	822983	823510	732	0.9375	0.6948356807511737	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_K1270763v1_alt_635	190	298	0.0075	11.5	672478	673047	635	0.8315789473684211	0.47315436241610737	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr1_K1270763v1_alt_732	176	298	0.0075	11.5	822983	823510	732	0.8636363636363636	0.4563758389261745	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270759v1_alt_497	85	213	0.00038	15.4	323035	323289	497	0.7411764705882353	0.24882629107981222	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr2_K1270770v1_alt_86	339	180	0.089	6.6	76390	77406	86	0.2949852507374631	0.39444444444444443	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr1_K1270761v1_alt_72	106	213	5.8e-13	42.9	116783	117100	72	0.8773584905660378	0.39906103286384975	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270770v1_alt_88	479	213	7.30E-38	173.3	78750	80186	88	0.5365344467640919	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_K1270770v1_alt_88	479	298	4.9e-13	42.6	78750	80186	88	0.44676409185803756	0.6375838926174496	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csx24_0_CAS-III-D	chr2_K1270774v1_alt_156	116	149	0.00027	15.1	207278	207625	156	0.5258620689655172	0.28859060402684567	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270774v1_alt_134	730	213	2.4e-52	171.7	189476	191665	134	0.39315068493150684	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270774v1_alt_33	242	213	3.4e-24	79.7	67267	67992	33	0.49586776859504134	0.4413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270774v1_alt_36	315	213	4.7e-24	79.2	74367	75311	36	0.39365079365079364	0.460093896713615	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_K1270774v1_alt_134	730	298	4.6e-14	46.0	189476	191665	134	0.3958904109589041	0.8456375838926175	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_K1270774v1_alt_33	242	298	1.7e-06	21.1	67267	67992	33	0.35537190082644626	0.2483221476510067	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_K1270774v1_alt_36	315	298	5.2e-06	19.6	74367	75311	36	0.273015873015873	0.2483221476510067	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr2_GL383521v1_alt_20	339	180	0.31	4.9	21103	22119	20	0.35103244837758113	0.4388888888888889	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_GL383521v1_alt_21	1239	213	5.00E-38	177.2	22294	26010	21	0.20742534301856336	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_GL383521v1_alt_21	1239	298	3.7e-12	39.8	22294	26010	21	0.23163841807909605	0.8456375838926175	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas1_3_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270772v1_alt_95	138	262	0.0033	10.9	18190	18603	95	0.34782608695652173	0.183206106870229	-1
Cmr5gr11_9_CAS-III-B	chr2_K1270772v1_alt_135	106	137	0.00071	13.3	48919	49236	135	0.5283018867924528	0.41605839416058393	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270772v1_alt_136	366	213	2.9e-33	109.5	49812	50909	136	0.5218579234972678	0.7417840375586855	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270775v1_alt_34	70	213	1.5e-09	32.0	59076	59285	34	0.7571428571428571	0.2300469483568075	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270775v1_alt_35	90	213	1.6e-19	64.6	59322	59591	35	0.9666666666666667	0.3755868544600939	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270775v1_alt_77	692	213	1.2e-51	169.5	133753	135828	77	0.4147398843930636	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_K1270772v1_alt_136	366	298	1.2e-09	31.7	49812	50909	136	0.45901639344262296	0.5033557046979866	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_K1270775v1_alt_35	90	298	3.3e-09	30.3	59322	59591	35	0.9555555555555556	0.2684563758389262	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_K1270775v1_alt_77	692	298	2.4e-11	37.3	133753	135828	77	0.41329479768786126	0.8456375838926175	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8a2_2_CAS-I-A	chr2_K1270771v1_alt_2	148	357	0.00013	14.5	5284	5727	2	0.43243243243243246	0.16526610644257703	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_K1270771v1_alt_16	325	213	0.00013	14.5	55162	56136	16	0.7046153846153846	0.9436619718309859	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_K1270771v1_alt_16	325	298	0.00013	14.5	55162	56136	16	0.6584615384615384	0.6375838926174496	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr2_GL582966v2_alt_7	305	180	0.054	5.3	28066	28980	7	0.3836065573770492	0.5111111111111111	-1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_GL383522v1_alt_13	257	213	3.1e-33	107.2	38253	39023	13	0.6147859922178989	0.6572769953051644	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_GL383522v1_alt_24	122	213	3.9e-07	21.9	55240	55605	24	0.27049180327868855	0.13145539906103287	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_GL383522v1_alt_25	223	213	3.80E-20	116.7	55663	56331	25	0.8654708520179372	0.7511737089201878	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr2_GL582966v2_alt_6	1239	213	4.5e-55	178.5	24175	27891	6	0.20742534301856336	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_GL383522v1_alt_13	257	298	1.8e-11	35.4	38253	39023	13	0.5758754863813229	0.4597315436241611	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_GL383522v1_alt_25	223	298	7.7e-11	33.4	55663	56331	25	0.7040358744394619	0.4697986577181208	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr2_GL582966v2_alt_6	1239	298	7.00E-14	43.3	24175	27891	6	0.23163841807909605	0.8456375838926175	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csx19_3_CAS-III-D	chr2_KI270776v1_alt_15	202	160	1.3	1.4	19097	19702	15	0.6683168316831684	0.19375	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csf1_0_IV	chr2_KI270767v1_alt_118	379	227	0.0027	10.9	90615	91751	118	0.11873350923482849	0.06607929515418502	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_JH636055v2_alt_33	74	213	1.8e-10	33.2	91903	92124	33	0.7432432432432432	0.24882629107981222	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_JH636055v2_alt_49	121	213	1.8e-10	33.2	123682	124044	49	0.2727272727272727	0.13145539906103287	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_JH636055v2_alt_50	186	213	1.8e-10	33.2	124102	124659	50	0.8978494623655914	0.6901408450704225	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270783v1_alt_13	467	213	1.8e-10	33.2	81693	83093	13	0.550321199143469	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270783v1_alt_7	72	213	1.8e-10	33.2	13211	13426	7	0.8472222222222222	0.27230046948356806	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_JH636055v2_alt_33	74	298	1.8e-10	33.2	91903	92124	33	0.6756756756756757	0.17114093959731544	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_JH636055v2_alt_50	186	298	1.8e-10	33.2	124102	124659	50	0.8387096774193549	0.4664429530201342	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_KI270783v1_alt_13	467	298	1.8e-10	33.2	81693	83093	13	0.4603854389721627	0.6442953020134228	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270780v1_alt_12	164	213	9.4e-16	49.3	53127	53618	12	0.6402439024390244	0.6572769953051644	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270780v1_alt_17	194	213	9.4e-16	49.3	75758	76339	17	0.7628865979381443	0.8591549295774648	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8a3_1_CAS-I-A	chr3_GL383526v1_alt_53	101	294	0.00029	12.6	99896	100198	53	0.3465346534653465	0.11904761904761904	1
Cmr5_1_IIIC	chr3_GL383526v1_alt_82	169	178	0.00029	12.6	159793	160299	82	0.48520710059171596	0.4550561797752809	-1
Cmr5gr11_10_CAS-III-B	chr3_GL383526v1_alt_43	155	146	0.00029	12.6	89025	89489	43	0.23225806451612904	0.2465753424657534	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr3_GL383526v1_alt_82	169	180	0.00029	12.6	159793	160299	82	0.5029585798816568	0.4444444444444444	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_GL383526v1_alt_42	309	213	0.00029	12.6	87783	88709	42	0.5339805825242718	0.9906103286384976	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_GL383526v1_alt_61	99	213	0.00029	12.6	124318	124614	61	0.2323232323232323	0.13145539906103287	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_GL383526v1_alt_62	96	213	0.00029	12.6	124636	124923	62	0.9479166666666666	0.4788732394366197	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_GL383526v1_alt_42	309	298	0.00029	12.6	87783	88709	42	0.22006472491909385	0.2348993288590604	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas12a_M11_0_V-A	chr3_KI270777v1_alt_24	131	1241	3.2e-05	13.5	64548	64940	24	0.6412213740458015	0.06768734891216761	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270777v1_alt_4	217	213	3.2e-05	13.5	14999	15649	4	0.8847926267281107	0.7417840375586855	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_KI270777v1_alt_4	217	298	3.2e-05	13.5	14999	15649	4	0.6682027649769585	0.4261744966442953	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8b5_0_CAS-I-B	chr3_KI270778v1_alt_54	76	825	0.69	1.1	75591	75818	54	0.6447368421052632	0.06060606060606061	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270778v1_alt_120	104	213	2.00E-08	27.5	185646	185957	120	0.8076923076923077	0.3568075117370892	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270778v1_alt_38	201	213	2.9e-44	144.7	57868	58470	38	0.9651741293532339	0.784037558685446	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270778v1_alt_55	304	213	3.3e-47	154.3	81541	82452	55	0.819078947368421	0.9906103286384976	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr3_KI270778v1_alt_71	69	213	3.1e-07	23.6	100661	100867	71	0.7536231884057971	0.24413145539906103	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_KI270778v1_alt_38	201	298	1.4e-13	43.7	57868	58470	38	0.7860696517412935	0.49328859060402686	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr3_KI270778v1_alt_55	304	298	4.3e-11	35.6	81541	82452	55	0.5789473684210527	0.5503355704697986	-1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas10_0_III	chr4_KI270790v1_alt_232	140	414	0.00096	12.1	205571	205990	232	0.6142857142857143	0.1932367149758454	1
Cas10_7_CAS-III	chr4_KI270790v1_alt_232	140	410	0.00096	12.1	205571	205990	232	0.6285714285714286	0.2097560975609756	1
Cas8a1_0_IB	chr4_KI270790v1_alt_34	71	308	0.00096	12.1	26422	26634	34	0.39436619718309857	0.09090909090909091	-1
Cmr5_1_IIIC	chr4_KI270790v1_alt_232	140	178	0.00096	12.1	205571	205990	232	0.34285714285714286	0.2696629213483146	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL383528v1_alt_61	190	213	2.30E-06	73.5	106479	107048	61	0.5210526315789473	0.4131455399061033	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL383528v1_alt_78	653	213	2.30E-06	73.5	134702	136660	78	0.39356814701378257	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL383528v1_alt_78	653	298	2.30E-06	73.5	134702	136660	78	0.327718223583461	0.6375838926174496	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_KI270787v1_alt_5	362	213	1.1e-06	17.3	32224	33309	5	0.17955801104972377	0.26291079812206575	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_119	103	213	2.1e-08	28.3	218244	218552	119	0.7378640776699029	0.27699530516431925	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_152	117	213	2.1e-08	28.3	255714	256064	152	0.9658119658119658	0.4507042253521127	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_202	212	213	2.1e-08	28.3	325476	326111	202	0.589622641509434	0.6666666666666666	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_215	168	213	2.1e-08	28.3	345683	346186	215	0.4523809523809524	0.27699530516431925	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_217	257	213	2.1e-08	28.3	346625	347395	217	0.12840466926070038	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_229	76	213	2.1e-08	28.3	370959	371186	229	0.9736842105263158	0.2676056338028169	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_270	125	213	2.1e-08	28.3	460566	460940	270	0.928	0.4225352112676056	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_279	110	213	2.1e-08	28.3	479657	479986	279	0.8818181818181818	0.4788732394366197	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_321	466	213	2.1e-08	28.3	567387	568784	321	0.34334763948497854	0.596244131455399	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_68	181	213	2.1e-08	28.3	117451	117993	68	0.8011049723756906	0.596244131455399	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_152	117	298	2.1e-08	28.3	255714	256064	152	0.27350427350427353	0.10738255033557047	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_202	212	298	2.1e-08	28.3	325476	326111	202	0.4009433962264151	0.2785234899328859	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_270	125	298	2.1e-08	28.3	460566	460940	270	0.696	0.2516778523489933	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_279	110	298	2.1e-08	28.3	479657	479986	279	0.5	0.1912751677852349	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_321	466	298	2.1e-08	28.3	567387	568784	321	0.1888412017167382	0.2550335570469799	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_GL000257v2_alt_68	181	298	2.1e-08	28.3	117451	117993	68	0.6077348066298343	0.3523489932885906	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr4_KI270788v1_alt_13	272	180	0.038	3.9	96989	97804	13	0.4227941176470588	0.4388888888888889	-1
Csm2gr11_7_CAS-III-A	chr4_KI270788v1_alt_13	272	110	0.0026	8.9	96989	97804	13	0.35294117647058826	0.8090909090909091	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_KI270788v1_alt_10	496	213	1.5e-23	73.6	93283	94770	10	0.3024193548387097	0.5821596244131455	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr4_KI270788v1_alt_11	201	213	2.5e-24	76.2	94839	95441	11	0.5373134328358209	0.45539906103286387	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_KI270788v1_alt_10	496	298	9.6e-07	18.0	93283	94770	10	0.3084677419354839	0.412751677852349	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr4_KI270788v1_alt_11	201	298	1.2e-07	21.0	94839	95441	11	0.472636815920398	0.30201342281879195	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csm6_5_CAS-III	chr4_KI270789v1_alt_31	98	278	0.00043	11.2	168631	168924	31	0.7040816326530612	0.15467625899280577	-1
Csm6_5_CAS-III	chr4_KI270789v1_alt_40	98	278	0.00043	11.2	170322	170615	40	0.6836734693877551	0.15467625899280577	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8c_2_CAS-I-C	chr4_KI270786v1_alt_57	654	713	1.5e-05	15.6	184103	186064	57	0.9434250764525994	0.2005610098176718	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas2_10_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_KI270793v1_alt_2	191	86	8.5e-05	14.5	15823	16395	2	0.5287958115183246	0.7093023255813954	1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL949742v1_alt_153	94	213	7.7e-14	45.4	160858	161139	153	0.8404255319148937	0.30985915492957744	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL949742v1_alt_154	178	213	7.7e-14	45.4	161195	161728	154	0.39325842696629215	0.2676056338028169	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL949742v1_alt_16	316	213	7.7e-14	45.4	21153	22100	16	0.7531645569620253	0.9342723004694836	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL949742v1_alt_48	86	213	7.7e-14	45.4	50617	50874	48	0.6744186046511628	0.2535211267605634	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL949742v1_alt_79	112	213	7.7e-14	45.4	82245	82580	79	0.8392857142857143	0.38028169014084506	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL949742v1_alt_153	94	298	7.7e-14	45.4	160858	161139	153	0.35106382978723405	0.11073825503355705	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL949742v1_alt_16	316	298	7.7e-14	45.4	21153	22100	16	0.5063291139240507	0.4798657718120805	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL949742v1_alt_79	112	298	7.7e-14	45.4	82245	82580	79	0.42857142857142855	0.1610738255033557	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csx3_0_CAS-I-III	chr5_K1270794v1_alt_4	244	83	9	-21.9	50266	50997	4	0.45081967213114754	0.24096385542168675	-1
Mem_04_0_CAS-III-D	chr5_K1270794v1_alt_4	244	241	9	-37.2	50266	50997	4	0.4426229508196721	0.2946058091286307	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5f_1_CAS-I-F	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_1121	54	293	0.0031	13.1	1409276	1409437	1121	0.6666666666666666	0.12286689419795221	-1
Cas8f_3_CAS-I-F	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_669	1254	376	0.12	7.9	632419	636180	669	0.10047846889952153	0.11702127659574468	1
Cas8f_3_CAS-I-F	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_684	1254	376	0.1	8.0	652872	656633	684	0.10127591706539076	0.11702127659574468	1
Cas8f_3_CAS-I-F	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_847	1522	376	0.63	5.4	921241	925806	847	0.10972404730617609	0.11436170212765957	-1
Csy2_0_IF	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_1121	54	296	0.0031	13.0	1409276	1409437	1121	0.6666666666666666	0.12162162162162163	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_1288	647	213	1.00E-53	178.4	1604284	1606224	1288	0.3972179289026275	1.0	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_524	254	213	5.6e-21	71.4	452564	453325	524	0.4015748031496063	0.4272300469483568	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_525	289	213	1.7e-19	66.6	453422	454288	525	0.41522491349480967	0.4413145539906103	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_701	162	213	1.7e-17	60.0	686699	687184	701	0.6975308641975309	0.4084507042253521	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_815	162	213	1.7e-17	60.0	872635	873120	815	0.6975308641975309	0.4084507042253521	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_1288	647	298	1.4e-12	43.3	1604284	1606224	1288	0.33075734157650694	0.6375838926174496	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL339449v2_alt_524	254	298	0.00024	16.3	452564	453325	524	0.3661417322834646	0.2953020134228188	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
CasR_0_CAS-III-B-III-D	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_111	62	255	0.0022	11.5	119456	119641	111	0.5806451612903226	0.1411764705882353	-1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_84	153	180	0.041	7.7	84199	84657	84	0.6601307189542484	0.3388888888888889	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL383530v1_alt_35	187	213	1.2e-27	90.9	41110	41670	35	0.8502673796791443	0.5915492957746479	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL383530v1_alt_59	326	213	2.10E-32	158.7	57876	58853	59	0.6901840490797546	0.9248826291079812	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL383530v1_alt_6	101	213	3.8e-22	72.9	6091	6393	6	0.9405940594059405	0.39906103286384975	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_160	215	213	2.8e-32	106.0	171967	172611	160	0.7581395348837209	0.6807511737089202	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_72	182	213	2.3e-12	41.0	74160	74705	72	0.7692307692307693	0.5211267605633803	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_80	493	213	1.1e-36	120.5	80415	81893	80	0.4239350912778905	0.7981220657276995	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_81	92	213	1.00E-06	22.5	81933	82208	81	0.358695652173913	0.13145539906103287	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL383530v1_alt_35	187	298	1.4e-06	21.4	41110	41670	35	0.47593582887700536	0.25838926174496646	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL383530v1_alt_59	326	298	5.4e-12	39.2	57876	58853	59	0.49693251533742333	0.5067114093959731	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL383530v1_alt_6	101	298	8.6e-07	22.1	6091	6393	6	0.8613861386138614	0.2516778523489933	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_160	215	298	2.9e-11	36.8	171967	172611	160	0.7209302325581395	0.48322147651006714	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_72	182	298	0.0014	11.6	74160	74705	72	0.38461538461538464	0.2348993288590604	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_K1270796v1_alt_80	493	298	7.5e-10	32.1	80415	81893	80	0.3204868154158215	0.47315436241610737	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas8a3_1_CAS-I-A	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_28	91	294	0.00078	11.9	98176	98448	28	0.3076923076923077	0.09523809523809523	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_15	320	213	2.2e-37	121.9	67845	68804	15	0.721875	0.9436619718309859	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_20	393	213	7.1e-24	77.7	81965	83143	20	0.2951653944020356	0.49295774647887325	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_21	229	213	1.5e-23	76.7	83146	83832	21	0.5152838427947598	0.431924882629108	1

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_4	540	213	9.2e-38	123.1	12369	13988	4	0.3537037037037037	0.8028169014084507	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_15	320	298	6.6e-13	41.3	67845	68804	15	0.490625	0.4697986577181208	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_20	393	298	3.1e-06	19.4	81965	83143	20	0.33587786259541985	0.4228187919463087	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_21	229	298	1.1e-06	20.8	83146	83832	21	0.36681222707423583	0.24161073825503357	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr5_GL383531v1_alt_4	540	298	1.4e-11	37.0	12369	13988	4	0.4074074074074074	0.6677852348993288	1

Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas12a_M11_0_V-A	chr6_K1270799v1_alt_7	130	1241	1.3e-05	14.5	26814	27203	7	0.6307692307692307	0.06607574536663981	1
Cmr5_1_IIC	chr6_GL383533v1_alt_17	146	178	0.055	4.8	108685	109122	17	0.6986301369863014	0.5674157303370787	1
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr6_K1270799v1_alt_2	295	180	0.038	5.3	22200	23084	2	0.30847457627118646	0.48333333333333334	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL383533v1_alt_18	51	213	5.5e-05	14.4	109503	109655	18	0.9019607843137255	0.18779342723004694	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_GL383533v1_alt_25	152	213	5.8e-26	82.9	123699	124154	25	0.881578947368421	0.5446009389671361	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270799v1_alt_10	282	213	5.50E-23	125.5	37680	38525	10	0.7411347517730497	0.7981220657276995	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270799v1_alt_14	92	213	1.9e-10	32.3	51636	51911	14	0.8913043478260869	0.3427230046948357	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270799v1_alt_5	282	213	2.40E-23	126.7	24836	25681	5	0.7411347517730497	0.7981220657276995	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_GL383533v1_alt_25	152	298	2.3e-09	28.0	123699	124154	25	0.631578947368421	0.30201342281879195	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_K1270799v1_alt_10	282	298	7.5e-15	46.1	37680	38525	10	0.5780141843971631	0.4899328859060403	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_K1270799v1_alt_5	282	298	5.4e-13	40.0	24836	25681	5	0.5602836879432624	0.47315436241610737	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas12f2_2_CAS-V-F	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_387	117	493	0.0016	12.4	483799	484149	387	0.358974358974359	0.0872210953346856	-1
Cmr5_1_IIC	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_124	121	178	0.015	10.5	144483	144845	124	0.2644628099173554	0.1797752808988764	-1
Csn2_13_CAS-II-A	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_588	58	180	0.0024	12.9	774127	774300	588	0.6206896551724138	0.2	1
Csx1_5_CAS-III	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_188	68	132	0.0006	15.3	217745	217948	188	0.5147058823529411	0.26515151515151514	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_113	84	213	1.3e-09	33.3	134799	135050	113	0.8214285714285714	0.29577464788732394	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_114	158	213	6.8e-16	53.9	134992	135465	114	0.8037974683544303	0.5164319248826291	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_13	327	213	5.70E-33	162.0	14399	15379	13	0.7033639143730887	0.9436619718309859	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_144	126	213	0.0021	13.0	161395	161772	144	0.373015873015873	0.2112676056338028	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_168	96	213	7.2e-16	53.8	192393	192680	168	0.9583333333333334	0.38497652582159625	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_21	93	213	3.2e-07	25.5	22665	22943	21	0.7849462365591398	0.3145539906103286	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_226	316	213	1.2e-47	157.7	275107	276054	226	0.7531645569620253	0.9342723004694836	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_438	44	213	2.6e-07	25.8	552316	552447	438	0.8636363636363636	0.1784037558685446	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_501	75	213	3.1e-14	48.4	647779	648003	501	0.9866666666666667	0.3192488262910798	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_502	262	213	2.00E-12	94.9	648010	648795	502	0.6106870229007634	0.596244131455399	1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_94	96	213	2.00E-05	19.6	116034	116321	94	0.5520833333333334	0.20187793427230047	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_114	158	298	0.00056	14.2	134992	135465	114	0.1962025316455696	0.1040268456375839	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_13	327	298	3.4e-12	41.2	14399	15379	13	0.654434250764526	0.6409395973154363	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_168	96	298	1.4e-05	19.4	192393	192680	168	0.8854166666666666	0.24496644295302014	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_226	316	298	3.00E-12	41.4	275107	276054	226	0.5031645569620253	0.47651006711409394	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr6_K1270801v1_alt_502	262	298	1.7e-06	22.5	648010	648795	502	0.4122137404580153	0.3221476510067114	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cas5_1_CAS-I	chr6_K1270798v1_alt_188	186	241	0.074	6.5	204766	205323	188	0.22043010752688172	0.1078838174273859	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand

RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr7_KI270804v1_alt_2	839	213	3.8e-55	179.5	3214	5730	2	0.3063170441001192	1.0	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr7_KI270804v1_alt_2	839	298	3.8e-55	179.5	3214	5730	2	0.2550655542312277	0.6409395973154363	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr7_KI270809v1_alt_52	279	213	2.40E-19	115.0	49456	50292	52	0.7562724014336918	0.8497652582159625	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr7_KI270809v1_alt_53	86	213	2.2e-14	46.5	50356	50613	53	0.6162790697674418	0.22535211267605634	-1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr7_KI270809v1_alt_52	279	298	3.4e-11	35.4	49456	50292	52	0.5125448028673835	0.41946308724832215	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Csf2_0_IV	chr7_KI270806v1_alt_116	79	329	0.0052	11.0	76281	76517	116	0.27848101265822783	0.0668693009118541	-1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr7_KI270803v1_alt_1001	219	213	3.7e-23	78.3	1002954	1003610	1001	0.867579908675799	0.7323943661971831	-1
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr7_KI270803v1_alt_1082	140	213	3.7e-23	78.3	1104958	1105377	1082	0.8142857142857143	0.4694835680751174	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr7_KI270803v1_alt_1082	140	298	3.7e-23	78.3	1104958	1105377	1082	0.22857142857142856	0.10738255033557047	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
Cmr5gr11_1_CAS-III-C	chr7_KI270808v1_alt_135	190	180	2.6	1.4	209342	209911	135	0.6263157894736842	0.5	1
Hmm	ORF	tlen	qlen	Eval	score	start	end	Pos	Cov_seq	Cov_hmm	strand
RT_0_CAS-I-II-III-IV-V-VI	chr14_GL000225v1_random_432	318	213	5.8e-39	128.7	145524	146477	432	0.7358490566037735	0.9154929577464789	1
RT_0_CAS-III-AM-III-B	chr14_GL000225v1_random_432	318	298	5.8e-39	128.7	145524	146477	432	0.4937106918238994	0.4697986577181208	1

222

223

224 **Methods**

225 The genomic sequence of all standard autosomal and sex chromosomes (chr1 to chrY) of the human
226 reference genome (Hg19, Hg38 and T2T CHM13v2.0/hs1) was analyzed using the stand-alone CRISPR
227 identification software tools CRISPRFinder, CRISPRCasFinder and CRISPRCasTyper using default
228 settings and is described earlier³. Related to Figure 1 the identified *cas* cluster in the CRISPRCasFinder
229 software was obtained by analysing the region hg19_dna range=chrY:4904392-5944391 and hg38_dna
230 range=chrY:5036351-6076350 by selecting in the CAS settings; 1) perform *cas* gene detection; 2)
231 clustering model general permissive; 3) unordered and 4) search *cas* only when CRISPR detected. For
232 identification of *cas* gene signatures (remnants) we retrieved the flanking regions 20,000 bp upstream
233 or downstream of the hCRISPR and applied the 3D uniprot BLAST tool
234 (<https://www.uniprot.org/blast/>) using settings UniProtKB with 3D structure (PDB) and advanced
235 parameters set at sequence type (protein), program (blastP), E-threshold (1000), Matrix (Auto-
236 BLOSUM62), Filter (none), Gapped (Yes) and Hits (1000)